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**DIGITAL MAPPING OF SOIL PROPERTIES WITH
APPLICATION FOR SUSTAINABLE INTENSIFICATION
OF AGRICULTURE IN CAMEROON**

THESIS

Submitted in fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in
Soil Sciences

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Digital mapping of soil properties with application for sustainable intensification of agriculture in Cameroon

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Doctorate / Ph.D. Defense Report of Mr. SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice

In respect of authorization N° B14/06942/UDs/R/ED/D/VR-RECOME/DAAC/DRD/BuER of 23th November 2020, by the Vice Chancellor of the University of Dschang, **Mr. SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice** publicly defended his Ph.D. thesis titled '**DIGITAL MAPPING OF SOIL PROPERTIES WITH APPLICATION FOR SUSTAINABLE INTENSIFICATION OF AGRICULTURE IN CAMEROON**' on Tuesday, December 1 2020, in the Dschang School of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Hall of the University of Dschang.

The study intended to investigate the applicability of digital soil mapping methods on legacy soil data for inventorying soil resource information in Cameroon as input for sustainable intensification of agricultural production and estimation of agroecosystem services.

A harmonized soil profile database (Camsodat 0.1) has been developed, which contains currently 5, 050 layers distributed over 1600 georeferenced positions. A total of 5.67 Pg of SOCS is stored in the first one-meter of soil in Cameroon, with 50% in the top 30 cm, and national estimates of key soil properties are available at a high spatial resolution (100 m). An evaluation of soil properties and climatic factors revealed pieces of land suitable for cocoa-production with varying levels of suitability and requiring site-specific management approaches. Although there are some gaps in soil survey across Cameroon, DSM has a high potential to close these gaps with an acceptable accuracy (68%) for most properties, which therefore provides a basis for its use in sustainable agricultural intensification and decision-making on climate change mitigation in Cameroon.

After examining the thesis that was submitted for review and listening to the oral presentation (40 mins, using ICT tools), the jury appreciated the excellent quality of the thesis, the pertinence of the subject, its originality and the relevance of the results obtained as well as the mastery of the subject matter. Equally, the responses provided to the questions asked by the jury were satisfactory.

The jury after deliberation, accepted unanimously the thesis presented by Mr. SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice and conferred on him the title Doctor/Ph.D. in Soil Science, with a "Mention **TRES HONORABLE**".

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ATTESTATION OF CORRECTION OF THESIS

We, the undersigned, testify that the Doctorate/Ph.D thesis entitled “**Digital mapping of soil properties with application for sustainable intensification of agriculture in Cameroon**” that was publicly defended by **Mr. SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice** (Registration number: CM04-10ASA0762) on December 1, 2020 in the DSAES Hall (Campus: Ecole Doctorale) of the University of Dschang for the award of a Doctorate/Ph.D Degree in Soil Science, has been corrected according to the remarks and recommendations of the jury. In witness whereof this attestation is issued to serve the purposes for which it is intended.

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CERTIFICATE OF ORIGINALITY

I, the undersigned, **SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice**, hereby certify that this thesis was written by me and it is a record of my research work carried out at the **University of Dschang** under the supervision of **Pr. TABI Fritz OBEN** and **Dr. YEMEFACK Martin**. This thesis is original and has not been presented before in any previous application for a higher degree.

Signature of the candidate

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of several overlapping loops and lines, positioned below the text 'Signature of the candidate'.

SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice

Date: 05/01/2021

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated

to God almighty,

my parents,

and my wife.

DECLARATION

I, **SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice** hereby certify that I am the sole author of this thesis done with the counselling of my supervisors. To the best of my knowledge, this thesis does not infringe upon anyone's copyright or violate any proprietary rights. Any ideas, techniques, quotations, or any other material from the work of other people included in this thesis, published or otherwise, are fully acknowledged.

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for a degree to any other University or Institution of Higher Education.

SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice
(Student)

05/01/2021
Date

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ABSTRACT

Although soil survey is required to guide agricultural land use planning and management in Cameroon, attention on it has been limited, thus creating gaps in soil resource inventory. However, with the availability of well compiled legacy soil data, nationwide reliable thematic soil properties maps, with high accuracy can be produced using digital soil mapping tools, and effectively used to guide decision making in agroecosystems. This study aimed at investigating the applicability of digital soil mapping (DSM) methods on legacy soil data for inventorying soil resources at 1-ha spatial resolution in Cameroon. Specific objectives were to (i) rescue, compile and harmonize the soil profile database; (ii) assess and map the distribution of some key soil properties (pH, Ca, Mg, K, SOC, N, P, CEC, Sand, Silt, Clay, and textural classes); (iii) assess the countrywide distribution of soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) down to 100 cm depth, and (iv) appraise the DSM methodology for applications in sustainable intensification of cocoa production in Cameroon. The spatial distribution of soil properties was predicted using machine learning algorithms at internationally recognized standard soil depths (0 – 5 cm, 5 – 15 cm, 15 – 30 cm, 30 – 60 cm, 60 – 100 cm, and 100 – 200 cm). The harmonized soil profile database (Camsodat 0.1) contains currently about 5250 layers which are unevenly distributed over 1600 georeferenced positions across the country. Prediction models estimated the national distribution of soil properties, with good performances (R^2 up to 68%). Terrain and climate attributes were the most relevant environmental factors to predict soil properties distribution across the Country. The national distribution of SOCS was consistent with the pattern of agroecological zones. In total, about 5.67 Pg of SOCS is stored in the first 100 cm depth of soil in Cameroon, with 50% in the top 30 cm depth. Land evaluation revealed pieces of soils suitable for cocoa-production with varying levels of suitability and requiring site-specific management approaches. Generally, for cocoa production, 9%, of the area is highly suitable, 78% moderately suitable, and 13% marginal suitable. Five (5) soil properties mostly affecting cocoa productivity in decreasing order of importance are $OC > Clay > Mg > pH > Silt$. Although there are some gaps in soil survey across Cameroon, DSM showed a high potential to close such gaps, and the versatility in determining SOCS down to 100 cm depth and applicability in soil suitability analysis for intensification of cocoa production in Cameroon.

Keywords: Legacy soil data, Digital soil mapping, Soil properties, sustainable agriculture, soil suitability

RESUME

Bien que l'étude des sols soit nécessaire pour guider la planification et la gestion de l'utilisation des terres agricoles, la connaissance des sols du Cameroun reste limitée. Par ailleurs, la disponibilité de données pédologiques anciennes permet de développer des cartes thématiques fiables des propriétés des sols à l'échelle nationale grâce aux outils cartographie numériques pouvant être efficacement utilisées faciliter la prise de décision dans les agroécosystèmes. Cette étude visait à évaluer l'applicabilité des méthodes de cartographie numérique des sols (CNS) sur les données pédologiques existantes pour l'inventaire des ressources en sols à 1 ha de résolution spatiale au Cameroun. Il s'agissait spécifiquement de : (i) compiler et harmoniser la base de données des profils pédologiques ; (ii) évaluer et cartographier la répartition de certaines propriétés clés des sols (pH, Ca, Mg, K, SOC, N, P, CEC, sable, limon, argile et classes de texture) ; (iii) évaluer la répartition à l'échelle nationale du stock de carbone organique du sol (SCOS) jusqu'à 100 cm de profondeur, et (iv) évaluer la méthodologie CNS pour l'intensification durable de la production de cacao au Cameroun. La distribution spatiale des propriétés du sol a été prédite à l'aide d'algorithmes d'apprentissage automatique à des profondeurs standard internationalement reconnues (0 - 5 cm, 5 - 15 cm, 15 - 30 cm, 30 - 60 cm, 60 - 100 cm et 100 - 200 cm). La base de données harmonisée des profils pédologiques (Camsodat 0.1) contient actuellement environ 5250 horizons qui sont inégalement réparties sur 1600 positions géoréférencées à travers le pays. Les modèles de prédiction ont estimé la distribution nationale des propriétés des sols, avec de bonnes performances (R^2 jusqu'à 68%). Les attributs du terrain et du climat ont été les facteurs environnementaux les plus pertinents pour prédire la répartition des propriétés du sol dans le pays. La répartition nationale des SCOS est conforme au schéma des zones agroécologiques. Au total, environ 5.67 Pg de SCOS sont stockés dans les 100 premiers cm de profondeur du sol au Cameroun, dont 50 % dans les 30 premiers cm. L'évaluation des terres a révélé des sols adaptés à la production de cacao avec différents niveaux d'aptitudes et nécessitant des approches de gestion spécifiques aux sites. En général, pour la production de cacao, 9 % de la zone est très convenable, 78 % modérément convenable et 13 % marginalement convenable. Cinq (5) des propriétés des sols affectant principalement la productivité du cacao, par ordre décroissant d'importance, sont OC > Argile > Mg > pH > Limon. Bien que les sols du Cameroun restent peu connus, la CNS a montré un potentiel élevé pour combler ces lacunes, et sa polyvalence par la détermination des SCOS jusqu'à 100 cm de profondeur et l'applicabilité dans l'analyse de l'adéquation des sols pour l'intensification de la production de cacao au Cameroun.

Mots-clés : *Données historiques sur les sols, cartographie numérique des sols, propriétés des sols, agriculture durable, aptitude des sols*

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AFNOR	: Association Française de Normalisation
AfSIS	: African Soil Information Services
AGB	: Above Ground Biomass
ANN	: Artificial Neural Network
ASB	: Alternative to Slash and Burn
ASTER	: Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer
BD	: Bulk density
BDSolos	: Brazilian Soil Information System
BGR	: Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources
BN	: Bayesian Network
BORIS	: Boden Information System
Camsodat	: Cameroon Soil DataBase
CanSIS	: Canadian Soil Information Service
CART	: Classification and Regression Trees
CDC	: Cameroon Development Corporation
CNA	: National College of Agriculture
COMDEV	: Commonwealth Development Corporation
COP	: Conference of the Parties
CRS	: Coordinate Reference System
CSM	: Conventiounal Soil Mapping
CUD	: University Centre of Dschang
DAP	: Development Aid Program
DATZF	: Department of Land Use Planning and Development of Border Areas
DBH	: Diameter at Breast Height
DEM	: Digital Elevation Model
DSCE	: Document de Stratégie pour la Croissance et l'Emploie
DSM	: Digital Soil Mapping
DSSAT	: Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer
DTM	: Digital Terrain Model
EFSA	: Federal High School of Agriculture
EIA	: Environmental Impact Assessment
ENSA	: National High School of Agriculture
ENSAC	: National School of Colonial Agriculture
EthioSIS	: Ethiopian Soil Information System
EVI	: Enhanced Vegetation Index
FAO	: Food and Agriculture Organizations
FASA	: Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences
GBR	: Generalized Boosted Regression
GDP	: Gross Domestic Product
GHG	: Greenhouse Gas
GSIF	: Global Soil Information Facilities

GSM	: Global Soil Map
HFBR	: Humid Forest with Bimodal Rainfall
HFMR	: Humid Forest with Monomodal Rainfall
HGSZ	: High Guinea Savanna Zone
HWSO	: Harmonized World Soil Data
ICRAF	: World Centre Agroforestry
IDW	: Inverse Distance Weighting
IITA	: International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
IMF	: International Monetary Fund
INA	: National Institute of Agronomy
INADER	: National Institute of Rural Development
IPCC	: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRA	: Institute of Agronomic Research
IRAD	: Institut de Recherche Agronomique pour le Développement
IRCAM	: Scientific Research Institute of Cameroon
IRD	: Development Research Institute
ISO	: International Organization for Standardization
ISRIC	: International Soil Reference and Information Centre
ITA	: Institute of Agricultural Techniques
LM	: Logistic Model
MINADER	: Ministère de l'Agriculture et du développement Rural
MINEPAT	: Ministère de l'Economie, de la Planification, et de l'Aménagement du Territoire
MINEPDED	: Ministère de l'Environnement, de la Protection de la Nature, et du Développement Durable
MINESUP	: Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur
MINFOF	: Ministère des Forêts et de la Faune
MINRESI	: Ministère de la Recherche Scientifique et de l'Innovation
MODIS	: Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MRV	: Monitoring, Reporting, Verification
NASA	: National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NASIS	: National Soils Information System
NRCS	: Natural Resources Conservation Service
NSC	: National Soil Center
OCP	: Office chérifien des phosphates
OK	: Ordinary Kriging
ORSTOM	: Office of Overseas Scientific and Technical Research
PAC	: Policy Assessment Center
PRDFCC	: Plan de Relance et de Développement des Filières Cacao et Café
PRESS	: Project on Soil and Subsoil Resources of North and South-West Regions
PROLEG	: Vegetable production company
PSF	: Particle size Fraction
PSS	: Proximal Soil Sensing
PWV	: Precipitable Water Vapor
QUEFTS	: Quantitative Evaluation of the Fertility of Tropical Soils

RA	: Rapid Assessment
REDD	: Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Degradation
RF	: Random Forest
RK	: Regression Kriging
RMSE	: Root Mean Square Error
RQF	: Rational Quadratic Function
RT	: Regression tree
SAGA	: System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses
SALMS	: Shifting Agricultural Landscape Mosaic System
SAP	: Structural Adjustment Plans
SEM	: Structural Equation Modeling
SIMS	: Hungarian Soil Information and Monitoring System
SIS	: Soil information systems
SISINTA	: Soil Information system of INTA
SOC	: Soil Organic Carbon
SOCS	: Soil Organic Carbon Stock
SOM	: Soil Organic Matter
SRTM	: Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SSZ	: Soudano-Sahelian Zone
TIM	: Soil Information and Monitoring System
UDs	: University of Dschang
UN	: United Nations
UNCCD	: United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UNDP	: United Nations Program for Development
UNFCCC	: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USAID	: United States Agency for International Development
USDA	: United States Department of Agriculture
Vis – NIR	: Visible and Near Infra-Red
VLIR	: Flemish Interuniversity Council
WHZ	: Western Highlands Zone
WoSIS	: World Soil Information Service

CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Soil is one of the major life support systems, hence soil functions are vital for ensuring food security as well as sustaining human existence. Numerous environmental and socio-economic models require soil parameters as inputs to estimate and forecast changes in our future living conditions. Policymakers and environmental managers need accurate information on soil distribution and spatial variation, to assess the suitability of the soil to perform its functions and the interaction between the soil and the wider environment (Keesstra et al., 2016). Soils are fundamental in food production and essential to be considered in climate change mitigation strategies. Global, national, and regional models addressing issues such as climate change, land degradation and hydrological processes need soil input parameters, often with complete spatial coverage (Grunwald, 2010). Likewise, through their functions and ecosystem services, soil can in many ways, help to achieve sustainable development goals (Bouma, 2014). More particularly in the aspects related to food, water, climate, health, biodiversity, and sustainable land use (Bouma and Montanarella, 2016; Keesstra et al., 2016).

In Africa, 70% of the population still depends directly on the pressures on natural resources for daily subsistence, especially in rural areas. The population is also expected to rise to about 4 billion by the end of the century (UN, 2015). To adequately meet the food demand of such a growing population, the quantity of food production will almost have to increase more than ten times in several African countries (van Ittersum et al., 2016). However, the cropland area has increased in Africa during the recent decades in response to population growth (FAO, 2014), with high pressures on soil resources, that will be rising as a consequence of increasing food demand (Godfray et al., 2012). As such, solutions on how soils can be best managed, require accurate soil information as the basis for decision making. Soil knowledge is vital and prerequisite to meaningful management decisions on environmental quality and sustainable agricultural production. Unfortunately, in Sub-Sahara Africa, soil datasets available are currently few and sparse (Anderson et al., 2008) and often not readily available in the required format (Greve et al., 2012). It is likely why Sanchez (2002) reported that soil scientists will have a large impact on the society because there is an incomplete understanding of the soil and insufficient hard information.

Agriculture plays a prominent role in the economy of many countries of Sub-Saharan Africa. In Cameroon, agriculture contributes to about 45% of the gross domestic product (GDP) and 65% of full-time employment (Abia et al., 2016). Due to its agro-ecological diversity, Cameroon has a great potential for agricultural production, with natural resources suitable for a strong and sustainable agricultural development scheme. The government has put agriculture at the top of development strategies to become an emerging country by 2035 (DSCE, 2009). In such strategies, the soil management scheme should be the backbone on which all agricultural production systems must be built (Khormali et al., 2015) since the soil provides nutrients for plants to grow, stocks water as well as providing physical support for plants (Bonfante et al., 2017). Soils have the chemical, physical and biological characteristics that determine the quantity, quality, and productivity of agricultural systems.

For an adequate agricultural planning and sustainability, the knowledge of the characteristics and distribution of soils is essential and needed to allocate each land portion to the uses that provide the greatest sustainable benefits. Intimate knowledge of the soils and their spatial distribution is a prerequisite for a successful and rational land use plan for agriculture, forestry, irrigation, drainage, etc. Moreover, unsustainable expansion of agricultural areas and inadequate usage of fertilizers has been adopted by farmers as a strategy to overcome the soil constraints for agricultural production in Cameroon (Tayoh et al., 2016). As awareness of the non-renewable nature of soil resources is growing (Hartemink and McBratney, 2008), if strategies for rapidly and sustainably closing the yield gap in Cameroon are not developed and implemented, the pressure on soils due to the increase of the population may be amplified with the internal food demand and that of neighboring countries (REDD-PAC, 2015). A frequently expressed concern is that, where it occurs, agricultural production increases in Cameroon comes mainly from expansion in the area of cultivated land, not from increases in yields or from gains in factor productivity. Thereby, agricultural expansion is likely to exacerbate soil degradation in Cameroon by 2030 (REDD-PAC, 2015).

Current strategies for sustainable intensification of agricultural production recommend a strong use of fertilizers and other agricultural inputs in Cameroon (Gizaki et al., 2015; Abia et al., 2016). However, the accessibility of fertilizers and their cost is one of the major constraints. Also, the misuse of fertilizers is a major risk. Several technical agricultural production documents for fertilizer recommendation currently in use in Cameroon do not take into account the specific local soil conditions. The use of such documents is therefore increasing the misuse of fertilizers in the country. Soil knowledge production in Cameroon is thus becoming a vital

need for both agriculture and food security, which are essential to our country's economy, and also for minimizing the risks associated with current agricultural intensification policies focused on the use of agricultural inputs. The availability of soil data as well as large-scale soil maps might assist to improve the accuracy of fertility assessment, and to convey precise information with regards to proper soil management requirement at the local, regional and national level in Cameroon (Ngachie, 1992).

On the environmental aspect, soils hold the largest organic carbon stock in the global terrestrial ecosystem (Lal, 2003) and therewith play a significant role in mitigating climate change (Guo et al., 2015). Soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration also contributes to maintaining and improving soil quality and soil fertility. Supporting decisions for sustainable SOC sequestration requires a sound understanding of the distribution of soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS), its importance, and the potential to define efficient management approaches to reduce SOCS losses and/or enhance its accumulation (Minasny et al., 2017). Mapping SOCS is thus of high priority for assessment and monitoring purposes, because estimation of carbon stocks is also necessary for the broader context of a carbon inventory for global circulation models and carbon economy studies (Antle et al., 2003; Scharlemann et al., 2014).

While the information on many environmental attributes such as terrain and climate can easily be obtained from many sources (topo-cadastral maps, digital elevation models, weather stations, and climate models), soil information is more difficult to gather. Especially at refined levels of detail. Substantial financial investment is often necessary to obtain soil data because soils and their properties change very substantially over short distances, and the skills and expertise necessary to accurately record, measure and map such changes are time and labor extensive. Consequently, soil information remains either missing at the appropriate scale, or its meaning is not well explained for reliable interpretation when the information exists. A necessary point is to reach an adequate level of knowledge on their status to raise awareness on their importance based on national or local observations from soil surveys (Sanchez et al., 2009).

Surveying soils was reported to always be a financially profitable investment, as it is an instrument that is almost certain to return a profit for several reasons (Bie and Ulph, 1972). The economic value of soil survey depends on the quality of the output map, and also on the difference in payoffs between alternative management practices. It supports land-use decisions for the future and helps in setting rules to meet the socio-political objectives, whilst preserving

the delicate balance between economic and ecological aspects of land and land use. Optimum yields or gains are achieved when land use and management are perfectly adapted to local soil conditions. Planning decisions, usually are based on maps of soil, land use, relief, climate, and soil condition or quality is also a focal point for an increasing number of competing and even conflicting lands uses. The lack of soils information was pointed out as the cause of the failure of many development programs. In regions of the country where the economy is predominantly based on agriculture, an intimate knowledge of the soils, their character, spatial distribution, and Physico-chemical properties is a fundamental requirement (Demattê et al., 2002). Despite the known and wide documented importance of soil, spatially explicit data on soil are drastically lacking in Cameroon. The level of soil knowledge in Cameroon remains very weak, and the available databases often fail to provide the necessary soil parameter to assist in decision making (Silatsa and Yemefack, 2019). Large-scale soil maps either do not exist or cover only a very small percentage of the country (Van Ranst et al., 2010). To support the development scheme and sustainable development of the territory set by the government in the 2035 vision, an infrastructure for geospatial soil data collection and updating are essential. It is the best way to produce harmonized and shared soil data for sustainable development planning.

In the production of soil information, the soil survey models define qualitative correlation that formulates a mental model in the surveyor's mind, used to understand and characterize the soil resources (Dobos et al., 2019). Decisions are made mainly on the field, where all environmental covariates can be directly observed and information on the soil can be deduced, based on intensive fieldwork, which is cost-intensive and time-consuming. Started in the '40s, soil survey efforts have been recorded at various scales in Cameroon. Several other studies have collected soil data for soil fertility assessment and land evaluation. In the course of these investigations, soils were mainly grouped into similar types and their boundaries were delineated on maps based on geology and landform. Information assembled from profile was used to predict or estimate the potentials and limitations of the soils under particular uses. In recent decades, methods for valuing existing soil data (legacy soil data) have been successfully developed. One promising approach to quick delivery of required soil information is the use of quantitative soil modeling techniques such as digital soil mapping (DSM) (Hartemink and McBratney, 2008). These modeling techniques require large amounts of data for their appropriate implementation at detailed scales (Hengl et al., 2014). Fortunately, these modeling techniques allow using the data from soil surveys carried out several decades ago. There is a potential to capitalize on DSM with existing soil data in Cameroon to afresh and refresh soil information.

Worldwide, there is a growing interest in applying spatial prediction methods for producing detailed soil maps to support agricultural development intensification, and monitoring of the soil resource (Shepherd et al., 2015). The first decade of 2000s witnessed a quantum of new approaches to soil mapping (McBratney et al., 2003). The emergence of DSM as a credible alternative to fulfill the increasing demand in spatial soil data has been illustrated by his ability to increase spatial resolutions, enlarge extents, and deliver relevant soil information. DSM is known as the creation and extension of spatial soil information systems by numerical models inferring the spatial and temporal variations of soil types and soil properties from soil observations and related environmental variables (Lagacherie, 2008). It provides continuous soil information instead of spatially discrete point or profile information. Applicable to recent increasing computer performances, it is cost and time effective and a promising technique in areas with a huge lack of soil information availability. The basis of DSM is the application of pedometric methods that predict the spatial and temporal distribution of soil types and soil properties based on soil forming factors. Typically, the environmental variables influencing soil formation are exhaustive georeferenced data layers, including digitized geological and topographic maps, satellite images and derivatives (Mulder et al., 2011). DSM provides the means for supplying soil information in format and resolution compatible with other fundamental data sets from remote sensing, terrain analysis, and other systems for mapping, monitoring, and forecasting biophysical processes. DSM techniques have been shown as viable tools assisting to develop soil data, while the state-of-the-art requirements on the quality assurance, accuracy assessment, GIS support, and reported quantitative data development procedure are more easily fulfilled.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the '80s, Cameroon had a good agricultural policy illustrated as an example for other African countries (Madeley, 1987). Cameroon achieved food self-sufficiency by giving priority to agriculture and implementing a range of policy measures that contributed to releasing the potential of the food-producing sector. However, because of soil misuse and degradation, agricultural production in Cameroon has degenerated (Hartemink, 2003a). Soil fertility decline and reducing crop yields were reported as majors concerns contributing to acute poverty, as a result of inappropriate soil fertility management practices (Lal, 2015). Cameroon agriculture is now seen as underperforming (World-Bank, 2007) because of climate change and soil degradation (Hartemink, 2003a; Sanchez, 2002) which negatively affects food security achievement. The successful agriculture land seems to coincide with the preceding intense soil

survey areas in Cameroon. This suggests that agricultural policy was based on sound pedological knowledge. The decades that followed were marked by a blatant absence of major soil survey activities throughout the country and the high population growth that has contributed to exacerbated pressures on unknown soil resources.

All of the soil data collected in the previous studies currently constitute the legacy soil data, which are now in the form of soil survey maps or reports (also called “soil resource inventories”). Some of these soil data are frequently of good quality because of the surveyor’s efforts in understanding soil-landscape relations. To increase the value of the existing soil data, they must be kept in a digital soil database and as such made available for reusing with state-of-the-art methods of soil modeling. Therefore, existing legacy and heritage soil survey data are being rescued and processed into an applicable dataset and used as a huge reservoir of soil information for decision making, and also serving as input for soil mapping in many countries (Adhikari et al., 2014; Akpa et al., 2016; Arrouays et al., 2001; Chen et al., 2018b; Ramifehiarivo et al., 2017; Vaysse and Lagacherie, 2017). New soil data collection is cost-prohibitive and not justifiable without first having made optimal use of earlier collected data in many countries (Arrouays et al., 2017). However, to the best of our knowledge, no effort has so far been initiated to rescue and safeguard legacy soil data in Cameroon. Given that intensive soil surveys campaigns covering the whole Cameroon is very expensive and unlikely to happen soon, the current strategy to address the data gap is the consolidation of previous soil surveys data. The concern is to rescue, compile and harmonize existing soil data into a database that will enable the production of soil information for guiding policy making in development planning and other interested areas of expertise.

Likewise, data rescue efforts in many countries are being used at national, continental, and global levels for assessing soil spatial distribution (Hengl et al., 2017a, 2014; Leenaars et al., 2018). Leenaars et al. (2014) reported that the contribution of each country by creating a national soil database could improve the response of the prediction models at Worldwide level. There is thus, a responsibility for each country to consider setting up a mechanism that would enable to develop a usable database for improving the quality of their current soil information (Leenaars et al., 2014) and to make technical recommendations more site-specific (Tabi et al., 2007).

Notwithstanding the soil data rescue and harmonization possibilities, soil properties distribution of many African countries remain poorly explored and the recent Global Soil Partnership (GSP)

initiative on global carbon stock mapping using a bottom-up approach reported a national contribution of only 20% of these countries (FAO, 2018). Therefore, the information provided on carbon stocks of most African countries is mainly inferred from global estimates, with SoilGrids (Hengl et al., 2017a), and the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) (Wieder et al., 2014) as the most commonly cited sources worldwide (Deng et al., 2018). However, there is a growing awareness of the accuracy limitations of such global models on estimating soil properties at the national level (Tifafi et al., 2018), due to forcing a global model for local prediction. The difference between national and global estimates in Sub-Sahara African countries remains poorly explored. The issue of accurately assessing countrywide soil properties is now critical (Carvalho et al., 2019; Kempen et al., 2019; Vitharana et al., 2019).

The recent development of new digital methods and technologies of analysis has initiated a new era in soil mapping, which allows fulfilling the increasing demand in spatial soil information (Lagacherie, 2008). To transform the legacy soil data through quantitative soil-landscape modeling such as to meet the modern demands for quantitative soil information, many prediction options are currently in use. Classification and regression trees, random forest regression, support vector machines, artificial neural networks, and many other variants are currently applied. Amongst these techniques that have been used to predict and map soil properties at multiple scales (farm, landscape, national, regional, continental and global), random forest and boosted regression models have proven to be valuable methods for spatial soil assessment (e.g., Chen et al., 2018; Ließ et al., 2016; Malone et al., 2009a; Ramcharan et al., 2018; Ramifehiarivo et al., 2017; Sreenivas et al., 2014). An improved understanding of the applicability of these algorithms on legacy soil data in Cameroon would contribute valuable knowledge needed to fill the gap and densify the spatial soil information.

To improve the performance of the estimations, after applying machine learning algorithms on soil properties, situations with a spatial structure in the model residuals have been reported and many studies have successfully applied hybridization on residual kriging (Chen et al., 2018; Ramcharan et al., 2018; Ramifehiarivo et al., 2017). While the residual component is reported to have a strong spatial dependence at field scale for small areas, it often exhibits a moderate to weak spatial dependence for large areas (Vaysse and Lagacherie, 2017). This raises the question of whether inverse distance weighting (IDW) interpolation, which is less complex to deploy (single-step procedure) as compared to kriging (which has several intermediate steps and requires quantification of the residual spatial autocorrelation) could provide comparable hybridization results for improving national soil properties estimates.

In applying DSM for improving agricultural production, Cameroon has a huge agricultural potential, and agriculture could play a very important role in poverty reduction and sustainable development (Tabi and Mukete, 2017). One of the main agricultural products is Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* Linn.) which has been a very important commodity contributing significantly to the national economy (Amougou et al., 2013). As an important source of national income, it has been a leading sub-sector in the economic growth and development of the country (Duguma et al., 2001; Tabi and Mukete, 2017). About 90% of households in the cocoa-producing areas directly depend on it for their income (Kimengsi and Azibo, 2015). Cocoa is a major perennial cash crop predominantly cultivated in the humid forest zone of Cameroon (Yemefack et al., 2006a). With a current production of about 300,000 tons/year, Cameroon is among the leading cocoa producers in Africa (Wessel and Quist-Wessel, 2015), and the government is targeting to achieve a national production of 600,000 tons/year through intensification and extension of planting areas (PRDFCC, 2014). However, extending planting area will conflict with forest protection and conservation. So, to achieve such target, it is more appropriate to design ways for sustainable intensification of the production, to limit the negative impact and to avoid the massive destruction of forest and degradation of soils (Gockowski and Sonwa, 2011).

The cocoa productivity in Cameroon is low (300-400 kg/ha) as compared to that of other African countries (Amougou et al., 2013). This is due to many factors, such as the lack of appropriate agronomic and management practices (e.g., soil fertility management, appropriate pruning timing, shade control, adequate pest control, and weeding). Although, the prospect of climate change is also going to harm cocoa production (Laderach et al., 2013), the low soil fertility under cocoa is among the major causes for the poor cocoa yields (Adewole et al., 2011; Afrifa et al., 2009; Agbeniyi et al., 2010; Agyemang et al., 2011; Aikpokpodion, 2010; Appiah et al., 1997; Baah et al., 2011; Baligar and Fageria, 2005; Ibiremo et al., 2011; Koko, 2014; Kongor et al., 2019; Njukeng and Baligar, 2016; Nunoo et al., 2015; Schroth et al., 2016; Snoeck et al., 2010), since the climatic suitability of cocoa cultivation coincides with the soils with natural low fertility in the humid tropics (Hartemink, 2003a; Sanchez, 2002). Poor soil productivity is also because farmers fail to appropriately replenish the soils with fertilizers after extracting nutrients through harvests (Njukeng and Baligar, 2016). The gap between the potential yield and actual yield of cocoa in Cameroon can be decreased by addressing the nutritional needs of cocoa through the understanding of soil conditions to anticipate implementing appropriate soil management measures (Van Villet et al., 2015).

Furthermore, cocoa is produced in the shifting agricultural landscape (SAL) of Cameroon. Shifting agriculture is criticized for its continual encroachment into the tropical forest landscape, which is considered a reserve for biodiversity conservation and carbon (C) sink (Ickowitz, 2006; Lambin et al., 2003). While modeling the land-use transition in the SAL, Yemefack et al. (2006b) reported that cocoa agroforest systems (CAF) were a common land-use transition within the system. So far in the country, increasing cocoa production has been done primarily through forest destruction rather than by promoting improved yields on existing land (Tabi and Mukete, 2017). Although perceived as one of the deforestation drivers, the complex structure of CAF systems was described to contribute to maintain a large number of ecological characteristics of natural forests (Sonwa et al., 2007). Duguma et al. (2001) also revealed that the CAF systems could remain productive and environmentally sustainable for up to 50 years, at a level comparable to long-term fallow. This suggests that to promote sustainable development of cocoa production, there is a need to investigate the ecological sustainability of CAF in order to propose the conditions under which sustainable intensification of cocoa production can be achievable and efficient. Therefore, there is a need to understand the variations and the distribution of soil properties in the cocoa production areas in Cameroon, because a holistic intensification cannot be achieved without considering the potential of a given soil to fulfill its functions (Takoutsing et al., 2018).

In summary, facing the increasing and urgent needs for the implementation of the various segments of the Cameroonian development strategies and land use planning, there is a pressing necessity for a quick and concise production of reliable soil information, and the increasing development in DSM is a seizeable opportunity. But the challenge is on how to value existing legacy soil data to apply such technologies to support national-scale soil mapping and sustainable agricultural production in Cameroon. There is a need to rescue and safeguard legacy soil data, of which no effort has so far been initiated in Cameroon. Although, this is a responsibility for each country to develop a usable database for improving the quality of their current national soil information and to make technical recommendations more site-specific. An improved understanding of the applicability of DSM algorithms on legacy soil data in Cameroon would contribute valuable knowledge needed to densify the spatial soil information and to fill the gap between the potential yield and actual crop yields. Considering the important place occupied by cocoa in agriculture and the country's economy, the DSM methods assessment can be tested on soil suitability for sustainable cocoa intensification before the methods is extended to other crops.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1.3.1 Main research question

The main research question of this study was to assess whether the application of digital soil mapping (DSM) methods on legacy soil data for soil resource inventory could support sustainable agricultural intensification in Cameroon?

1.3.2 Specific research questions

The specific research questions of this study are:

i) What is the level of soil data collection in Cameroon?

- What is the spatial spread of legacy soil data in Cameroon?
- What is the temporal trend of legacy soil data collection in Cameroon?
- What is the gap and how to improve their spatial coverage?

ii) Can DSM algorithms support soil properties mapping in Cameroon?

- Does SoilGrids improve the national prediction of soil properties?
- How are particle size fractions and soil texture spatially distributed in Cameroon?
- How are soil pH classes spatially spread over Cameroon?

iii) How are soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS) distributed over the country

- How is the soil SOCS spatially distributed in Cameroon?
- Is there a gap between global and national estimates of SOCS?
- Does inverse distance weighting (IDW) and ordinary kriging (OK) interpolation of residual (hybridization) with machine learning algorithms provide a comparable result?
- How do agro-ecological zones influence the SOCS distribution in Cameroon?

iv) Can digital soil mapping support sustainable agricultural production in Cameroon?

- How are topsoil properties spatially distributed in Cameroon's cocoa production zone?
- How does SOCS accrete in the cocoa agroforest as compared to fallow systems over time (50 years)?

- Is there a relationship between soil properties distribution, climate suitability, and cocoa productivity in Cameroon?
- Which soil properties mostly influence the distribution of cocoa production in Cameroon?

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1.4.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this study was to investigate the applicability of digital soil mapping methods on legacy soil data for inventorying soil resource information in Cameroon, as input for sustainable intensification of cocoa production.

1.4.2 Specific objectives and research questions

To achieve our main objective, four specific objectives were defined as to:

i) Carry out a review of soil surveys in Cameroon and develop the national soil legacy database

- Assess the spatial spread of legacy soil data in Cameroon,
- Assess the temporal trend of legacy soil data collection in Cameroon,
- Appraise the gaps in the spatial coverage of soil data and propose a sampling plan to improve it.

ii) Apply DSM algorithms for key soil properties mapping at high resolution in Cameroon

- Assess the nationwide soil pH and particle size fractions distribution,
- Appraise the SoilGrids contribution on national soil properties prediction in Cameroon,
- Compare the Inverse distance weighting (IDW) and ordinary kriging (OK) hybridization performances on predicting soil properties with machine learning algorithms in Cameroon.

iii) Assess the countrywide SOCS in Cameroon

- Quantify the SOCS up to 1m depth in Cameroon,

- Appraise the spatial distribution of SOCS at high resolution in Cameroon,
- Assess the gap between the global and national estimates of SOCS.

iv) Explore DSM approach for sustainable agriculture production in Cameroon, with emphasis on cocoa production

- Determine which soil properties mostly influence the distribution of cocoa productivity in Cameroon
- Assess the key topsoil properties spatial distribution in Cameroon's cocoa production zones
- Appraise the long term (50 years) SOCS accretion in the cocoa agroforestry system as compared to fallow system
- carry out a soil suitability analysis of Cameroonian soils for cocoa production

1.5 ORGANIZATION OF THE THESIS

This thesis is divided into five chapters. Chapter one provides the introduction and the rationale to the study with a focus on the problem statement, research objectives and questions, and the scope of the study. Chapter two contains the literature review on related and similar works, the conceptual framework, and gaps identified in the literature. Chapter three focuses on the materials and methods of the study consisting of a description of the study area, data collection approaches, data processing methods, and measures for validating the results. Chapter four presents, interprets and discusses the results of the study as well as their implications and limitations. Finally, chapter five presents conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This review provides the historical background leading to the current state of soil information in Cameroon, highlights the soil information requirements in Cameroon, and outlines the way forward in terms of data capture, storage, and interpretation using recent technological advances. We have presented digital soil mapping (DSM) as the potential option to address the soil data gap in Cameroon. We finally explored cocoa production in Cameroon by presenting its growth conditions, the main production basins, and the role of cocoa in the cycle of shifting agricultural landscape dynamic. Soil fertility and fertilization related issues are then explored from a variety of perspectives.

2.2 HISTORICAL REVIEW OF SOIL SURVEYS IN CAMEROON

The most critical of natural resources, in terms of agricultural production, are terrain, climate, and soil (Paterson et al., 2015). Regarding soils, knowledge of the history of soil studies turns out to be a necessary step to capitalize on the achievements of the past, learn lessons from failures, improve the value of the existing information, and better approach strategies to understand and address current and future challenges. It is likely why Lakatos (1969) stated that the philosophy of science without history of science is empty. According to Greenland (1991), soil science has been practiced too long in the virtual obscurity from the public and much of the scientific community. The history of soil research has largely been a history of soil use related to agriculture (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010a), because, throughout much of its history, soil science has been concerned primarily with agriculture and emphasis was often placed on the study of soils related to crop production. Soil research in the tropics started several decades later than in the temperate regions, and the evolution of soil survey in Cameroon is undoubtedly associated with the complexity of the political history of the country. However, little has been reported about the progress and development of soil survey in Cameroon. Whereas such information is of interest for determining research priorities in terms of soil information, with the current challenges on food security and climate change. This section does not aim to present a detailed and exhaustive historical review of soil survey in Cameroon but to highlights the main development pathways.

2.2.1 Survey before 1915

2.2.1.1 Before the colonial period

The first documented descriptions of soils in Africa date back to 1820 when Berthier analyzed soil samples from Fouta Djallon in West Africa and found them to be similar to that of Kerala (Showers, 2006). However, the high diversity of African soils, in general, was observed early in the twentieth century mainly due to wrong beliefs and the complexity encountered while implementing modern or improved imported agricultural techniques throughout the continent. For example, Europeans initially thought that the red-colored soils under tropical African high forest must be extremely fertile to support such luxuriant growth. There was also a belief that the dry Semi-arid or arid African landscape, perceived as being defective, or in a state of decline or degradation was a sign of God's punishment of the indigenous people (Showers, 2006).

Until some 100 years ago, little was known about tropical soils (Hartemink, 2002). Nevertheless, during the 16th century, Niccolo Machiavelli noticed that variations in population density were primarily a function of soil fertility and agricultural settlements were established in places where the soils were suitable and favorable for crop growth (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010a). This implies sound knowledge on soils even before the era of conventional soil studies. According to Brevik and Hartemink (2010), local soil knowledge already existed since the Middle Ages in some parts of the world and expanded where religion had less influence. Likewise, Neumann (2005) reported evidence that bananas (*Musa* sp.) have been cultivated in Cameroon since the years 800/400 BC. On the eve of colonization, palm products (palm oil and palm nuts) were among the main goods on the Cameroonian coast (Ndjogui et al., 2014). This confirms the existence of local soil knowledge at least applied to agriculture in Cameroon and probably derived from long-term empirical observations.

Before European colonization at the end of the 19th century, the territory was only a mosaic of peoples and tribes with a diversified socio-political organization. Guyer and Eno Belinga (1995) reported that in the pre-colonial period in Cameroon, social leadership was associated with the capacity of a person to bring together different bodies of knowledge effectively. Environmental and soil knowledge required for survival was acquired by peoples living in a place and was a component of information transfer through oral traditions from one generation to another. Learning from observation, with the subsequent adaptation of lifestyles, was essential for survival. Local soil knowledge was found to be widespread among people. Some specialized people somewhat knew about soils they encountered with a strong historical dimension.

Whether these non-agriculturalists acquired soil knowledge by noting correlations between plant distribution or topography and soil types is not well known, but knowledge on soils by local peoples seem likely very old in Cameroon. Recent study reports have corroborated the effectiveness of the local knowledge in coping with agricultural production constraints and climate change (Birmingham, 2003; Kome et al., 2018a; Ndaka et al., 2015; Souhore et al., 2017; Wartenberg et al., 2018).

In several countries, local knowledge has contributed to the development of national soil classification systems (Kyebogola et al., 2020). Niemeijer and Mazzucato (2003) argued that local knowledge will be useful for sustainable development interventions, and suggested that we should invest further on capturing the “grammar” behind, rather than just translating the sentences, while Krasilnikov and Tabor (2003), recommended these local soil knowledge to be understood and used as complementary perspectives from which to learn about the soil and its processes. Unfortunately, nor in the past, and even less currently, efforts have been made to document these valuable knowledges in Cameroon. In other parts of Africa (for which written records are sparse or absent, and historical linguistics methods have not yet been applied), ancient soil names have not been documented and dates can be less clearly assigned to soil classification, value, or management systems (Showers, 2006). This state of facts significantly limits the knowledge of our soil resources and imposes on us a knowledge-based only on conventional thoughts, forcing us most often to import management solutions that are sometimes not adapted to our context. In conclusion, we can argue that the history of our soils although related to agriculture, began long before the arrival of the settlers, and unfortunately remains not documented. We would probably benefit from investing more in rescuing, collecting cataloging, and using local soil knowledge.

2.2.1.2 Colonial period (1884-1915)

Cameroon was colonized by the Germans between 1884 and 1915. At the beginning of the German occupation, trading was of primary interest for the metropolis, then the creation of plantations was envisaged first in the current south-western region while remaining a secondary concern (Ndjogui et al., 2014). Large agricultural estates were established in southwestern Kamerun (Cameroon) to provide tropical goods for Germany (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010a). The largest cocoa plantation in the world at that time (nearly 4 000 ha) is said to have been created in 1897 by the Germans (West Afrikanische Pflanzungs Gesellschaft) in Cameroon (Etoga, 1971). It was around 1905 that the first colonial palm oil plantations were established

in Cameroon. The establishment of industrial farms preceded the development of soil mapping technology, which was developed simultaneously in several European countries. Soil mapping originated in Germany, France, Austria, Netherlands, and Belgium in the 1850s and 1860s based on ideas and classification developed in agroecology (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010a). The aim of developing soil mapping was to understand the extent and diversity of soils to better control soil productivity.

The history of agricultural research in a country is always as old as the time of occupation of the area and associated with indigenous soil knowledge. That of Cameroon has the distinction of having benefited in the creation of several test gardens during the German colonial period around 1889. Indeed, the establishment of large German plantations was preceded by experimentations in test gardens such as that of Victoria, which at the same time was a training center for agricultural instructors, with 97 students as early as 1910, an average of 100 per year. The German occupation lasted until the end of World War I, with the expansion of industrial plantations and the introduction of agricultural experimentation. However, the German period was not devoted specifically to the soil survey. Knowledge of soils was derived from their agronomic performance and not as a separate entity.

2.2.2 Soil survey between 1915 and 1960

2.2.2.1 Sub-Saharan Africa perspective

The history of soil investigation in the whole sub-Saharan Africa is not very old. The legacy soil data are mostly from about 50 years ago. Soil science as an academic discipline and as a strong arm of the process of agricultural development had its humble beginning during the early 1940s (Huq and Shoaib, 2013). However, soil science did not become a true science in its own right until the 19th century with the development of genetic soil science, led by Dokuchaev (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010a). In the 1940s and 1950s major colonial state-sponsored soil survey campaigns throughout Africa. The earliest known soil map of Africa was published in 1923 at a scale of 1: 25 M, based on limited observations and intended to show the probable location and trend of the great soil belts of Africa (Shantz and Marbut, 1923). In the period 1930-1945, several notable reconnaissance surveys were undertaken in Africa on limited budgets and with few staff (Van Ranst et al., 2010). Until the 1950s, very few soil maps existed (FAO/Unesco, 1977) in African countries, although intensive field surveys and reconnaissance

were undertaken. For example, the first provisional soil map of Nigeria was published by the Survey Department, Lagos in 1952 (Odeh et al., 2012).

The idea of a map of the whole African continent's soils based on regional soil surveys emerged at the Commission for Technical Cooperation in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Inter-African Pedological Service's first administrative council meeting, in Yangambi in 1953. At its second meeting in 1955, they recommended that a map (scale 1: 5 000 000) for soil conservation and use should be drafted in collaboration with their four regional committees (southern, eastern, central, and western Africa). The decision stimulated the preparation of new maps throughout the continent. Subsequent meetings produced compromises among Belgian, French, British, Portuguese, and South African classification systems to reach agreement on a uniform map legend. When finally produced in 1963, it was the first map ever drawn as the result of an international agreement (Showers, 2006). Although the first important and significant contributions to tropical soil science date back from the thirties, the 1950s perhaps mark the second renaissance of pedology in Africa with emphasis on soil mapping. The decade of the 1950s saw an increase in the number of studies on the mapping of African soils as some European countries, notably Belgium, France, and Portugal, funded soil research in their African colonies (Van Ranst et al., 2010).

Meanwhile, in the 20th century, soil science moved beyond its agricultural roots (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010b), and one of the earliest non-agricultural uses of soil surveys was in highway construction in the U.S. around 1920. Later on, County governments started using soil surveys to plan residential developments. United States soil surveys were expanded to include information on the engineering properties of soil, the suitability of given soils for uses including campgrounds, picnic areas, foundations, septic systems, wildlife management, and other uses in addition to the more traditional agricultural information (Showers, 2006). After the Second World War, a lot was still invested in soil surveys in many countries around the world by the colonial metropolis. This was in support of the development of agricultural sectors to stimulate food production until the years of independence.

After the defeat of the Germans during the First World War, Cameroon was occupied by France and England. On March 4, 1916, they signed a convention for the division of Cameroonian territory pending the approval of the international community. France obtained 4/5 of the eastern part of the territory while the remaining 1/5 in the west was entrusted to Great Britain. Agricultural policies were closely linked to the colonial policy of each metropolis, as well as

the changing economic conditions in the colonies. Emphasis was placed exclusively on export crops (Bamou and Masters, 2007). With the recent advances in soil mapping in Europe, it is during this period that soil mapping will begin and take a decisive turn in Cameroon and whole Africa.

2.2.2.2 French mandated Cameroon territory (1916-1960)

Greater agricultural development took place in French Cameroun, with significant efforts invested in soil mapping. The main driving force for a systematic study of Cameroon's soils was to understand the distribution of soils to enhance their agricultural productivity through soil suitability assessment. The beginning of a systematic collection of soil information in Cameroon was initiated in the 1940s, two years before the official creation of the Scientific Research Institute of Cameroon (IRCAM), with a complete pedology section (Segalen, 1961). When it was created, the soil section included 3 soil scientists from ORSTOM (Office of Overseas Scientific and Technical Research) and a Cameroonian assistant. The section also had a Physico-chemical analysis laboratory in Yaounde, with a chief laboratory technician. Between 1946 and 1960, works of variable scope covering almost the whole of the country on various scales were carried out. The progress report on soil mapping activities in Cameroon published in 1961 (Segalen, 1961) illustrates the main findings and maps produced during these studies, which were grouped into three main categories.

- **Very large-scale maps (> 1: 25 000);** These studies were carried out in areas with very high agricultural potential, at scales ranging from 1: 2 000 to 1: 25 000, and areas explored under these studies ranged from 100 to 55 000 ha, for a total area of approximately 140 000 ha surveyed. One can cite among these studies; the soil study of the banana plain (1: 20 000), soil map of the agricultural stations of Dschang and Bansa (1: 4 000), soil study of the rice plain of Logone (1: 10 000), soil study of the sub Mousgoy modernization sector (1: 20 000), soil study of Yaounde (1: 10 000) (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Yaounde soil map (Bachelier and Segalen, 1958)

- **Large scale maps (1: 50 000);** These studies were mainly carried out in the Western region, on areas varying from 25 000 ha to 77 000 ha, with a total of 455 500 ha of land surveyed in the West and Adamawa regions. The main studies that we can list in this category are the soil map of the plain of Mbo (25 500 ha), soil map of Foubot (77 000 ha) (Figure 2.2), and the soil map of the recent volcanic area of Ngaoundéré (60 000 ha).

Figure 2.2: Foubot soil map (Bachelier and Segalen, 1958)

- **Medium-scale maps (1: 100 000 & 1: 200 000);** These studies were mainly carried out in the far north region, on areas of about 300 000 ha. A total of 1 189 900 ha was covered at scale 1: 100 000 and 1 950 000 ha of land were surveyed at scale 1: 200 000. The 1: 200 000 maps were mainly made in the North region. Figure 2.3 shows the soil map of Mora at 1: 100,000.

The efficiency of France in conducting soil studies in Colonies, as well as in Cameroon comes from its colonial agricultural training policy. The need for trained professionals to develop agriculture in the French colonies appeared very early in the French colonial “empire” (Kleiche-Dray, 2006). From the beginning of the 20th century, France set training in colonial agriculture as a priority. In 1902, the National School of Colonial Agriculture (ENSAC) was created in France, with objectives to train executives in the agricultural techniques of their colonies, build a modern type of agriculture, and a new science likely to contribute to the wealth of France (Kleiche-Dray, 1996).

The training was done in one complementary year of specialization after two years of study at the National Institute of Agronomy (INA). Thus, the French staff (public and private) arriving in Cameroon for agricultural exploitation or soil research were highly skilled and specially trained. These agricultural experts contributed to the birth of scientific tropical agricultural research in the aftermath of the Second World War. It was the experience of these first generations of colonial agronomists that were used to organize tropical agronomic education as it was developed after 1945 (Kleiche-Dray, 1996). On the eve of independence, the work carried out by IRCAM teams (with pedologists of ORSTOM) made it possible to cover almost the entire country at low scales, and contributed in 1957 to elaborate the first soils Atlas in Cameroon (Figure 2.4) at scale 1: 2 000 000 (Martin and Segalen, 1966). Likely due to the significant contribution from soil research and related fields, greater agricultural development took place in French Cameroun. At the time of independence, French Cameroun had a higher gross national product per capita (Benneh and DeLancey, 2019).

2.2.2.3 British mandated Cameroon territory (1916-1961)

In terms of soil investigations, the British occupation seems not to have been very significant. According to Njung (2019), the British wanted to integrate the mandate of British Cameroon into that of Nigeria and failed to promote the advancement of British Cameroons as stipulated by the system of trusteeship. Unlike the French who bought the German plantations after the World war I, enlarged and valued them, the British took advantage of article 279 (02) from the Treaty of Versailles to sell many of them at auction (Ndjogui et al., 2014). Several of these plantations (about 60%) were bought by the Germans.

Figure 2.4: Cameroon soil atlas at scale 1: 2 000 000 (Martin and Segalen, 1966)

After the World War II, plantations in the British Administered Territory were united into a single parastatal (government-owned enterprise) estate, first known as the Commonwealth Development Corporation (COMDEV), which later became Cameroon Development Corporation (CDC) in 1946, and served as the mainstay of the economy (Ndjogui et al., 2014). Development also occurred in agriculture, especially in the latter years of British rule with CDC initiatives. Two agricultural research centers have been created in Barombi-Kang in 1951 and Ekona 1954 (Beye, 2013). The production of cacao, coffee, and bananas grew rapidly (Benneh and DeLancey, 2019). However, under the British occupation period, no specific documentation exists to the best of our knowledge on soil studies in the ruled areas.

2.2.3 Soil survey between 1960 and 1980

Odeh et al. (2012) noticed that after independences in 1960, succeeding governments became increasingly interested in national food production self-sufficiency, although efforts towards providing soil suitability for various crops did not start until in the mid-1960s. The complexity of political evolution in Cameroon affected the progress in soil survey projects. At the political level, the unification in 1961 and reunification in 1972 had conditioned the extend of soil survey. Key progress that will mark this period in terms of soil mapping and survey concerns bilateral cooperation's and agricultural training in Cameroon. According to Hartemink (2002), in the 1960s, the number of research workers per 100 000 farmworkers in Cameroon was about 1.0 and with some exceptions, the total number of soil scientists, as well as the number of soil scientists per million inhabitants or hectare agricultural land, is commonly lower in the tropics (Hartemink, 2002). Given the importance attached by the government to the training of local expertise, we can say that the agricultural training of Cameroonians was the main asset of this period.

Indeed, higher agricultural training in Cameroon began with the creation of the Cameroon National School of Agriculture (ENCA) upon independence in 1960. After unification in 1972, it became the Federal Higher School of Agriculture (EFSA) in 1962 and attached to the Federal University of Cameroon. In 1972, in favor of reunification, ENSA (Ecole Nationale Supérieure Agronomique) was created in Yaounde. In 1977, the Institute of Agricultural Techniques (ITA) was created on the former National College of Agriculture (CNA) site in Dschang. In the same year, ENSA moved to the West region and, together with ITA, formed the two institutions of the University Centre of Dschang (CUD). Undoubtedly, training in pedology, soil survey and mapping was among of the core foundations of training in each of these institutions.

As a bilateral partner in cooperation with Cameroon's after independence, the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) supported Cameroon in the creation of agricultural training institutions (Beye, 2013). Concerning soil training specifically, Cameroonian engineers were trained, unlike the initial training which consisted of training field technicians for field assistance during soil surveys (Segalen et al., 1962). Several exchange cooperation partnerships were created for the mobility of Cameroonian students abroad. Exchange programs will be set up to enable Cameroonians to stay abroad for complementary studies in various fields of expertise, as well as soil. In the meantime, several soil studies will be carried out in the field, while others will be finalized. The bulk of the work and literature collected during this period was described in (ORSTOM, 1987). However, the main studies that we can list are; the pedological reconnaissance map of Garoua (Humbel and Barbery, 1974), Bogo-Pouss pedological reconnaissance map (Barbery et al., 1980), soils of some volcanic regions of Cameroon (Sieffermann, 1973), soils of the Benue valley, from Lagdo to the confluence of the Faro River (Gavaud et al., 1975), etc. These works will contribute to the publication of the soil map of Eastern Cameroon (North and South sheets) at scale 1:1 000 000 in 1965 (Figure 2.5).

These achievements have benefited from partial funding from the French development aid program. For example, according to Champaud (1966), this aid amounted to a total of 4 billion CFA francs during the 1964-65 fiscal year for all French projects in Cameroon. Noor (1998) noticed that in Africa, the allocation of funds for agricultural research grew rapidly in the 1960s, moderately in the 1970s, and stagnated in general in the 1980s in most countries. Soil assessment and mapping were among agricultural research priorities, as it was land suitability assessment oriented. To support agricultural development projects that were initiated, the United Nations Program for Development (UNDP) under the development aid program (DAP), supported many developing countries financially, and technically with the FAO in soil surveys (Brevik and Hartemink, 2010b). It is moreover thanks to the UNDP program that the first documented soil mapping work will be carried out in the British ruled federal part of Cameroon after unification in 1961.

Figure 2.5: Soil map of Eastern Cameroon, North sheet (Segalen et al., 1965)

The project FAO-PNUD (CMR/72/009) started in 1974 and contributes to the capacity building of Ekona research center and their pedological program as well as to a set of studies on soil suitability. During the 1970s, several study reports were published at Ekona research center, mainly on topics related to land evaluation for CDC extension programs (FAO/UNDP, 1977a, 1974). At the same time, several other studies on the suitability of cocoa and coffee will be carried out (FAO/UNDP, 1979, 1977b). Soil surveys for the development of large agricultural farms were funded under UNDP and technically controlled by FAO in the East (FAO/UNDP, 1980) and center (FAO/UNDP, 1975) regions. Fruitful cooperation will be established between the FAO and ORSTOM teams, which will make it possible to establish the soil map of Western Cameroon in 1970 (Vallerie, 1975). The second biggest achievement of this period is the finalization of the soil map of Cameroon at scale 1: 1 000 000 with the missing part from Southern Cameroon (Figure 2.6). The contribution of the Cameroon - Belgium cooperation through the VLIR - Technical University Cooperation, which started at the end of the 1970s, will be decisive to the training of Cameroonian pedologists and the study of the soils of Cameroon.

2.2.4 Soil survey after 1980

At the beginning of the 1980s, soil training and studies in Cameroon was coordinated by a team of Belgian researchers from the University of Ghent as part of the VLIR - Technical University Cooperation. The team supported the last two reforms in agricultural training in Cameroon and conducted several soil survey-related projects across the country. Indeed, while migrating to the University Centre of Dschang, the soil unit head was a Belgian. They remained in Dschang until early in the 1990s when the cooperation ended with the last educational reform in 1993. In addition to the soil maps, there is a set of reference books that have been produced with Cameroonian soil scientists and which are widely used to date for soil knowledge and assessment in Cameroon (Pauwels et al., 1992; Beernaert and Bitondo, 1993; Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005a, 2005b). ENSA and ITA merged in 1988 to form the National Institute of Rural Development (INADER) and the University of Dschang (UDs) was created in 1993, with INADER, replaced by the Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences (FASA). It was the first faculty of agricultural studies in the country, with a department of soil sciences and a laboratory in soil, plants, and water analysis, a laboratory in soil survey and mapping, and a laboratory in soil physics. Several other departments of soil sciences and earth sciences exist to date across the country and continue to provide soil training up to the Ph.D. level.

Figure 2.6: Soil map of Western Cameroon (Vallerie, 1975)

During the Belgian leadership, many soil-related projects were completed. The most important contribution includes the Cameroon soil map at scale 1:1 000 000 (Van Ranst et al., 2007) (Figure 2.7). The map was produced by aggregating 11 maps of Cameroon at scale 1: 500 000 established based on the physicochemical and morphological characterization of Cameroon's regions (Van Ranst et al., 2007).

The second cycle of the UNDP project (CMR/78/002) gets funded for the period 1983-1986. The new phase aimed to develop the section of pedology as a national soil service. The service comprised three complementary sections as follows: (a) at Ekona (south-west) as the base of

central service; (b) at Nkolbisson (Centre-South) for basic research; (c) at Maroua (North) for agro-pedology. The objective of the project was to emphasize the training of national personnel, parallel with the establishment of a large soil map, which is necessary for the pursuit of rational land use and physical planning policy (UNDP, 1983). The project effectively began in 1983 with the creation of the National Soil Center (NSC) as a component of the Institute of Agronomic Research (IRA). In its creation decision, the main tasks assigned were threefold; i) management (centralization, programming, and direct or indirect implementation) of all soil studies across the country, ii) acquisition and vulgarization of pedological information and, iii) training of national soil experts (MESRS, 1983). Through the creation, operationalization, and financing of the center, the Government supported by the UNDP has expressed its interest in promoting economic development based on soil-based scientific and technical acquisitions.

The third cycle of the UNDP project (CMR/83/004), from 1987 to 1991 aimed at providing supplementary support to the NSC with expert assistance to meet the training needs as a continuation since 1974. Following the assessment mission in 1986, the new cycle of the project was expected to (with reduced financial assistance from UNDP) i) continue local personnel training and the soil inventory South of the eight parallel ii) prepare a map of agro-ecological zones, iii) support the program of medium scale-sized agricultural enterprises (UNDP, 1987). In this third cycle, the budgets related to soil investigations were explicitly reduced. This project, with its three cycles, has significantly contributed to the advancement of pedology and knowledge of soils in Cameroon. This project with its three cycles has significantly contributed to the progress of pedology and knowledge of soils in Cameroon more particularly thanks to the NSC which in addition to staff training has strengthened the technical platform of the Yaoundé-Nkolbisson and Ekona laboratories. Such centers have been created in several other countries in sub-Saharan Africa as a tool for planning and development by increasing agricultural yields. The existence of this center, although brief, allowed the realization of many detailed soil surveys. After the third cycle, international organizations such as FAO essentially stopped collecting soil data because of the lack of funds from the UNDP and other bilateral partners (Hartemink, 2002). Most developing countries faced reduced funding and investments in pedological research shrank (Eswaran et al., 2004). Some of the reasons put forward to explain the crisis are external to soil survey, but strongly influenced by the general economic situation of the world at that time. Inappropriate presentation and the poor accuracy of soil information, together with high survey costs, are often to blame, as the soil science jargon is often not user-friendly or user-oriented (Van Ranst et al., 2010).

Legend

CAMEROUN_NOV2007

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| dtl | k/lU-kdO | puU/qE |
| e/adl | k/luU | puV |
| eal/htl | k/luU-huU | sqL |
| etl | k/luU-kuO | tdU |
| fqE | kuU | thU |
| hal | ldU | toE |
| hdO | lhU | tpE |
| hdU | lqU | tqA |
| hhU | luA | tqE |
| hoO | luU | tqI |
| htl | non | tqU |
| huA | nqA | ufE |
| huO | nuA | uoE |
| huU | pdU | upE |
| k/hhU | phU | utL |
| k/lU | puA | |

Figure 2.7: Soil map of Cameroon, scale 1: 1 000 000 (Van Ranst et al., 2007)

Moreover, the general public has never been widely interested in soils, and there is a deep concern about the public profile and appreciation of soil science, as far as the government has never thought of including the valuation of land as a basis for taxation as in many countries, which will imply evaluation and mapping of the soil (White, 1997). As a consequence, a limited number of these NSC have survived and continue to provide laboratory and field survey services. In 1997, the NSC was transformed into IRAD's Soil, Plant Water and Atmosphere Program.

The end of the UNDP project marked a sad turning point in the evolution of soil information investigation in Cameroon. Since then, pedological information has been collected primarily for specific research needs, such as for end-of-study theses, by a few handfuls of producers who integrate the need for soil knowledge into their agricultural production system, or by a few development projects whose soil component only concerns a minor part of their budgets. Despite the budget limitation, training has significantly progressed and many Cameroonian soil experts graduate in Cameroon and abroad each year. On a national level, the training is currently provided by the expertise of Cameroonians, whose most have benefited from training programs in the framework of the bilateral partnerships. At the national symposium of Cameroon Soil Science Society in December 2018, in which the participants included researchers, academics, government officials, private consultants, and industry representatives, the participants came to the resolution calling for improved availability of soil data and better interaction between data users and decision-makers in Cameroon. The call was also made to develop new strategies and policies for soil information collection, storage, and dissemination.

2.2.5 Soil survey renewal in Cameroon

At the global level, apart from a few countries (Belgium, Holland, Poland, Cuba, ...), detailed soil mapping is not very developed. Soil surveys arrived at a crossroads in many countries worldwide and soil survey centers closed down or were privatized and abandoned systematic soil mapping (Van Ranst et al., 2010). Discussing the role of soil science in agricultural development in East Africa, Muchena and Kiome (1995) concluded that it has played a modest role, although this role is still largely unquantified. They noticed that despite the activities of numerous foreign experts, there is still inadequate expertise in some key disciplines such as soil physics, and water management. These observations are also likely applicable to Cameroon, and knowledge of Cameroon's soils remains incomplete, more particularly concerning the current challenges linked to food security and climate change. However, soil information is

difficult to gather, especially at more refined levels of detail. Substantial financial investment is often necessary to obtain soil data, because soils and their properties, and consequently their potential and limitations, change very substantially over short distances, and the skills and expertise necessary to accurately record, measure and map such changes are time and labor extensive.

Several soil studies have been carried out during the last decades in Cameroon. All information collected on soils in the past exists on physical media and remains dispersed across the country. Modernizing Cameroonian agriculture should be based on a robust and reliable soil database, which can use the benefit from technological developments, to provide accurate predictions of soil properties. Given the current economic context, it is unlikely that authorities will agree to support the investment in research needed to fill these gaps, as funds for soil surveys are not available anymore or very difficult to obtain. To satisfy the social demand for freely obtainable and usable soil information and resources, several national and international soil databases have already been developed (Balla et al., 2016). To the best of our knowledge, such a facility does not yet exist in Cameroon. There is an urgent need to consolidate and integrate the soil information already existing and store in databases, with quality-controlled. Previous studies carried out in Cameroon seem to have the potential to be explored for this useful purpose. Our essential concern in this study is to rescue and rejuvenate legacy soil profile data in Cameroon, as input for DSM processes.

Computer techniques, like DSM, may solve the increasing demand for soil information (Van Ranst et al., 2010). DSM spatial tools may be used to improve the soil information for soil protection and soil quality management. As such, digital soil mapping, if supported by sufficient soil data collected in the field, can design much more consistent thematic maps using a transparent and repeatable approach and providing more information on the accuracy of the presented data yet, the current demands for soil data are real challenges and among the soil information factors, anthropogenic disturbance starts to play an increasingly important role, influencing the intensity of soil processes and as such, changing soil functioning.

Soil mapping is slowly coming back on research agendas in Cameroon. The implementation of the government's second-generation agriculture strategy requires precise and high-resolution information on the distribution of soils in Cameroon. Besides, land use plans for the sustainable development of the territory (Regional and Local) are being developed, and require a variety of soil information. To support the government in these actions, their partners in bilateral

cooperation are increasingly interested in the production of soil information, with priority on strengthening the capacity of technical personnel and improving technical platforms for soil studies. Current initiatives include the Project on Soil and Subsoil Resources of North and South-West Regions (PRESS NO & SW), which is a bilateral technical project in the framework of German Cooperation between MINEPAT/DATZF and BGR, to support land use planning in Cameroon with geospatial database contributions to geo-resource aspects, with a focus on soil, for the North and the South-West regions. The soil fertility map project, with the 'Office chérifien des phosphates' (OCP), is also to be credited. The OCP project is part of the partnership agreement signed between the OCP Foundation and the Cameroonian ministry of agriculture (MINADER). The objective of the project is the development of a soil fertility map in Cameroon and the construction of a soil and fertilizer analysis laboratory in Yaounde.

2.3 NEED OF SOIL INFORMATION IN CAMEROON

Efforts have been made to describe the distribution of soils in Cameroon since pre-colonial times and have continued for several decades after independence (Section 2.2). Soil survey, in particular, has gone through a deep cut-off in the last years influencing the production of information and its impact on decision making. However, soil information is fundamental, especially in addressing the key needs of the countries and regions in many fields of application and decision-making. While the agricultural use of soils is extremely important, the need for soil data is rapidly expanding to a range of fields, including health, food security, hydrological modeling, climate change, community planning, taxation, etc. Soil information should be provided to address the current demands and future challenges.

2.3.1 Sustainable development planning

The purpose of planning is to manage the development and use of resources in the long-term public interest. Soil is a multipurpose and multifunctional object which will always remain the medium that satisfies primary human needs for food and shelter. It is a key part of our environment and is a non-renewable resource. Soils are the most important and valuable resource, and mounting pressures upon them are constantly making this resource more and more valuable, though they are subjected to grave abuse and misuse through improper land use development (Bauer, 1974). Soil degradation can have major implications not just for soils and the benefits they provide but also for air and water quality as well as our climate, biodiversity, and economy. Knowledge of the soil resource and its ability to sustain development not only

help to avoid such problems but can also contribute to reducing rural and urban development costs. Emphasis is therefore placed upon the knowledge of the varied nature and properties of soils and, consequently, upon the need for appropriate management to be considered during the planning process. Furthermore, surveying soils is always a financially profitable investment, as it is an instrument that is almost certain to return an economic, social, and environmental profit for several reasons (Bie and Ulph, 1972). According to Western (1978) estimates, in several countries, the cost-benefit of doing a soil survey can be 1:125 or more. It supports land-use decisions for the future and helps in setting rules to meet the socio-political objectives, whilst preserving the delicate balance between economic and ecological aspects of land and land use. For example, optimum yields are achieved when land use and management are adapted to local soil conditions. Evidence-based planning decisions should be based on thematic soil maps. The lack of soil information was pointed out as the cause of the failure of many development programs. In regions where the economy is predominantly based on agriculture, an intimate knowledge of the soils, their character, spatial distribution, and Physico-chemical properties is a prerequisite for land use and sustainable development planning (Demattê et al., 2002).

Proper consideration of soils through the planning system is needed to make sure that soils can deliver essential functions vital for the sustainability of the environment and economy. Soil changes in time are of major importance to funding agencies and policymakers who need to justify investments and implemented policies in terms of a consequent positive change. It could also serve farmers, for instance, in precision farming and to rationalize fertilizer use. Adequate planning and decision making about land use must be facilitated by soil information, provided on a national soils policy framework (Verheye, 1997). Soil information can be used for a variety of planning purposes including land use planning, environmental farm planning, and watershed management planning, etc. All of these planning processes attract a range of stakeholders that are interested in the activities that take place in their communities.

In Cameroon, development planning is a multi-level process, starting at the national level with the National Land Use and Sustainable Development plan (SNADDT) where the main policy orientations are defined as a reference framework to structure the national territory and achieve the development objectives. The second level of planning is regional, known as the regional land use and sustainable development plan (SRADDT). It specifies the fundamental and medium-term guidelines for the sustainable development of a regional territory and its planning principles. At the local level, the local spatial planning and sustainable development plan (PLADDT) is considered. It is the local decision-making guide local people and their

representatives use to make decisions about allocating land, providing appropriate services, promoting a good quality of life for residents, ensuring orderly development and the prudent use of natural resources, to ensure that development occurs in ways that are compatible with the environment. The intent of these is to designate and protect land for certain purposes to promote development, avoid land-use conflicts, protect property values, provide efficient servicing, promote a healthy and safe living environment and protect natural resources.

Cameroon's national land-use plan has already been completed, and regional plans for some regions of the country are being drawn up. With the decentralization process being implemented, local development plans will soon be initiated. However, the inclusion of soil information in the elaboration of these plans is not respected, due to the lack of adequate soil information. In countries such as Scotland, soil information is considered an integral and compulsory part of the planning process. Any proposal that includes physical development or changes in land use or land management likely to affect soil with possible consequences for the wider environment, society, and the economy should provide soil development management, and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). The consideration of soil as part of the development management and EIA process will help identify appropriate mitigation to minimize soil degradation and maintain soil quality. Such examples should be applied in Cameroon to ensure effective consideration of soils in the formulation of effective sustainable development policies. Whereof, to help avoid further abuse and misuse of soils, a need exists in any comprehensive planning program to examine not only how land and soils are presently used but how they can best be used and managed. This requires definitive data about the geographic location of the various kinds of soils; about the physical, chemical, and biological properties of these soils; and about the capability of these soils to support various kinds of rural and urban land uses. Most importantly, it requires the use of such data to the greatest extent possible in guiding both rural and urban development and expansion (Bauer, 1974).

2.3.2 Climate change mitigation

Global warming has become a key question for humanity's preservation and represents a threat to world economies. Outcomes of climate negotiations usually lead to political involvement and the establishment of a legally binding agreement for financial and technological participation to impact climate change. Several countries and international organizations are committed to greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction policies and mechanisms for climate change mitigation. During the presentation of country's action plan for the 2015 Paris Climate change

conference (COP 21), Cameroon unveiled an ambitious schedule which mainly consists in integrating climate changes to the national planning, sectoral policies and among other things, reinforce forests management, conservation of biodiversity, greening (intensified and sedentary) agricultural policy, increasing energy supply and improving power efficiency, achieve 25% of renewable energies by 2035. Using 2010 as the baseline year, the country intends to decrease by 32%, by 2035, the carbon-effect resulting from its development (Business in Cameroon, 2015). Furthermore, Cameroon is a signatory of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, under which the country is obliged to report on various indicators on GHG emissions as well as changes in soil carbon. Such courageous and relevant commitments require illustrating how the soil can contribute to their achievement.

Soils act as sources and sinks for greenhouse gases (GHG) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Oertel et al., 2016). Several factors make it possible to control the fluxes of GHG in the soil (Figure 2.8). These factors are directly related to the Physico-chemical, mineralogical, and biological composition of the soil. The effective monitoring of these indicators cannot be done without prior spatial knowledge of the distribution of soils and its properties.

Figure 2.8: Key drivers of GHG emissions from soils (Oertel et al., 2016)

Moreover, soils are the largest store of terrestrial carbon on Earth (Lal, 2004). Conserving and improving soil carbon through judicious soil use and land management can help to mitigate climate change. Farmers and other stakeholders can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions from

the soil by practices such as conservation tillage, residue management, and multiple cropping. Such interventions increase the input of organic matter into the soil and reduce the decomposition of soil organic matter. However, how can land managers and planners determine consistently the net effect of specific land-use practices without accurate soil information? Policymakers and other stakeholders require reliable data and tools to support informed decisions concerning possible actions aimed at mitigation and adaptation.

Soil information needed for carbon monitoring at a relatively detailed scale is vital to the global modelling community, in particular, those concerned with mitigating climate change and food security. Sustainable improvements in soil and land management, allowing the experience to be shared among farmers and scientists across countries and regions and to promote win-win solutions while addressing controversial issues such as payments for ecosystem services are also highly demanded. However, to improve decision-making towards improved soil management for climate change mitigation, sufficiently detailed quantitative data sets and methodologies that enable spatial and temporal quantification of SOC levels and dynamics in soils, are required. Since both storage and emission capacities may be large, precise quantifications are needed to obtain reliable global budgets that are necessary for land-use management (agriculture, forestry), global change, and climate research. National and local maps for soil function and properties must therefore urgently be provided and regularly updated to contribute to existing climate change mitigation initiatives, as well as to comply with international reporting obligations.

2.3.3 Agricultural production and food security

Agriculture is one of the most important components of our society and depends on productive soils. Agriculture makes a long-term economic return and environmental sense for sustainable land use plans to encourage the protection of both prime agricultural lands and viable lower-class lands that are used for agriculture and the conservation of soil. Soil is a critical part of successful agriculture and is the source of the nutrients that we use to grow crops. The world's soil potential is not yet used to its maximum, and there are still vast reserves of cultivatable land suitable for crop production, particularly in the intertropical belt (Verheye, 1997). However, healthy soils are critical to agriculture, and both are essential to enabling food security. Soil-related challenges include using soils and other natural resources sustainably, combating land and soil degradation, avoiding further reduction of soil-related ecosystem services, and ensuring that all agricultural land is managed sustainably. Often, there is a trade-

off between productivity goals related to immediate human needs on the one hand, and ensuring long-term continuation of ecosystem services on the other. While good agricultural soils are frequently referred to as the "fertile substrate", not all soils are suitable for growing crops. Ideal soils for agriculture are balanced in contributions from mineral components, soil organic matter (SOM), air, and water. The balanced contributions of these components allow for water retention and drainage, oxygen in the root zone, nutrients to facilitate crop growth, and they provide physical support for plants.

The agriculture sector in Cameroon is amongst the main occupations for over 70% of citizens and contributes enormously to the country's economy (Abia et al., 2016). Cameroon is no different than other African nations in that its agricultural sector is vital to its economy, its agricultural technology and yields lag behind non-African developing countries, and its agricultural potential is great, with 15% of the national territory (475 000 km²) as arable land. Cameroon is the breadbasket for the Central African Sub-region, and due to its agro-ecological diversity, the country has great potentials for agricultural production, which could contribute to the current challenging food demand.

Agriculture occupies a fundamental place in the country's development strategy for 2035 (DSCE, 2009). However, the gap between actual and potential yields remain significantly large for most crops (Yengoh and Ardo, 2014). Closing the yield gap requires detailed information about the biophysical environment, crop management as well as socio-economic conditions in which production is conducted. However, data needed to support sustainable agricultural policy, are often not available, while rapid population growth puts unprecedented pressure on soils (Kopittke et al., 2019). As food production strongly depends on the availability of nutrients, fertilization and soil fertility constraints are the most constrained management and edaphic factors explaining yield disparities (Ciceri and Allanore, 2019). Furthermore, concerning fertilization, quantity-related issues are more often limited compared to factors related to the timing of application. Thus, providing soil information to facilitate decision-making for the implementation of agricultural policies is a prerequisite step for the sustainable intensification of agricultural production.

Intensive use of fertilizers was suggested as a strategy to increase and improve sustainable food needs in Cameroon (Abia et al., 2016). Such intensification, without prior control of information on soils and the quantities to be provided according to specific soil constraints, could be dangerous for the environment and the profitability of these production systems.

Besides, agricultural models for crop growth improvement such as DSSAT or fertility evaluation (QUEFTS) for rationalization of fertilizer use in agricultural production require several soil parameters, which are often not available. Thus, accurate and detailed soil information will enable a much better assessment of where soils that can be cultivated are located. From there, the approximate management strategies would adapt to meet the government objective on agricultural prospective in Cameroon. There are also growing technologies used to make modern agriculture more efficient, which can be applied in Cameroon. Examples include global positioning systems (GPS) and large computerized harvesters under precision agriculture, which might likely make production more efficient. With precision agriculture, farmers and soils work better, not harder.

2.3.4 Hydrological modelling

Although water and soil have been managed and studied as separate specialized scientific disciplines since ancient times, each has incorporated some of the subject matter of the other (Amerman, 1955). Regarding the soil, it is a very important part of the physical framework of most hydrologic systems. Soil properties and their spatial variation should be captured in hydrological models for accurate water quantity and quality predictions and estimation of the hydrologic sensitivity of the land to change (Paterson et al., 2015). Soils play a major role in catchment hydrology by facilitating infiltration, controlling overland flow, redistributing water through the root zone, storing water for evapotranspiration and recharging groundwater aquifers, as well as a first-order control on the partitioning of hydrological flow paths, residence time distributions and water storage (Soulsby and Tetzlaff, 2008). Interpretation of soil properties can, therefore, serve as an indicator of the dominant hydrological processes and assist in structuring and configuration of hydrological models. On the other side, water is a primary agent in soil genesis, resulting in the development of soil properties and containing unique signatures of the way they were formed. Water is, therefore, an essential resource in the status and dynamics of soils (Lvovich, 1980). Soil inputs in hydrological models vary greatly between different models, but typically include water retention characteristics, hydraulic conductivities, storage ability (depth and porosity), and infiltration rates. These soil parameters are often not directly available and frequently estimated using pedotransfert functions (Al-Qinna and Jaber, 2013), which are mathematical relations between easily measured properties, e.g. texture, and properties that are tedious and expensive to measure, e.g. water retention curves. For the needs

of hydrological modeling, soil information in the form of basic data allowing to estimate the hydraulic soil parameters through pedotransfert functions are of high demand.

2.3.5 Health sector

Soils are home to a remarkable array of biodiversity with some estimates stating that 25% of the Earth's species find their home in soils (Jeffery and Van der Putten, 2011). A typical teaspoon of native grassland soil would contain between 600 to 800 million individual bacteria that are members of perhaps 10,000 species; several miles of fungi and perhaps 5000 species of fungi; and about 10,000 individual protozoa split into three main groups, i.e., flagellates, amoebae and ciliates, and perhaps 1000 species of protozoa (Sullivan, 2004). Of these organisms, the vast majority are not of any threat to human health. However, some are capable of causing diseases in humans (Lucas, 2006). They act either as opportunistic pathogens that take advantage of susceptible individuals, such as those who are immuno-compromised; or as obligate pathogens which must infect humans to complete their life-cycles (Otten and Gilligan, 2006). Thus, new and existing diseases related to humans, plants, or livestock health involve a range of potential factors, one of which may be soil type or soil specific conditions, usually as a potential host to organisms (Paterson et al., 2015). A good soil information infrastructure will help to address these, whether it refers to high potential soils that should preferably not be disturbed or soil with specific requirement managements. The amount of knowledge, as well as the level of detail, about soils occurring, will make a difference to almost all decisions that are taken to tackle soil induced health insecurity. In Cameroon, knowledge of soils in relation to diseases likely to develop remains very little documented, despite the abundant diversity of soils in Cameroon.

2.3.6 Soil policy in Cameroon

A national soils policy is a set of guidelines aimed at ensuring and stimulating optimum utilization of the land on a sustained basis without lowering productivity and limiting direct or indirect damage to the environment (Verheye, 1997). According to Verheye (1997) a national soils policy covers four basic aspects, addressing technical, socio-economic, institutional, and legal elements. In broad terms, national soils policies should aim to bring about activities which will:

- decide about future land in terms of various alternatives related to the national development objectives;
- assess available land resources and improve soil productivity by applying better management techniques or by developing and promoting more productive agricultural systems;
- enlarge cropping areas and/or improve the quality of available agricultural land wherever feasible;
- slow down losses of agricultural and forest land, monitor changes in soil quality and quantity, and evaluate the way land is used;
- bring to the attention of all concerned the dangers and adverse consequences of soil degradation and the needs for conservation and appropriate legislation; and
- create or improve the capability of national institutions to carry out these aims.

At the institutional level in Cameroon, four main ministries deal with issues related to soil information. The Ministry of Scientific Research and Innovation (MINRESI), in particular through its technical body in charge of agricultural research, the Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD). The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER), Ministry of Nature Protection, Environment and Sustainable Development (MINEPDED), Minister of Higher Education (MINESUP). Each institution, as far as it is concerned, carries out activities related to the achievement of its objectives. However, it is necessary to postpone the existence of several overlapping activities between these different institutions. This is explained by the nonexistence of a main national entity for the coordination of activities on soils. There is thus an urgent need to establish specifications for the different institutions to better coordinate the activities on the soils in Cameroon, and make one of the institutions responsible for the development and monitoring of national policy. In addition to these main actors, other government institutions such as the Ministry of Economy, Planning and Sustainable Development (MINEPAT), and the Ministry of Forests and Wildlife (MINFOF) are involved in related activities related to soils. Private institutions, national and international non-governmental organizations support the government in these actions.

In 2007, at the instigation of MINEPAT, the strategic document for water and soil management in the sylvo-agro-pastoral area of Cameroon was developed. In the diagnosis, two main problems were identified in the sustainable management of soils in the rural sector. These constraints are the inadequacies of the institutional and regulatory framework and constraints related to sustainable soil management.

As an insufficiency in the institutional and regulatory framework, it has been observed that there is a diversity of initiatives underway sometimes for the same objectives, sometimes with weak or poor coordination of the different actors, insufficient in regulatory texts which, moreover are poorly respected. It is, therefore, necessary to draft legislative texts in the area of soil management in Cameroon and to regulate the sector by making the actors responsible by precise specifications to avoid overlapping of activities and facilitate coordination (MINEPAT, 2007).

The main problems identified for the sustainable management of soils are insufficient knowledge, anthropogenic degradation, inappropriate and uncoordinated allocation of soils, difficult access to arable land, poor development of sustainable management practices (research and extension), high cost in time and money of restoration, the aggressiveness of climatic factors. The major consequences of soil degradation are Insecurity and threat to social peace, degradation of water resources, degradation of infrastructure, bare land, scarcity of arable land, loss of soil productivity, loss of biodiversity, and climatic changes.

The strategic options proposed to resolve the dignified problems are the establishment of adequate coordination and regulatory framework for the various interventions, the strengthening of access to information and training on soils, actions aimed at improving knowledge of soils, promotion, and popularization of techniques to combat anthropogenic degradation, and measures aimed at reducing the costs of restoring soil production capacities. Although the effective implementation of this strategic document in the area concerned is questionable, the initiative to produce it remains a beneficial action in the context of soil management policies in Cameroon. However, a national strategy should be developed, followed by several sub-strategies appropriate to the specificities of the soil diversity of the country.

2.3.7 Soil information system

Accurate soil information forms essential components of environmental characterization and monitoring. As such, there is a growing demand for soil information to cope with many political and environmental issues, such as food security, land suitability, land capability, developmental planning, climate change, freshwater scarcity, biodiversity loss, natural hazards, land management, and soil threats. Basically, soil surveys provide information needed for achieving aforesaid purposes (Dwivedi, 2017). However, for generating derivative information on soils to address the foregoing challenges calls for robust digital databases on soil resources. Once the

information on soils is generated using a common concept of inventorying soil resources, the next step would be to develop a standard, uniform, and usable database. Now being in a digital soil information age, a vast array of applications incorporating and developing soil information, together with complementary natural resource information, can be envisaged.

A soil information system (SIS) is a collection of people, activities, and procedures involving systematic, geographically referenced soil data collection, storage, manipulation, and retrieval using procedures of data processing (Dwivedi, 2017). They belong to the family of geographical information systems (GIS) and are often called soil data banks or soil data processing units. According to Keller (2013), SIS can also be seen as a storage and management system for soil maps and profile characteristics, along with additional services, e.g., to derive data lacking in the original dataset, to link a profile to geometrical data, or to analyze data by calculating indexes. SIS provides the basis for assessing the soil's ability to perform its multitude of functions and provide its related services, as they are designed to store and process data in a structured technical environment. Baritz et al. (2008) reported 8 key purposes for a soil information system:

- ✓ decision making in agriculture and forestry,
- ✓ local and regional spatial planning,
- ✓ evaluation of polluted soils,
- ✓ detection of spatial and temporal trends,
- ✓ reporting in soil protection and other related environmental assessments,
- ✓ supporting environmental evaluation systems,
- ✓ data exchange, and quality control,
- ✓ harmonizing data sets.

However, in conjunction with the various data sources and the purposes of SIS, Keller (2013) identified several data issues that have to be addressed during an SIS development, such as assuring comparability and transparency of soil data (guidelines and reference standards), interoperability and harmonization of soil information, transparency using proper methodological descriptions and access rights. For access rights and security purposes, restrictions are found in many soil information systems and/or related Web services. Along with the technical development of SIS, the main challenge is to implement procedures to achieve consistently harmonized soil data. Such procedures include the definition of the common data model comprising the metadata, recoding of legacy soil profile data with different data keys,

transformation, and screening rules, screening and visualization of invalid or implausible datasets, the definition of mandatory database attributes and mandatory query attributes, as well as recommending data workflows for SIS users (Keller, 2013).

Due to its efficiency, the Soil Information System is now an indispensable tool for soil data management at several decision-making levels. Thus, many types of SIS exist depending on the objectives or the administrative boundaries. The most common systems are national, regional, continental, or global. Thereby, realizing the importance of standardized information on soils in SIS for various developmental and research purposes, several countries including the USA, Canada, Australia, Ireland, Ethiopia, and India have developed their soil information systems. Table 2.1 illustrates some national soil information systems.

Table 2.1: Selected national soil information systems

Country	Abbreviation	Full name	profiles
Argentina	SISINTA	Soil Information system of INTA	5878
Hungary	SIMS	Hungarian Soil Information and Monitoring System	1,234
Brazil	BDSolos	Brazilian Soil Information System	6195
Austria	BORIS	Boden Information System	10,000
Hungary	TIM	Soil Information and Monitoring System	1,200
USA	NASIS	National Soils Information System	24,000
Australia	ASRIS	Australian Soil Resource Information System	nd
Canada	CanSIS	Canadian Soil Information Service	nd
Ethiopia	EthioSIS	Ethiopian Soil Information System	nd

nd = Not determined

Out of all the national soil information systems, one of the most interesting on which a comment seems essential is that of Ethiopia. This case is interesting firstly because it is a case close to us (Sub-Saharan Africa), and secondly because the government of Ethiopia has made considerable efforts for national investigation on soils and not just relying on legacy soil data for a SIS. Indeed, EthioSIS is the first initiative of its kind in Africa, employing remote sensing satellite technology and other state-of-the-art techniques for soil surveying. EthioSIS project has gathered hundreds of thousands of soil samples on a grid-based survey from the entire country to develop 22 different soil property maps and fertilizer recommendations for each region. This comprehensive soil assessment is required to achieve an ambitious goal to map the country's soil and compile in-depth soil fertility information, which could be eventually be used to well inform the fertilizer policies and recommendations and promote significantly higher crop yields. The project demonstrated that tailored specific fertilizer type application can replenish the fertility of a variety of soils found to be deficient in several essential nutrients. The project's extensive soil sampling and laboratory analysis work has led to the recommendation on ways

to improve soil health and fertility, including the use of at least 12 different fertilizers, which can be applied with or without potash depending on the status of each soil, to address the nutrient deficiencies of soils around the country.

This is an example that several Sub-Saharan African countries should follow, in particular Cameroon, to sustainably reduce the food deficit currently observed under conditions that make it possible to preserve the environment. Besides, digital storage of the soil data in an SIS prevents their loss and made them available to other scientists and decision-makers (Nachtergaele and Van Ranst, 2003). Such quantitative information is also very useful in the digital soil mapping process aimed at filling the gaps in areas that have either been not covered by regular soil surveys or have very scanty information on soils. To address the issue of gap filling in soil surveys Lagacherie and Mcbratney (2007) are of the view that soil spatial information systems need to extend their functionalities from the storage and the use of digitized soil maps to the generation of soil maps as in advanced SIS. There is a high need for Cameroon to set up a soil information system, which should allow the implementation of sustainable policies in terms of soil management to support the major challenges facing the country. This study is a precursor and will establish the foundations for a soil information system in Cameroon, based on legacy soil data.

2.4 DIGITAL SOIL MAPPING APPROACH

Given the relative dearth of and the huge demand for quantitative spatial soil information, new approaches to develop and implement provisions of soil data was necessary and highly expected. The explosion of new advances in the fields of information technology, satellite imagery, digital elevation models, geostatistics, and machine learning has enabled the establishment of various new soil data provision techniques. Flexible and quantitative methods to study soils and their relation or function to environmental factors, collectively known as digital soil mapping (DSM) are used (Hartemink and McBratney, 2008). DSM can be defined as the creation, and population of spatial soil information systems by the use of field and laboratory observational methods coupled with spatial and non-spatial soil inference systems (Lagacherie and Mcbratney, 2007). It can provide easily updatable soil characteristics maps, that meet the specific needs of various users at relatively low cost in a short time frame. DSM quantifies the huge amount of tacit knowledge gained during soil surveys, which simply went astray with conventional methods. DSM thus aims at utilizing various new technologies to

apply expert tacit knowledge to produce the same or better quality soil maps as conventional soil surveys at a fraction of the price (Van Zijl, 2013).

2.4.1 Digital soil mapping theoretical setting

Soil mapping is the term often used to describe the process of understanding and predicting the spatial distribution of soils. It is a process that involves collecting field observations (including recording soil profile descriptions), analyzing soil properties in the laboratory, describing landscape characteristics, and, ultimately, producing soil maps. Soil maps are the most widely used end-products of the soil mapping process since they illustrate the geographic distribution of soil types, soil properties (such as physical, chemical, and biological properties), and landscape characteristics.

With the expansion of geographic information systems (GIS), digital representations of soil information were initiated in the late 1970s (Tomlinson, 1978; Webster et al., 1979). These pioneering works in the digital era of soil mapping have focused specifically on the digitization of soil information for their integration into GIS software. According to Burrough (1991) soil survey applications were among the first uses of GIS. It's a decade later that the approaches to digital soil mapping as currently known began to be reported (Bell et al., 1992; McKenzie and Austin, 1993). The rapid evolution of numerical analysis techniques and the expansion of methods for observing and measuring environmental data has made it possible to revisit Jenny's (1941) conceptual equation and to consider undertaking soil mapping directly using empirical and deterministic methods. Indeed, Jenny (1941) described the formation and the variability, of soils to the “five factors of soil formation”, with a conceptual pedologic model, expressed as follows in the equation 2.1:

$$S = f(cl, o, r, p, t) \quad (2.1)$$

where properties of soil (S) at a given location are considered to be a function of climate (cl), organisms (o), relief (r), and parent material (p) interaction over time (t).

Advances in new technologies have offered great opportunities for building a valuable soil knowledge base. The conceptual basis for DSM was formalized in 2003 (McBratney et al., 2003). The fundamental principle of digital soil mapping lies in drawing correlations between soil and other factors that are easier to map than the soil. Equation 2.2 shows the relationship mathematically.

$$S = f(Q) + e \quad (2.2)$$

With S , the soil class or property to be mapped; Q , factors use to map S ; and e , the error involved with the estimation.

McBratney et al. (2003) refined and extended the initial Jenny's *clorpt* model to be considered for quantitative prediction of soil variability and distribution as a function of seven factors (Equation 2.3):

$$S = f(s, c, o, r, p, a, n) \quad (2.3)$$

With; S = soil class or property to be mapped

s = soil, or other properties of soil at a point

c = climate or climatic properties at a point

o = organisms, such as vegetation, fauna or human activity at a point

r = relief, topography and landscape attributes

p = parent material

a = age, the time factor

n = spatial location.

The *scorpan* model highlights the need for georeferenced soil information and its relationship with environmental controllers of soil variation to predict the spatial distribution of soils. However, not all seven factors need to be used at once, they are included in the model according to their availability and it is assumed that the more factors are included, the better the prediction will be (McBratney et al., 2003). The basis of DSM is the application of pedometric methods that predict the spatial and temporal distribution of soil types and soil properties. DSM methods have proven valuable for developing quantitative, more accurate, and more precise soil maps. Digital soil maps illustrate the spatial distribution of soil classes or properties and can document the uncertainty of the soil prediction. DSM better captures the spatial variability and reduces the need to aggregate soil types based on a set mapping scale (Zhu et al., 2001), and it can facilitate the rapid inventory, re-inventory, and project-based management of lands in a changing environment (Kienast-Brown et al., 2017).

2.4.2 Digital soil mapping vs conventional soil mapping

As described in Mulder (2013), conventional soil mapping (CSM) typically employs the free survey method to create soil maps. First, a mental soil-landscape model is made. Soil

boundaries are defined based on landscape features from aerial photograph interpretations. Next, sample locations are selected that are likely to be most informative. The mental model is refined based on these field observations. Additional samples might be obtained and finally, the map unit composition is determined. The map is a general-purpose map with soil classes and additional soil profile descriptions characterizing each map unit (Zhu et al., 2001). However, the conventional methods of soil survey do not satisfy the growing demand for soil maps, due to being labor-intensive and expensive. Furthermore, the cost of CSM can be greatly reduced by DSM methods (Van Zijl, 2013). The important distinction between DSM and CSM is that DSM utilizes quantitative inference models to generate predictions of soil classes or soil properties in a geographic database (raster). The major differences, strengths, and also limitations are coming from the way the environmental covariates are represented in the procedure. Digital soil mapping requires digital data sources (gridded raster layer) as input variables (covariates) for the quantitative models. Then, DSM provides the means for supplying soil information in format and resolution compatible with other fundamental data sets from remote sensing, terrain analysis, and other systems for mapping, monitoring, and forecasting biophysical processes. There is also growing agreement indicating that digital soil mapping techniques offer the potential to greatly accelerate the rate of map production and update. This makes DSM flexible and more suitable in quickly providing soil information for specific applications compared to CSM (Mulder, 2013), as well as it represents a ground-breaking solution compared to conventional soil survey by its ability to exploit large sets of spatial data, to produce uncertainty estimates associated with soil predictions and can be revised once new data are collected (Lagacherie and Mcbratney, 2007).

2.4.3 Data requirements for digital soil mapping

The DSM approach is both soil and environmental data-centered and so uses these data as a starting point to study the spatial distribution of soils and soil properties. To create a digital soil map, one requires sufficient soil (point data, soil map, land type inventory) and soil-forming factors also known as environmental variables (digital elevation models, satellite images, geological map) information to decipher the soil – environment relationship (Paterson et al., 2015).

2.4.3.1 Soil data

In general, DSM requires georeferenced soil data in a coordinate reference system (CRS). The ideal situation would be to organize intensive data collection campaigns and laboratory analysis to gather the data required to feed and run digital soil mapping algorithms. Unfortunately, in real situations, such soil information is very limited and the deficiency is exacerbated in developing countries such as Cameroon. The lack of soil data is most serious in developing countries where field data have always been few and often hastily gathered. However, following the pressing necessity to have soil geospatial data required to address the current urgent challenges (food security, climate change mitigation, etc.), intensive soil survey campaigns are very unlikely to happen shortly and would be very expensive. New huge surveys are in many contexts infeasible, whereas many areas of the world have been surveyed in the past, the results of these known as “legacy” soil information. Due to limited resources for new soil surveys, legacy soil inventories are often the major public source of soil data (Rasaei et al., 2020). According to Dent and Ahmed (1995), it is better to use legacy primary field data where these can be traced, however old they may be. Thus, legacy soil data have a major role to play in DSM, especially in the case of the soil data-poor countries (Odeh et al., 2012). Accordingly, attempts to keep this valuable information from destruction (Rossiter, 2008; Arrouays et al., 2017a), reuse and enhance their reliability through updating via new field samplings and DSM (McBratney et al., 2003) techniques, and use as an input in DSM process have been increasing over the past decades. Using legacy soil data is however not free of challenges. Dent and Ahmed (1995) identified two common problems with using old survey data: (i) the quality of the data may be unknown and must, therefore, be tested; (ii) the data may not exactly match today’s need for information and must, therefore, be reinterpreted. Using freshly collected data remains the best option.

Traditional soil analysis (field sampling + lab analysis) is a costly and time-consuming process, which often limits the density of observations made as well as the number of properties that can be measured for a specific site. A recent review has shown that NIR analysis can be reliably used to measure several soil properties, especially soil organic matter, mineralogy, texture, and water content. Cation exchange capacity, nutrient content, soil color, and pH have also been measured using NIR analysis with a proximal soil sensing (PSS) approach, which is the use of field-based sensors to obtain signals from the soil when the sensor’s detector is in contact with or close to the soil (McBratney et al., 2006; Rossel et al., 2016; Stenberg et al., 2010; Teng et al., 2018; Terra et al., 2018; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2017, 2011, 2006; Viscarra Rossel and

Webster, 2011). Proximal soil sensing provides high spectral resolution data from individually sampled sites (Mulder, 2013). These new techniques which have been applied with satisfactory results in many countries represent new lines of research to further explore in Cameroon for the production of soil data or at least facilitate the updating of maps produced with legacy soil data. The pioneering work in the application of this method of collecting data on soils in the western highlands of Cameroon constitutes an important basis (Takoutsing et al., 2018, 2017, 2016a, 2013).

2.4.3.2 Environmental covariates

Traditionally, remotely sensed imagery has been used in conventional soil mapping to support the segmentation of the landscape into homogeneous soil-landscape units from which soil composition was assessed by field sampling. With the great explosion in computation and information technology, have come vast amounts of quantitative data and tools in all field of endeavor. Increasingly, remotely sensed ancillary data are being used with mathematical models to add value to the legacy soil data. Remote sensing provides essential information to make DSM successful and is especially suitable for large-scale studies where soil legacy data is sparse (Mulder, 2013). Environmental covariates such as satellite images are considered to compute their correlation with soil properties and used as a secondary data source to support spatial interpolation of sparsely sampled soil property data. The extensive review of remote sensing tools for soil assessment was done by (Dwivedi, 2017). Nevertheless, a common criticism is that remote sensing observations are often limited to the first few centimeters of the surface, and allows spatial explicit characterization of soil properties at the soil surface. The set of covariates used in this study is described in section 3.2.2.

2.4.4 Spatial prediction and machine learning algorithms in DSM

DSM employs several modeling techniques for spatial prediction of soil class and attributes. These techniques can be broadly grouped into two major categories (i) spatial prediction models including geostatistical models (e.g. kriging), statistical models (e.g multiple linear regression) and their hybrids (e.g. regression kriging), and (ii) data mining tools such as regression or decision trees, neural networks, boosting machines and random forest (Akpa, 2016a). In this study, although the methods generally encountered in DSM literature are presented, only random forest and generalized boosted regression trees with their hybrids with ordinary kriging and inverse distance weighting methods were used because of their robustness.

2.4.4.1 Random Forest (RF)

Random forest (RF) is a nonparametric multivariate algorithm, developed as an extension of regression trees to improve prediction accuracy and reduce model overfitting (Breiman, 2001; Liaw and Wiener, 2002). In the training procedure, the RF algorithm produces multiple trees. Each tree is independently constructed based on a unique bootstrap sample (sample with replacement) from the original data set. RF has several advantages over other prediction models and is rather robust to noise and irrelevant features, which makes it a favorable choice for soil properties modeling (Viscarra Rossel and Behrens, 2010). However, RF requires a sufficiently large training set of data to calibrate the model. RF has been successfully applied in many soil assessment studies, with demonstrated strong performance (Chen et al., 2018b; Deng et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2015; Heung et al., 2014; Ließ et al., 2012). Furthermore, RF provides also the model variable importance, i.e. it ranks the controlling factors of the covariate of interest.

2.4.4.2 Boosted regression trees (GBR)

The GBR algorithm is a procedure in which a subset of the data is randomly selected to iteratively fit new tree models to minimize the loss function and provides greater predictive performance compared to regression trees by aggregating several regression trees (Sindayihebura et al., 2017). The GBR uses a specialized form of stochastic gradient boosting as described in Friedman (2001). The stochastic characteristic of the algorithm relies on the fact that only a subset of the dataset is used for fitting the base learner on a given iteration. The subset is produced in each iteration using a uniform random draw without replacement (Martin et al., 2014), which improve the model prediction power and minimize the overfitting risk. Computing options are also available for deciding when to stop adding base learners to the model. One of them, based on internal cross-validation, was shown to be the most efficient one for avoiding overfitting (Lawrence et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2017). Furthermore, GBR provides valuable tools for interpreting the behavior and characteristic of the models, such as the variable importance index for assessing the contribution of predictors and partial dependence plots for assessing the relationships between predictors and the predicted variable (Martin et al., 2014).

2.4.4.3 Regression kriging (RK)

Regression-kriging (RK) is a spatial prediction technique that combines a regression of the dependent variable on auxiliary variables (such as parameters derived from digital elevation modeling, remote sensing/imagery, and thematic maps) with kriging of the regression residuals.

It is mathematically equivalent to the interpolation method variously called Universal kriging and kriging with external drift, where auxiliary predictors are used directly to solve the kriging weights (Hengl et al., 2004). The RK model assumes that the residuals are generated from a normally distributed, second-order stationarity random process—i.e. a random process that has a constant mean and variance, and a spatial correlation that only depends on the separation distance between locations and not on the locations themselves. This method by its flexibility allows integrating several regression approaches, which allows it to have several variants. In digital soil mapping, it is the most widely used hybrid method (Akpa, 2016b; Arrouays et al., 2014; Hengl et al., 2015; Li et al., 2017; Malone et al., 2017; Patton et al., 2018; Rentschler et al., 2019; Taghizadeh-Mehrjardi et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2009a). In this study, we compare the performance of RK and the hybrid regression with the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) method for the national estimation of soil properties.

2.4.4.4 Classification and regression tree (CART)

Classification and regression trees (CART) are machine-learning methods for constructing prediction models from data. The models are obtained by recursively partitioning the data space and fitting a simple prediction model within each partition (Loh, 2011). As a result, the partitioning can be represented graphically as a decision tree. A regression tree is similar to a classification tree, except that the Y variable takes ordered values and a regression model is fitted to each node to give the predicted values of Y. The CART algorithm is structured as a sequence of questions, the answers to which determine the next question if any should be. The result of these questions is a tree-like structure where the ends are terminal nodes at which point there are no more questions. The main elements of CART (and any decision tree algorithm) are:

- Rules for splitting data at a node based on the value of one variable;
- Stopping rules for deciding when a branch is terminal and can be split no more; and
- Finally, a prediction for the target variable in each terminal node.

The CART method is one of the most successful, widespread, and efficient data mining techniques for supervised classification learning, as it builds complex relations by a sequence of simple decisions (Demattè et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2015; Keskin et al., 2019; Laborci et al., 2016).

2.4.4.5 Bayesian network models (BN)

Bayesian networks (BN) are a type of probabilistic graphical model that uses Bayesian inference for probability computations. BN aims to model conditional dependence, and therefore causation, by representing conditional dependence by edges in a directed graph. Through these relationships, one can efficiently conduct inference on the random variables in the graph through the use of factors. BN is ideal for taking an event that occurred and predicting the likelihood that any one of several possible known causes was the contributing factor. It could represent the probabilistic relationships between the dependent and independent variables. Given independent variables, the network can be used to compute the probabilities of the presence of various dependent variables. A Bayesian network is a directed acyclic graph in which each edge corresponds to a conditional dependency, and each node corresponds to a unique random variable. Formally, if an edge (A, B) exists in the graph connecting random variables A and B, it means that $P(B|A)$ is a factor in the joint probability distribution, so we must know $P(B|A)$ for all values of B and A to conduct inference. It also satisfies the local Markov property, which states that a node is conditionally independent of its non-descendants given its parents. BN has been widely applied in DSM (Marchant et al., 2011; Mayr et al., 2008; Qi and Zhu, 2003; Zhang and Shi, 2019a).

2.4.4.6 Artificial neural networks (ANN)

The ANN is a prediction model with a three-layer structure: an input layer, an output layer, and a hidden layer. ANN is a non-parametric data mining tool that is analogous to neural networks of the human brain. The nodes of the neurons in the input layer and the output layer of the ANN model are determined by the number of input and output variables. The input layer contains independent variables (input layer nodes) for model predictions and the output layer consists of predicted dependent variables (output layer nodes). The input layer and output layer are connected by a hidden layer “black-box” (Ding et al., 2020). Two neighboring layers are connected with links and each node in one layer is linked with all nodes of the next layer. All links between input layers and hidden layers composed the input weight matrix and all links between hidden layers and output layers composed the output weight matrix. Weight (w) controls the propagation value (x) and the output value (o) from each node and how w and x from nodes are summed according to Equation 2.4:

$$o = f(-T + \sum w_i x_i) \tag{2.4}$$

where T is a specific threshold (bias) value for each node. f is a non - linear sigmoid function, which increases monotonically.

One important feature of ANNs is their adaptive nature through “learning” during the classification or prediction process. However, they are criticized as being “black-box” models and require higher computational power than most prediction models (Akpa, 2016a). ANN has been used in many soil mapping studies (Bagheri Bodaghabadi et al., 2015; Beucher et al., 2017; Hateffard et al., 2019; Mehrabi-Gohari et al., 2019; Rudiyanto et al., 2016; Song et al., 2016; Zeraatpisheh et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2009b)

2.4.4.7 Structural equation modeling (SEM)

Structural equation modeling is a multivariate statistical analysis technique that is used to analyze structural relationships. This technique is the combination of factor analysis and multiple regression analysis, and it is used to analyze the structural relationship between measured variables and latent constructs. This method is preferred by the researcher because it estimates the multiple and interrelated dependence in a single analysis. In this analysis, two types of variables are used endogenous variables and exogenous variables. Endogenous variables are equivalent to dependent variables and are equal to the independent variable. Although the main focus is on testing hypotheses, it can also be used for prediction. It includes both graphical and equational forms (Figure 2.9). The concept of SEM was introduced in DSM by Angelini et al. (2016). Its advantage is that it converts a conceptual soil-landscape model into a statistically explicit model and uses this for prediction and testing whether the hypotheses involved are supported by observed data. Moreover, SEM enhances the understanding of soil-landscape processes which is beneficial to a direct application on decision making for land management Angelini et al. (2016). Several studies reveal its relevance and potential for digital soil mapping (Angelini et al., 2020; Angelini and Heuvelink, 2018; Rossiter, 2018).

Figure 2.9: Steps of SEM application in DSM (Angelini et al., 2016)

2.5 APPLICATION OF DSM FOR SOIL ASSESSMENT

2.5.1 Soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS)

The national and international demand for data on soil organic carbon (SOC) distribution, existing stocks and potential changes is rapidly increasing as a result of the crucial role of SOC in soil fertility, food security, nutrient and water retention, biodiversity and ecosystem services (Paterson et al., 2015). Soils hold the largest organic carbon stock in the global terrestrial ecosystem (Lal, 2003) and therewith play a significant role in mitigating climate change (Guo et al., 2015). Soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration also contributes to maintaining and improving soil quality and soil fertility. Supporting decisions for sustainable SOC sequestration requires a sound understanding of the distribution of soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS), its importance, and the potential to define efficient management approaches to reduce SOCS losses and/or enhance its accumulation (Minasny et al., 2017). Mapping SOCS is thus of high priority for assessment and monitoring purposes, because estimation of carbon stocks is also necessary for the broader context of a carbon inventory for global circulation models and carbon economy studies (Antle et al., 2003; Scharlemann et al., 2014). Countrywide spatial assessment of SOCS has become the key issue over recent years, as it provides relevant information for understanding soil carbon variation (Mulder et al., 2016c).

Despite its importance in influencing many agronomical, environmental, political, and socio-economic issues, estimation of SOCS remains a big challenge, especially in countries with weak and sparse soil data infrastructure and poor data availability. As SOCS displays complex variation patterns from field to global scales, it often requires a high density of point data distribution to accurately infer spatial patterns (Goidts et al., 2009). The reliability of the assessment depends on the density and quality of data and the method used to upscale soil profile point data to comprehensive spatial estimates (Martin et al., 2011). According to Arrouays et al. (2017), new soil data collection is cost-prohibitive and not justifiable in many countries, without first having made optimal use of earlier collected data. Therefore, existing legacy soil data are being rescued and processed into usable harmonized datasets (Arrouays et al., 2017; Batjes et al., 2016; Leenaars et al., 2014) and made available as a reservoir of soil information, serving as input for soil mapping, including SOCS assessment in many countries (e.g., Adhikari et al., 2014; Akpa et al., 2016; Arrouays et al., 2001; Chen et al., 2018; Ramifehiarivo et al., 2017; Vaysse and Lagacherie, 2017).

Notwithstanding the above soil data rescue and harmonization initiatives, the SOCS of many African countries remains poorly known. The recent Global Soil Partnership (GSP) initiative on global carbon stock mapping using a bottom-up approach reported a national contribution of only 20% of African countries (FAO, 2018). Therefore, the information provided on carbon stocks of most African countries is mainly inferred from global estimates, with SoilGrids (Hengl et al., 2017a), and the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) (Wieder et al., 2014) as the most commonly cited sources worldwide (Deng et al., 2018). These global estimates provide both information on the total content and the spatial pattern of SOCS distribution for countries worldwide. However, there is a growing awareness of the accuracy limitations of such global models on estimating the national carbon stock (Tifafi et al., 2018), due to forcing a global model for local prediction and the public unavailability of soil data for numerous countries. In China, Liang et al. (2019) reported SoilGrids to overestimate and HWSD to underestimate the national SOCS. In France, where soil data are not publicly available, SoilGrids substantially overestimated the national SOCS, although the spatial distribution pattern was adequately captured (Mulder et al., 2016c). Such assessments remain scarce and the difference between national and global estimates in Sub-Sahara African countries remains poorly explored. The issue of accurately assessing national SOCS is now critical (Carvalho et al., 2019; Kempen et al., 2019; Vitharana et al., 2019). Our essential concern here is to make use of legacy soil data for the first national estimate of SOCS in Cameroon and to investigate the accuracy of the global estimates (SoilGrids and HWSD) on the national SOCS estimate in Cameroon. In this thesis, we appraised the spatial distribution of SOCS at five depth layers (0 – 15 cm, 15 – 30 cm, 30 – 100 cm, 0 – 30 cm and 0 – 100 cm) in Cameroon at 100 m spatial resolution, using a national harmonized legacy soil database. We assessed the prediction performances of random forest (RF) and generalized boosted regression (GBR), combined with two hybridization approaches of spatial interpolation of the residuals using ordinary kriging (OK) and inverse distance weighting (IDW). The estimates were compared to two global estimates derived from the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) and SoilGrids250m.

2.5.2 Particle size fraction (PSF)

Soil texture is an important soil property controlling most physical, chemical, and biological soil processes. It can influence soil thermal capacity, permeability, water holding capacity, and solute movement which are closely associated with applications of climate, ecological, hydrological modeling, smart agricultural management, and soil pollution control. Moreover,

soil texture influences the leaching or runoff of soil nutrients with an inefficient use of these nutrients which becomes potentially harmful to the environment (Petrovic, 2004). Soil texture also affects root penetration (Barbosa et al., 2018), and the effects of soil texture on land capability, vegetation distribution, and composition are well described globally (Pinheiro et al., 2018). Soil texture was also reported to affect soil organic carbon concentration and soil microbial activity (Deiss et al., 2017; Orobator et al., 2018) as well as the richness and the diversity of bacterial communities in the soils (Chau et al., 2011). Clay has been also shown to constrain woody biomass production in Australian drylands (Fensham et al., 2015), while sand content was the most effective soil property that affected soil bulk density (Aşkin and Özdemir, 2014). Additionally, within a time frame relevant to soil management, soil texture can be considered to be time invariable, making it an interesting property to investigate and map with legacy soil data (Van Meirvenne and Van Cleemput, 2010).

In view of the foregoing, mapping soil PSF has been gaining growing attention in diverse studies, scales, and extents. Soil texture has been characterized and mapped intensively in previous studies using diverse methods; Zhao et al. (2009) developed and trained Artificial neural network (ANN) to generate high-resolution soil texture maps using coarse resolution soil texture map and DEM derived hydrographic parameters in the north western New Brunswick, Canada. Pinheiro et al. (2018) evaluated regression trees (RT) and multiple linear regression to predict topsoil (0 – 5 cm and 5 – 15 cm) texture in a Brazilian watershed, and the outperformance of RT was noticed. Shabou et al. (2015) successfully predicted the clay content in the Kairouan plain in central Tunisia, using a time series of Landsat TM. Visible and near infra-red (Vis – NIR) spectra were also applied to predict the soil PSF (Virgawati et al., 2018). Many reports applied machine learning on soil for spatial prediction of soil texture (Ließ et al., 2012; Zhang and Shi, 2019) and compositional data analysis with PSF also showed improved predictive performances (Buchanan et al., 2012; Odeh et al., 2003a; Wang and Shi, 2017). National estimates of PSF for many countries have already been reported (Adhikari et al., 2013; Akpa et al., 2014; Bagarello et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2020; Padarian et al., 2017; Poggio and Gimona, 2017; Shangguan et al., 2012). In China, Shangguan et al. (2012a) first developed a practical 1-km-resolution dataset of soil PSF, which were recently refined and updated by Liu et al. (2020) following GlobalSoilMap specifications. In Cameroon, studies on the spatial distribution of PSF remain sparse and the spatial distribution of soil texture on a national scale remains poorly documented. In this study, we assessed and mapped the national distribution of the PSF and texture in Cameroon following the GlobalSoilMap specifications.

2.5.3 Soil pH

If there is one measurable property of the soil that can serve above all others as an indicator of the soil's quality, functioning, and environmental consequences it is its pH (Chen et al., 2018a). Soil pH is a measure of soil acidity/alkalinity, which defines the soil environment and affects nutrient availability. If soil pH deviates above or below an optimum range, crop performance may suffer. Soil pH is the most routinely measured soil property for assessing plant nutrient availability, as it provides the basic information on plant nutrient availability, aluminum and heavy metal equilibria and toxicity, organic matter decomposition, liming requirement, and microbial activity (Minasny et al., 2011). Soil pH was reported to affect bacterial diversity (Cho et al., 2016), and also to influence soil microbial activities (Whittinghill and Hobbie, 2012). Both acidification and salinization are causes of significant problems worldwide, and they are especially serious in developing countries.

Like other soil properties, soil pH varies spatially at various scales under the influences of both natural and anthropogenic factors (Liu et al., 2013). Information on the spatial variability of soil pH across the landscape is required for many ecological and environmental models, as it is the basic input to understand the decline of land productivity due to imbalanced fertilizer application (Sulaeman et al., 2012). Topsoil acidity (pH <5.5) now affects nearly 30% of the total ice-free land area of the world, and subsoil acidity affects as much as 75 % (Noble and Sumner, 2003). Modern agriculture with increasing application of nitrogen fertilizer has also accelerated the soil pH decline (Wang et al., 2018). A government would likely want to know where its soil is too acid or too alkaline and to monitor change there, especially if it needs to be controlled for agricultural production. High-resolution maps of soil's pH are needed for those purposes to ease the decision making (Chen et al., 2018a). However, creating soil pH maps at high resolution is costly since the process requires a significant number of samples to be collected and analyzed in the laboratory.

DSM methods are increasingly been apply for soil pH mapping at local, national, and global scales. Otieno et al. (2020) developed an approach based on geographically weighted regression-kriging (GWRK) to predict the continuous variation of topsoil (15 cm) pH in a tropical afro-montane landscape. Gonzalez et al. (2008) predicted soil pH in Honduras using readily available biophysical datasets and Gaussian Processes. A High-resolution national map of soil pH in China was made by (Chen et al., 2018a) using hybrid modeling of sparse legacy soil data and environmental covariates, and its implications for pollution was assessed.

Likewise, soil pH distribution on Chile and Denmark soils was estimated under GlobalSoilMap specifications with legacy soil data (Adhikari et al., 2006; Padarian et al., 2017). Soil pH distribution was also predicted at the continental scale in Europe (Gardi and Yigini, 2012; JRC, 2010) and Africa (Hengl et al., 2015) global scale (Hengl et al., 2017a, 2014). In Cameroon, Ngachie (1992) reported soil acidity to be among the main soil fertility constraint for agricultural production. However, the national distribution of soil pH in Cameroon remains poorly known. This study allowed for assessing the first baseline distribution of soil pH in Cameroon based on GlobalSoilMap specifications.

2.5.4 GlobalSoilMap project

GlobalSoilMap project was initiated to meet the needs for higher resolution soil datasets (Ballabio et al., 2016), with soil scientists being challenged to provide assessments of soil conditions from local to global scales. The objectives of the project have been consistently described by Arrouays et al. (2018, 2014). Indeed, the GlobalSoilMap project initiative aims at developing and transferring methods to improve the prediction accuracy of soil properties and their associated uncertainty, by using legacy soil data and ancillary spatial information. The project promotes maximum use of legacy soil data collected and reported over many decades of fieldwork, with state-of-the-art and emerging technologies for soil mapping and predicting soil properties at fine resolution (Arrouays et al., 2014). The objective of the GlobalSoilMap project is to provide a scientific framework to deliver fine grids soil attributes as a consistent, spatially explicit, and continuous database freely available for all. GlobalSoilMap and SoilGrids (section 2.5.5), presently aim at delivering the first generation of global, high-resolution soil property fine grids, the former relying on a bottom-up approach (from country to globe), while the latter uses a top-down approach (a global model that predicts properties for every country) (Arrouays et al., 2018).

The fine grids of soil attributes will be delivered at the high spatial resolution, thus applicable to both global and local applications. The specifications of the GlobalSoilMap products (Figure 2.10) have been discussed collegially by a scientific consortium and written into a detailed document based on peer review. The specified product includes predicted values of selected key soil properties at 6 standard depth intervals (0 – 5 cm, 5 – 15 cm, 15 – 30 cm, 30 – 60 cm, 60 – 100 cm and 100 – 200 cm), at a global scale on a 3 arc-second support grid (approximately 90 × 90 m) along with their uncertainties.

Figure 2.10: GlobalSoilMap project specifications (Vaysse, 2015)

The key primary soil properties include the clay, silt and sand contents, coarse fragments, pH in water, soil organic carbon (SOC) content, cation exchange capacity (CEC), soil depth to bedrock, and effective root zone depth (Arrouays et al., 2014). The minimal dataset may be supplemented by other soil attributes on an ad-hoc basis (e.g., P, N and S contents, electric conductivity, soil type, presence of diagnosis horizons, trace elements contents). Several national initiatives under the banner of the GlobalSoilMap project have already been successfully carried out.

Mulder et al. (2016a) developed an automatic procedure for mapping the primary soil properties (clay, silt, sand, coarse elements, pH, soil organic carbon (SOC), cation exchange capacity (CEC) and soil depth) for the first GlobalSoilMap (GSM) in France. Padarian et al. (2017) reported the first contribution of Chile to the GlobalSoilMap project using a CART regression method to link environmental covariates describing soil-forming factors with eight selected soil properties (organic carbon, field capacity, permanent wilting point, bulk density, pH, and clay, silt, sand particle size fraction). Particle size fraction distribution in Nigeria, Denmark, and

Scotland were predicted following GlobalSoilMap specifications (Adhikari et al., 2013; Akpa et al., 2014; Poggio and Gimona, 2017).

2.5.5 SoilGrids

SoilGrids is a system for global DSM making use of global soil profile information and covariate data to model the spatial distribution of soil properties across the globe. It is a collection of world's soil properties maps (pH (in water), texture fractions, coarse fragments, bulk density, total nitrogen, organic carbon concentration, and cation exchange capacity) for produced using machine learning at 250 m resolution (Hengl et al., 2017a). SoilGrids contains predictions and associated prediction uncertainties for soil properties, following the GlobalSoilMap specifications (Arrouays et al., 2014), and relying exclusively on open source tools. SoilGrids also provides global estimates for 'complex' soil properties such as organic carbon densities and organic carbon stocks. SoilGrids is based on a workflow that allows updates when new soil profile observations or new covariates become available. Predictions are made at six standard depths (0 – 5 cm, 5 – 15 cm, 15 – 30 cm, 30 – 60 cm, 60 – 100 cm and 100 –200 cm). SoilGrids uses global models that make use of all available input point data to map a property across the globe, which results in consistent predictions (no abrupt changes in predicted values at country boundaries, etc).

2.6 DIGITAL SOIL MAPPING PERSPECTIVE FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE IN CAMEROON

2.6.1 DSM and sustainable agriculture in Cameroon

The government of Cameroon is relying on agricultural intensification for the development of the country. However, the state of coverage of soil surveys remains very limited while Soil information is indispensable for the planning and implementation of successful agricultural projects at all levels (plot, farm, local, regional or national). Unsustainable intensification of agricultural practices is already resulting in increasing soil degradation. Major forms of degradation include the loss of organic matter, the release of greenhouse gases, the over-application of fertilizers, erosion, contamination, acidification, salinization, and loss of genetic diversity (Kopittke et al., 2019). A failure to identify and include the importance of soil within increasingly intensive agricultural systems will undoubtedly have serious consequences for humanity and represents a failure to consider intergenerational equity (Kopittke et al., 2019).

According to Van Ranst et al. (2010), only 1% of the Cameroonian soils has been mapped at a scale greater than 1: 25 000 (Large scale), about 5% at scales between 1: 50 000 and 1:100 000 (Medium scale) and 30% at a scale ranging from 100 000 to 1: 500 000 (Small scale). Depending on the type of agricultural project under consideration, soil maps at different scales are required. A small extended agricultural project (farm level) will require very high-resolution soil maps, while regional or national agricultural planning will integrate medium and low-resolution soil maps. Cameroonian agriculture is mostly family-based and is carried out on small pieces of land. To improve or to intensify these production systems, it is necessary to set up strategies to make soil data available for decision making at least at the farm level in the main production basins. However, there are no detailed general maps adapted for use at the farm level for agriculture in arable land in Cameroon. DSM seems to be the key strategy to solving this problem, as it can be used to create initial soil survey maps, refine or update existing soil surveys, generate specific soil interpretations, and assess risk at high resolution (Carré et al., 2007). Furthermore, DSM is becoming essential due to the reduction of costly and time-consuming field surveys, which are currently not affordable. Digital soil mapping for crop-land suitability analysis has been previously applied in Nigeria and Ghana (Akpa, 2016; Forkuo and Nketia, 2011).

2.6.2 DSM for sustainable intensification of cocoa production in Cameroon

Global cocoa (*Theobroma cocoa* Linn.) demand is projected to keep increasing up to 4.5 million tons by the end of 2020 whilst unstable production persists due to low productivity per unit area as well as climate variability. Between 1980 and 2017, global land area under cocoa cultivation increased from 4.7 to 11.7 million ha while yield levels during the same period barely increased, 350 to 443 kg ha⁻¹ (Abdulai et al., 2020). This emphasizes that global cocoa production increases have mainly relied on land expansion and therefore contributed to a significant loss in tropical rainforest (Gockowski et al., 2013). Observed and projected increase in spatiotemporal climate variability now contributes alongside the numerous challenges such as low soil fertility, increased pest and disease pressure, lack of quality planting material, and inadequate extension services faced by smallholder cocoa farmers (Abdulai et al., 2020). Narrowing the gap between attainable and actual yield through intensification can be an important means of reducing the pressure on the remaining forests and adapting to climate change (Schroth et al., 2016; Sonwa et al., 2019).

The government launched the recovery plan (2015 – 2020) for the cocoa sector in Cameroon (PRDFCC, 2014). The plan envisaged an increase in cocoa production, through the expansion and efficient exploitation of productivity reserves, to promote a sustainable cocoa economy. The government's objective by 2020 was to reach 600 000 tons of annual cocoa production (PRDFCC, 2014). To reach this level of production sustainably, it requires designing ways for intensification of cocoa production, to limit the negative impact of such engagement, and also to avoid unsustainable massive land expansion (Gockowski and Sonwa, 2011). Soil fertilization has been recognized as an essential operation to boost cocoa production, with the basic assumption that fertilizing cocoa would increase yields by about 30% of initial production. In the same perspective, the project intended to build a fertilizer factory, as well as the establishment of a laboratory for the analysis of agricultural inputs such as pesticides, and fertilizers. Among other things, this involved extending the area of cocoa plantations to nearly 400 000 ha by 2020 (PRDFCC, 2014). The distribution of about 2 800 tons of fertilizer was planned over the 6 years duration of the project.

In this review, we first discussed the conditions for suitable cocoa growth and then, illustrate the dynamics of land use in the shifting agricultural landscape where cocoa is cultivated to evaluate the sustainability of cocoa as compared to fallow chrono-sequences in the system. Afterward, we illustrated the facets related to the fertility and fertilization of cocoa as a preliminary step in the strategy for sustainable cocoa intensification in Cameroon.

2.6.2.1 Cocoa growing conditions

2.6.2.1.1 Climatic conditions

Many ecological factors are involved in the normal development of cocoa trees. The natural habitat of the cocoa tree is in the lower storey of the evergreen rainforest, and climatic factors, particularly temperature and rainfall, are important in encouraging optimum growth (Mbondji, 2010). Cocoa plants respond well to relatively high temperatures, with a maximum annual average of 30 – 32° C and a minimum average of 18 – 21° C. Variations in the yield of cocoa trees from year to year are affected more by rainfall than by any other climatic factor. Trees are very sensitive to soil water deficiency. Rainfall should be plentiful and well distributed throughout the year. An annual rainfall level of between 1500 mm and 2000 mm is generally preferred. Dry spells, where rainfall is less than 100 mm per month, should not exceed three months. A hot and humid atmosphere is essential for the optimum development of cocoa trees. In cocoa producing areas, relative humidity is generally high: often as much as 100% during

the day, falling to 70-80% during the night. The cocoa tree makes optimum use of any light available and traditionally has been grown under shade. Its natural environment is the Amazonian forest which provides natural shade trees. Shading is invaluable in a cocoa tree's early years. Schroth et al. (2016) analyzed cocoa's vulnerability to climate change in the African cocoa belt, based on climate projections for the 2050s. Areas with levels of climate suitability were identified in Cameroon (Figure 2.11).

Figure 2.11: Climate suitability of cocoa production areas of Cameroon modified from Schroth et al. (2016)

They also reported significant spatial differentiation of climate vulnerability, likely to induce future shifts in cocoa production, and recommended that adaptation strategies for cocoa need to focus at several levels. At the crop level, by selecting cocoa varieties and companion trees and crops that are tolerant to high maximum temperatures in addition to drought and diseases; at the farm level by increasing shade to protect the sensitive cocoa trees against increasing dry season temperatures and to diversify farmers' incomes as a buffer against the market and environmental risks; and at the national and regional policy level by implementing agricultural and forest policies that encourage the intensification of existing cocoa farms where climatic conditions permit and the siting of new cocoa plantings on previously deforested land, and that

create incentives for farmers to retain and plant native trees in their farms (Schroth et al., 2016). Thus, Cocoa production and productivity in the coming decades are likely to be governed by climatic factors.

2.6.2.1.2 Soil conditions

Basically, cocoa is grown in a wide variety of soil types. However, there are special physical and chemical soil conditions that allow the proper growth of the cocoa tree. Cocoa needs a soil containing coarse particles and with a reasonable quantity of nutrients, to a depth of 1.5 m to allow the development of a good root system. Below that level, it is desirable not to have impermeable material, so that excess water can drain away. Cocoa trees will withstand waterlogging for short periods, but excess water should not linger. The cocoa tree is sensitive to a lack of water, so the soil must have both water retention properties and good drainage. The chemical properties of the topsoil are most important, as the plant has a large number of roots for absorbing nutrients. Cocoa can grow in soils with a pH in the range of 5.0 - 7.5. It can, therefore, cope with both acid and alkaline soil, but excessive acidity (pH 4.0 and below) or alkalinity (pH 8.0 and above) must be avoided. Cocoa is tolerant of acid soils, provided the nutrient content is high enough. The soil should also have a high content of organic matter: 3.5% in the top 15 cm of soil. Soils for cocoa must have certain anionic and cationic balances (Mbondji, 2010). Exchangeable bases in the soil should amount to at least 35% of the total cation exchange capacity (CEC), otherwise, nutritional problems are likely and the optimum total nitrogen / total phosphorus ratio should be around 1.5.

2.6.2.2 Cocoa production basins in Cameroon

Cocoa production was introduced in the coastal zone of Cameroon since 1892 from South America (Ngo-Kelle, 2010). National cocoa production comes mainly from two production basins, and climate difference explains the distinction between the main production basins (Mbondji, 2010). According to Jagoret (2011) these two production areas are the South-West and the Center-South (Figure 2.12). The contrast between the main cocoa production basins was then described, illustrating the dynamism of the production basin in the South-West compared to that in the Center-South.

In fact, in the South-West basin (Figure 2.12), the cocoa plantations were reported to be relatively young and only 20% of the cocoa plantations over 30 years old (Losch et al., 1991). Besides, farmers manage their cocoa plantations with light permanent shade limited to the

presence of fruit trees. The technical routes would be intensive, the farmers carrying out the weeding and pruning work diligently and almost systematically using fungicide and insecticide products (Losch et al., 1991). Yields of marketable cocoa would be between 900 kg and 1200 kg ha⁻¹ in intensive production and 600 kg ha⁻¹ in a semi-intensive or traditional setting (Varlet and Berry, 1997).

Figure 2.12: Cocoa production (green area) basins in Cameroon (Jagoret, 2011)

In the Center-South basin (Figure 2.12), the cocoa plots are older (Champaud, 1966), with almost 40% of the cocoa plantations having been planted before 1950, except for the Mban and Kim department where the cocoa plantations are more recent (Varlet and Berry, 1997). As far as plot management is concerned, cocoa plantations in the Center-South production basin are generally carried out under heavy shade made up of forest and fruit trees.

Figure 2.13: Cocoa production in Cameroon (MINADER, 2015)

Overall, management is extensive, characterized by reduced weed control, an absence of size, and adjustment of shade (Losch et al., 1991). The use of agricultural inputs is low and the yields of market cocoa in the Center-South would, therefore, be lower than in the South-West, ranging

between 100 and 250 kg ha⁻¹ in Nyong and So'o, and 250 and 500 kg ha⁻¹ in Lékié and Mbam and Kim (Varlet and Berry, 1997) divisions.

Thus, cocoa production varies with environmental management conditions. In the same country, it varies from a region to another, and according to the inherent intensity of cultivation techniques. Sonwa (2004) noticed that, in South Cameroon, the production is between 258 and 445 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Hietet (2005) reported that in the Center-South production basin, the Lékié division is the production site with the highest cocoa yield (575 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹), followed by Mefou Afamba (342 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) and Mvila divisions (337 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). However, in Lékié, cocoa management is intensive and production reaches 600 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. On the contrary, in South Cameroon where the management of the cocoa orchard is extensive, cocoa production is about 270 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Sonwa et al., 2002). Figure 2.13 shows the variation in cocoa production in Cameroon. This results in significant spatial variability in cocoa yields. This study should explore whether soil-related factors can justify this disparity.

2.6.2.3 Land use dynamics in the cocoa production area

In the forest zone of Cameroon, Yemefack (2005) developed a conceptual framework of land-use dynamics at different phases of development (Figure 2.14). Agricultural activities start by clearing a portion of forest land for forest crop field (FCF). After 1–2 years, this FCF is transformed into food crop field for two more years, and then followed either by perennial plantation or fallow of various durations. However, forests conversions directly to perennial plantations were sometimes observed as unusual transitions in the land-use management process.

The fallow system starts with the invasion by an exotic weed called *Chromolaena odorata* King & Robinson and a new vegetation dynamic is set in place following various stages during the fallow period. A distinct evolution of vegetation types can be observed between 2 and 50 years (Nounamo and Yemefack, 2001) Under the *Chromolaena odorata*-dominated vegetation, pioneer species germinate and grow rapidly, overtopping the shade-intolerant *Chromolaena* after 8–10 years. Seedlings of other forest species appear and grow under the pioneer species. Forest tree species will supersede pioneer species over ~20 years, after which vegetation evolves toward a secondary forest. (Zapfack et al., 2002) reported that biodiversity was only slightly decreased in the young fallow versus old-growth (Shannon index values of 6.64 and 7.04, respectively).

Figure 2.14: Land use transition within the SALMS (Yemefack, 2005)

For the fallow vegetation to recover and return to that resembling the original forest, with C stocks of about 300 Mg C ha⁻¹ (Ngo et al., 2013; Njomgang et al., 2011), will require at least a century (Kearsley et al., 2013; Kotto-Same et al., 1997). The establishment of the CAF can be considered as the beginning of a controlled fallow (Nounamo and Yemefack, 2001) A CAF system is commonly established within a thinned secondary forest canopy, adding to a multi-story agroforestry system (Sonwa et al., 2007). Cocoa trees make up the lower tree level under which dense understory vegetation develops. As a mixture of forest, fruit, and timber tree species, along with semi-cultivated woody and other cultivated plants, this multi-story system has a high level of plant biodiversity and, with it, potentially high conservation value (Bisseleua, 2007). (Ewane, 2012) reported plant diversity to slightly increase from young to old CAF, with Shannon index values of 4.47 and 4.8, respectively. To maintain the CAF, there is no external fertilizer input into this system but understory vegetation is cut at least once a year and left in place as mulch, adding organic matter and nutrients back into soil (Yemefack, 2005).

Duguma et al. (2001) reported that CAF systems could remain productive and environmentally sustainable for up to 50 years, at a level comparable to long-term fallow. Within the context of climate change mitigation, the question remains whether these two systems (CAF and fallows) are comparable in their capability to sequester new SOC. We have hypothesized that if an empirical model in the form of a continuous function of time can be fitted to SOC measurements, it can be used to predict C stock and accretion values at any point in time. We thus assessed the question of long-term comparative sustainability between the cocoa and fallow systems, as a prerequisite for a sustainable strategy for cocoa production in Cameroon. As such, it would also provide the quantitative information needed for MRV (Monitoring Reporting and Verification) within the mechanism of reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from deforestation and forest degradation (REDD+) to which the Cameroon Government is strongly committed

2.6.2.4 Soil fertility and cocoa production

Soil fertility management is the backbone of any successful agricultural production system. Proper management of soil fertility assumes knowledge of soils, their nutrient availability, and most importantly the nutritional demands of the crop (Uribe-leitz and Ruf, 2019). Soil capability refers to the presence or absence of soil constraints relevant to the production of crops and maybe posed simply as ‘whether a specific soil allows producing a specific crop’ (Singh et al., 2019). Soil condition refers to the necessary state of soil that would sustainably enable crop production, in other words, the question comes down to asking ‘will this soil continue to support crop production into the future? Given the variability in soil properties, managing soils condition often requires specific approaches, as soils might have intrinsic nutrient deficiencies.

2.6.2.4.1 Cocoa production under poor soil management conditions

In the cocoa literature, there has been a longstanding interest in understanding the impact of soil nutrients on cocoa growth and productivity (Kongor et al., 2016). Cocoa production has been mostly relying on the initial soil conditions without the use of fertilizer. Over time, continuous export of nutrients without replacement accordingly diminishes the condition of soil and yield in the future, highlighting the need for an integrative approach to developing management options for securing soil under cocoa (Singh et al., 2019). As soil nutrient content in many cocoa-growing regions is naturally low, an obvious way to increase yields is to address the nutritional needs of cocoa alongside other management impetus, such as pest and disease

control, pruning, weed control, etc. Compared to other tropical perennial crops, cocoa has higher nutrient requirements (Asare et al., 2017). Cocoa plants grow best on high nutrient content coarse soil, allowing for good root development, water retention, and drainage. Cocoa is a tap-rooted plant and requires deep well-drained soils, free from iron concretions (Opeke, 2005). Cacao plant requires an adequate supply of N, P, K, Ca, and Mg for optimal growth, and deficiency of these nutrients negatively affect yields (Njukeng and Baligar, 2016). For optimal growth, the soil should have among others high levels of CEC, organic matter, available P, Ca, Mg, K, and balanced proportions of particle size fractions in the top 15 cm (Wessel, 1971).

The inherent low soil fertility under cocoa plantations is among the major causes for low cocoa yields, as cocoa is cultivated in the low fertility soils of the humid tropics (Van Villet et al., 2015). Poor soil fertility is also because farmers fail to replenish the soil with fertilizers after extracting nutrients through harvests (Danso-Abbeam and Baiyegunhi, 2019; Hartemink, 2005; Kongor et al., 2018). Fertilizers and agrochemical inputs are usually not applied or used in insufficient quantities (Baah et al., 2011). Most of the cocoa farms have never been fertilized and possibilities of nutrition-related limitations to productivity are common. The gap between the potential yield and actual yield of cocoa in Cameroon can be close by addressing and reducing factors related to the soil condition. An obvious way to increase yields is to address the nutritional needs of cocoa through the understanding of initial soil conditions to anticipate and implement appropriate soil management measures (Van Villet et al., 2015).

2.6.2.4.2 Shade trees and cocoa soil fertility

Options for improving soil fertility management in cocoa production systems sometimes suggest the inclusion of shade trees. However, the role of shade trees in regulating soil fertility remains controversial. Asare et al. (2017) reported higher yields on no-shaded cocoa plots than on shaded ones, highlighting that shade trees might have no benefits for soil fertility in cocoa agroforests. Likewise, no evidence for positive effects of agroforests via improved soil fertility or carbon sequestration with increasing shade-tree cover at the plot scale was observed in the Ashanti Region of Ghana (Blaser et al., 2017). Cocoa growth was lower under individual shade trees and cocoa yields also decreased with increasing shade-tree cover. Conversely, shade trees showed a net positive effect on soil fertility in cocoa agroforests, with a 6% increase in soil carbon, a 4% in soil nitrogen and a 24% increase in mean weight diameter (used as an indicator for median soil aggregate size), under shade tree canopies compared to open areas (Wartenberg et al., 2019). Also, shade trees in agroforestry were reported to enhance soil fertility, functional

biodiversity, carbon sequestration, drought resistance as well as weed and biological pest control (Tschardt et al., 2011). Thus there is likely potential for soil improvements under shade trees with measurable positive effects on soil fertility in perennial cocoa systems (Franzen and Mulder, 2007).

2.6.2.4.3 Fertilizer trials and recommendation for cocoa

Several trials have shown that cocoa productivity can more than doubled when fertilizers are applied. However, large variability in yields and fertilizer response are often reported, and in some cases, fertilizers showed little effect (Van Villet et al., 2015). In many African countries, there are wide cocoa fertilizer recommendations that do not pay attention to the characteristics of soils where cocoa is being produced or the age of the plantation, which is not an optimal solution in the long term (Snoeck et al., 2016). Soil management recommendation for cocoa fertilization exists as a few generic formulas. However, there is rarely, if ever, one-size-fits-all solution, and as with many developing countries, the capacity of cocoa producers in Cameroon to implement interventions is heavily constrained by the prevailing social, economic and environmental context (Singh et al., 2019). Furthermore, the mechanism for cocoa certification requires rigorous controls of fertility and fertilization, which are difficult to monitor without prior knowledge of the soil status and nutrients dynamics (Uribe-leitz and Ruf, 2019). Knowledge required to come to suitable recommendations under different conditions is limited and due to infrastructure limitations and scarce soil information availability in the cocoa-growing areas, it can be assumed that few producers can satisfactorily comply with these requirements and get their cocoa certified.

In Ivory Coast, research has validated and recommended a simplified fertilizer formula called "Cocoa fertilizer" $0\text{ N} - 23\text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 - 19\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 10\text{ CaO} + 5\text{MgO}$ which proved not to be adapted to the context of soil fertility deterioration (Koko, 2014). A new fertilizer, named Teractiv cocoa with the formula $0\text{ N} - 15\text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 - 14\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 28\text{ CaO} + 5.5\text{ S} + 2.5\text{ MgO} + 0.9\text{ Zn} + 0.24\text{ B}_2\text{O}_3$ was developed, with innovations likely to improved mineral nutrition and productivity of cocoa in Ivory Coast (Koko, 2014). In Ghana, need for supplementary plant nutrients has led to current introduction of recommended cocoa fertilizers like Asaase Wura ($0\text{ N} - 22\text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 - 18\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 9\text{CaO} + 7\text{S} + 6\text{ MgO}$), Cocofeed (N:P:K 0:30:20), Potassium Rich Sidalco Liquid fertilizers ($6\text{ N} - 0\text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 - 20\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 1\text{ MgO} + \text{trace elements}$) and Balanced Sidalco Liquid fertilizer (N:P:K N 10 – 10 $\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 - 10\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 1\text{MgO} + \text{trace elements}$) for farmers (Afrifa et al., 2009). In Cameroon, cocoa is fertilized by adding a special cocoa fertilizer (NPK: $6\text{ N} - 15$

$P_2O_5 - 28 K_2O + 6 CaO + 3 MgO$). While these significant efforts have been made to intensify cocoa production in several countries, these fertilization recommendations still do not integrate the soil variability observed in the field. Given the wide variability in soils and other conditions which affect nutrient requirements across the cocoa production areas, fertilizer recommendations need to be tailored to local conditions. However, as the methods to establish them remain limited, current fertilizer recommendations continue to be highly generalized.

2.6.2.4.4 Cocoa production and deforestation

In the humid tropics, the expansion of agriculture is the leading driver of deforestation (Norris et al., 2010). Cocoa is the second commodity in terms of area expansion and has shown low growth in crop yields as evidence of a continuing reliance on extensive “land consuming” rather than a “land saving” scheme (Gockowski and Sonwa, 2011). Analysing land-use change scenarios, Gockowski and Sonwa (2011) estimated that over 21 000 km² of deforestation and forest degradation could have been avoided if intensified cocoa production technology was implemented. They further suggested a high potential for significantly increasing cocoa yields through an increasing application of fertilizer technologies. Intensification of cocoa production is an important objective to increase productivity and farmer incomes (Gockowski and Sonwa, 2011). The threat is that increasing cocoa production to meet the high demand could cause a wave of deforestation unless it is accompanied by effective agricultural policies emphasizing the intensification of existing cocoa farms and channelling future cocoa expansion on already deforested land (Schroth et al., 2016).

2.6.2.5 Soil suitability analysis for cocoa production

Many studies have focused on soil assessments for cocoa production in Nigeria. Ajiboye et al. (2015) surveyed soils of the major cocoa growing district in Cross River State, using a flexible grid method to assess their suitability for cocoa production. Apart from limitations related to climatic factors (rainfall and relative humidity), low fertility (N, P, K, Ca, Mg) resulting from nutrient leaching, low pH, and cation exchange capacity were noticed, and all soils were currently not suitable (N1) for cocoa production. Selected soils of South-eastern showed that all pedons evaluated were currently not suitable for cocoa cultivation with soil organic matter, available phosphorus, and texture as the major’s constraints limiting cocoa production (Ahukaemere, 2018). Soil constraints affecting the cocoa production in Osun State, were textures, low organic matter, nitrogen, phosphorus, and cation exchange capacity (CEC)

(Ayorinde et al., 2015). Nitrogen and phosphorus appear to be the most critical soil nutrients after soil fertility evaluation for cocoa production in South-eastern Adamawa State (Ibiremo et al., 2011). Fasina et al. (2007) identified poor soil fertility as major limitations for cocoa production in Ekiti State South-Western Nigeria. Ogunlade et al. (2012) showed that increasing soil quality by 1% will lead to an increase in yield of 16 kg ha⁻¹ in the cocoa-growing regions of Nigeria. In Ghana, assessing the topsoil (0 – 30 cm) fertility and quality for improved cocoa production, Kongor et al. (2018) reported low soil quality in most farms, with pH, CEC, and available phosphorus being the major's soil constraints. Farmers were encouraged in the direction of efficient application of fertilizer, rather than focusing on excessive land expansion was recommended to shortcut these soil constraints and boost their production (Kongor et al., 2018). Snoeck et al. (2007) recommended to first restore the ratios between the topsoil (0 – 20 cm) exchangeable bases (K, Ca and Mg) before being able to improve the cocoa yields in Ghana while assessing fertilizer requirements for the various soils.

CHAPTER THREE: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

3.1.1 Location

Cameroon is located between longitude $8^{\circ}30'$ – $16^{\circ}15'$ E and latitude $1^{\circ}30'$ – $13^{\circ}N$ in central Africa, and extends from the Gulf of Guinea in the Atlantic Ocean to Lake Chad, covering an area of approximately 475 000 km². It is bordered by Nigeria to the west and north; Chad to the northeast; the Central African Republic to the east; and Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, and the Republic of Congo to the south. Cameroon's coastline lies on the Bight of Biafra, part of the Gulf of Guinea and the Atlantic Ocean. The country has the approximate shape of a triangle and is often referred to as "Africa in miniature" for its geological and cultural diversity (Tchawa, 2012).

3.1.2 Geomorphology

The geomorphology of the country has been partially described by (Segalen, 1967). The generalization of the type of reliefs on these zones seems to come from unique and general causes which can be sought among the agents who preside over their formation and, or destruction. The detailed model seems to differ considerably from one region to another and is to be linked to the phenomena currently acting on the upper part of the Earth's crust. Seven major units are to be considered throughout the country.

3.1.2.1 Coastal surface

This surface extends from the ocean inward for about 150 km eastward and 200 km northward. The altitude rises regularly from sea level, up to around 350 m. The difference in altitude between this surface and the interior surface is quite significant around Matomb (100 to 150 m), and more marked between Kribi and Lolodorf. Towards the north, the immediately upper surface is not visible, hidden by the products of volcanic accumulation (hills).

3.1.2.2 Interior surface

This surface covers the South and South-East of the country, and ends abruptly to the West with a steep escarpment on the coastal surface. Towards the north, it ends at the foothills of the Adamawa,

from which it is separated by a slight drop in the east, but with several hundred meters in height on the west side. The average altitude of the surface is around 700 m, reaching 800 m to the north and decreases slightly in the center, where it is only 600 m, then increases up to 750 m (around Yaoundé) and decreases again to the south, as if the surface had been affected by a vast movement of ripples.

3.1.2.3 Centre and western surfaces

The center of Cameroon is located at altitudes even higher than the southern part of the country, and corresponds to the so-called "Adamaoua plateau". Two levels of altitude are distinguishable, one between 800 - 1100 m, and the other varying between 1000 and 1300 m, which however are not always very easy to differentiate. The first corresponds to the southern and northern parts of the Adamaoua plateau and extends to Meiganga, Betare-Oya, Yoko, Ngaoundéré, Banyo, and the Bamoun plateau. The second level includes the rest of the Adamaoua and the Bamileké plateau.

3.1.2.4 Benue surfaces

This surface corresponds to the Cameroonian part of the Benue watershed, coming down from the plateau of Adamaoua and heads first to the north before turning to the west rather abruptly. It extends from the foot of the cliff of Adamaoua in the South to the foot of the Mandara Mountains in the north. To the east, it connects to the Chadian basin to the east of a Mokolo-KaéIé line; to the west, it opens widely onto Nigeria. The altitude at the foot of the Adamawa escarpment is approximately 5 to 600 m; in Garoua, it is 180 m near the river and goes up 400 m near the Mandara massif.

3.1.2.5 Kapsiki surface

This surface increases on the Mandara massif brutally whether you come from the South, East, or from the North. A drop of 4 to 500 meters separates the peripheral plains, strewn with inselbergs, from an erosion surface whose altitude is between 800 and 1000 m. The edges are deeply cut by rivers coming from the plateau, but on this one, the difference in level between the bottoms of the very widely open thalwegs and the interfluves is very weak.

3.1.2.6 Volcanic accumulation surface

This surface varies according to the nature of the rocks or the form of volcanism. Accumulation plays an important role in western Cameroon. Considerable hills have formed, reaching several thousand meters high and varying in age from Cretaceous to the present day. The southernmost

mountain is Mount Cameroon (4,007 m) which is still active and periodically spreads lava flows on its flanks, some of which flow reaching the sea.

3.1.2.7 Alluvium surface

In Cameroon, only the northern end of the country is part of this surface and the boundary passes to the North and East of the Mandara massif and oblique to the southeast, towards Kaele. The Chad basin, without an outlet to the sea, constitutes an area where the deposit of alluvial materials is very old.

3.1.3 Hydrology

Cameroon's hydrological and rainfall regimes are quite similar, as large amounts of water, seasonal variability, and even interannual irregularity are strictly correlated. There is a relationship between annual stream flows, precipitation, catchment area, and morphology. According to (Molua and Lambi, 2006), Cameroon has vast water resources, in the form of groundwater and stream or surface water. In the well-watered southern region, which has metamorphic and igneous rocks, the resources are mostly surface water, while in the semi-arid less watered northern lowlands they are mostly groundwater, owing to the permeability of the sedimentary rocks. Streams do exist here but their flow is impermanent given the prolonged dry season period of this region, especially in the Logone-Shari plain which is part of the Chad basin (Molua and Lambi, 2006). The five major drainage basins in Cameroon are Chad, Niger, Atlantic, Congo, and Cross basins. The country's principal watershed in the Western highlands and the Adamawa plateau. North of the highlands, the rivers flow north into Lake Chad and northwest into the Niger basin. South of the highlands they flow west into the Cross basin, south-west into the Atlantic basin and south-east into the Congo basin (Tchoungui et al., 1995). Cameroon has a dense network of perennial rivers. The main rivers in the South of the country are the Ntem, Nyong, Sanaga, and Wouri, which flow southwestward or westward into the Gulf of Guinea. The Dja and Kadéï drain southeastward into the Congo River. In the north, the Benue River flows North and West into the Niger. The Logone flows northward into the Lake Chad basin, which Cameroon shares with three neighboring countries. Cameroon also has many smaller lakes throughout the country (Molua and Lambi, 2006).

3.1.4 Climate

Cameroon falls within the intertropical zone, with climate varying greatly from equatorial humid along the coastal area through the tropical hot semi-arid northern plains, and the arid Sahelian area

in the far North (Guenang et al., 2016). The tropical area is characterized by high temperatures and low rainfall, either Sudanian or Sahelian, marked by very irregular rains. The climate varies across the country, controlled by topography, with elevation increasing from the coast to the uplands. In general, rainfall decreases towards the north and interior of the country. Most of the littoral plain has over 4 000 mm of precipitation annually and at Debundsha, at the foot of Mt Cameroon, it regularly exceeds 10 000 mm. (Tchoungui et al., 1995). Thus, upland areas have a mild climate with high rainfall. The coast is hot and very wet, with only a short dry season. The plateau areas show distinct wet and dry seasons, with lower rainfall than the coastal region. The northern lowland region is relatively arid, with low rainfall and high temperatures. The climate is tropical, semi-arid in the north, and humid and rainy in the rest of the country. Almost everywhere, there is a dry season in winter and a rainy season in summer due to the African monsoon, which is shorter in the north and longer in the south, while along the coast, even in winter there can be some showers. The northernmost part of the country, on the shores of Lake Chad, is the driest area, where less than 600 millimeters of rain falls per year, while the wettest is the coast, where rainfall exceeds 3 000 mm per year. Yearly average temperatures are between 20°C to 32°C, generally increasing from the South towards the North.

3.1.5 Vegetation

Two major vegetation zone can be distinguished in Cameroon; The dense equatorial forest and the tropical grasslands (Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005a). The dense tropical forest covers the coastal lowlands and the southern part of the Southern Plateau and can be divided into three main types: i) Mangroves forest occupy the swampy coastal areas, ii) Rain forest lies inland adjacent to the mangrove forest, in the altitude between 200 m and 800 m, and cover a very large part of the Southern plateau to the east of the country, iii) Mountain forest found above 300 m to 1800 m, where tree size is reduced and few species exceed 30m. this vegetation is found at high altitudes on the slopes of mountainous massifs, where islands of dense forest can be found.

The transition from rain forest in the South to grassland in the North is gradual, and the area covered by the grassland corresponds to that of the tropical climate. Three main types of savanna are distinguished (Neba, 1999).

3.1.5.1 Guinea savanna

Laying immediately north of the rain forest and consisted of a mixture of high savanna and trees. Moving northward, the trees give way to grass.

3.1.5.2 Sudan savanna

Areas covering this type of vegetation can further be divided into two sub-groups; i) mountain savanna, which covers the western highlands and the southern slope of the Adamaoua plateau; ii) open savannas and forest, which is observed on the Adamaoua escarpment towards Garoua.

3.1.5.3 Sahel savanna

This zone can be divided into two main sub-areas: i) Open forest and spiny steppes, lying north a line passing through Mokolo and Guider and gradually enters into a zone whose vegetation is typical of the Sahelian zone; ii) The prairies found in the Chad Basin, subjected to periodic inundation grassland formation abound, with rare large tracks of forested lands.

3.1.6 Agroecological zones

Cameroon is divided into 5 agroecological zones (Figure 3.1).

3.1.6.1 Soudano-Sahelian (Zone I)

The rainfall is monomodal and increases from north to south (400 to 1200 mm). Unlike precipitation, temperatures decrease from north to south with estimated annual averages reaching 28°C around Garoua. The vegetation is mainly made of thorny steppes, periodically flooded meadows called « yaérées ».

3.1.6.2 High Guinea Savanna (Zone II)

With a total area of about 138 000 km², it is largely made up of a vast plateau of altitudes between 900 and 1 500 m, with peaks reaching 1 800 m. The climate is tropical Sudanian with two seasons per year. The average annual rainfall is around 1500 mm. Temperatures are moderate, with monthly averages of the order of 20 to 26°C.

Figure 3.1: Agro-ecological zones of Cameroon (IRAD, 2008)

3.1.6.3 Western Highland (Zone III)

The climate is equatorial in altitude characterized by two seasons of unequal durations. The altitude lowers the average temperatures (19°C on an annual average), the rains are abundant and vary between 1500 - 2000 mm per year. This is the domain of savannas and gallery forests.

3.1.6.4 Humid Forest with Monomodal Rainfall (Zone IV)

It is a low altitude area contrasted by Mount Cameroon which rises to 4095 m. The climate is equatorial monsoon, very humid, hot, and rainy. The rainfall regime is monomodal. The rains are abundant and distributed throughout the year. They vary on average between 2 500 to 4 000 mm, except the locality of Debundscha (10 000 mm). Temperatures are high throughout the year and range between 22 and 29°C.

3.1.6.5 Humid Forest with Bimodal Rainfall (Zone V)

This zone covers almost the entire South Cameroon plateau. The altitude varies between 500 and 1000 m, over a total area of 22.5 million hectares. The climate is equatorial Guinean characterized by high temperatures with annual averages of 25°C and rainfall of 1 500 – 2 000 mm per year.

3.2 METHODS OF STUDY

The method of study involved soil data gathering; i) legacy soil data, which were collected from existing soil literature and primary field data which were collected in the chrono-sequences of cocoa and fallow systems, and ii) environmental covariate gathering.

3.2.1 Soil data gathering

3.2.1.1 Legacy soil data rescue and renewal

Rossiter (2008) categorized three main steps leading to the rejuvenation of historical soil data. These steps were further differentiated and apply by Odeh et al. (2012) in Nigeria and Rasaei et al. (2020) in Iran;

3.2.1.1.1 Data archaeology

Which involves efforts to locate and catalogue historical soil records, including soil reports and maps. Here, attempts are made to find all possible legacy soil resources at hand in the desired study area.

3.2.1.1.2 Data rescue

Involving scanning of the historical records and storing them in an appropriate, easily-accessible media such as a database. The discovered legacy soil surveys are grouped based on some of their general characteristics such as researcher, year, scale, and categorical detail. The studies are afterward digitized, at least by scanning as images and preferably converted to text if possible, to save them from any danger of destruction or loss.

3.2.1.1.3 Data renewal or data resurrection

In this step, the studies are put into a new structure, which entails the transformation of the rescued data (Digital soil mapping process) into usable digital (GIS) formats.

However, the application of these steps is not always trivial. Identifying data sources is the first challenge, and several problems have been identified during the combination and harmonization of soil data from various resources (Leenaars et al., 2014; Odeh et al., 2012; Rasaei et al., 2020; Rossiter, 2008; Samuel-Rosa et al., 2020). The most common problems in combining and harmonizing the data once acquired are various sampling designs (sample distribution, density, uneven coverage, completeness, localization), different sampling depths (fixed depths vs. horizons vs. topsoil only), different laboratory methods, data availability, missing uncertainty.

3.2.1.1.4 Data sources

Identifying and locating the sources of legacy data is the most challenging in the process leading to data rescue and renewal (Rossiter, 2008). Likewise, in Nigeria, Odeh et al. (2012) identified potential soil data holders. On that sound base, we were able to identify some probable sources for Cameroon; *i*) Development Aid Organizations such as Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Development Research Institute (IRD); *ii*) Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER), Ministry of Forests and Wildlife (MINFOF) and affiliated Institutions; *iii*) Government-funded Research Institutions, such as Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD); *iv*) Universities (University of Dschang, University of Yaoundé I, University of Buea, University of Ngaoundéré, etc. ...); *v*) International research institutions such as the International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC), International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), World Centre Agroforestry (ICRAF) etc.; *vi*) retired soil scientists and resource persons; *vii*) Public and private agricultural companies such as Cameroon Development Corporation (CDC), Hight-Penja company (PHP), Vegetable production company (PROLEG) etc. ; *viii*) Internet.

3.2.1.1.5 Profiles localization

Many soil surveys in which legacy soil profiles were described and sampled were carried out before the era of Global Positioning Systems (GPS). In most cases, the spatial location of the soil profiles was not directly mentioned in the reports and could be estimated from the descriptions of the physical environment (Samuel-Rosa et al., 2020). In our case, three situations were expected:

3.2.1.1.5.1 Profiles or samples with GPS coordinates

These were ideal situations. The coordinates were just transformed when necessary in decimal degrees and recorded into the database.

3.2.1.1.5.2 Profiles or samples with maps of sampling locations

In these situations, the maps were scanned and georeferenced in a GIS environment and the coordinates belonging for each sampling point were recovered. It was not always an easy task to do the georeferencing, as some maps did not have geographical references (Figure 3.2). It was, therefore, necessary to observe the environment in the area with satellite images such as GoogleEarth to identify some tie-points or reference points (rivers, roads, etc.) to achieve georeferencing.

3.2.1.1.5.3 Profile or samples without GPS coordinates and maps of sampling locations

These were the worst situations expected. Fortunately, in the methodologies for describing soil profiles or collecting soil samples, the description of the physical environment surrounding the sampling location has remained consistently highly recommended in pedological textbooks and applied during field campaigns. Although the accuracy of the description varied from one study to another depending on the surveyor's perception of the environment, in most cases spatial coordinates with varying levels of precision could be assigned to several profiles. Several resources combined were used to achieve the localization of the soil profile under these conditions. Satellite images such as GoogleEarth were used to visualize the environment. Maps illustrating the villages of Cameroon was used to identify the villages and localities studied. Hydrographic network maps were used to identify the rivers to better locate the profiles according to the authors' descriptions. Terrain attribute maps were used to assess the morphology of the landscape described. Finally, the assignment of a coordinate to a specific sampling point was always the result of a multi-criteria analysis taking into account most of the details from the reports.

Figure 3.2: Map of a study area with sampling points indicated by numbers (Sieffermann, 1964)

3.2.1.1.6 Laboratory results harmonization

Description of soil condition, status, and change requires the availability of harmonized and comparable soil data relating to the site and general area of the soil profile. The value of the data recorded for each parameter in a given soil profile might vary significantly depending on the methods, because soil properties may have been determined using a range of analytical procedures, or has even changed in one survey during the time (Borůvka et al., 2018). To make these data comparable and fit for use, there is a need for harmonization (Leenaars et al., 2014). In several regions of the world, research is devoted to setting up equations to convert the results from one analytical method to another, for a range of soil properties. However, there is still generally no universal equation for converting soil properties values from one method to another in all situations. Several conversion methods are suggested in the context of studies on a global scale for specific soil properties (GlobalSoilMap, 2015).

3.2.1.1.6.1 Soil organic carbon (SOC)

Many sets of propositions for converting SOC data from Walkley and Black method (Walkley and Black, 1934) to lost on ignition or dry combustion have been developed (Adolfo Campos, 2010; Ali and Jenkins, 1995; De Vos et al., 2005; Enang et al., 2018; GlobalSoilMap, 2015; Kamara et al.,

2007; Wang et al., 2013). Each method was developed under specific conditions and soil requirements. Depending on situations, the SOC data was harmonized using the equation that best meets the conditions presented in the corresponding reports, with the priority to the local equation (Enang et al., 2018) when applicable.

3.2.1.1.6.2 Soil particle size fraction (Sand, Silt, Clay)

Differences in values reported for soil particle size fractions can arise because of differences in the method of analysis (e.g. hydrometer, pipette, laser diffraction) or differences in classification of particle size fractions. However, the literature on harmonization of soil texture data deals mainly with harmonizing differences in reported particle size fractions (Minasny and McBratney, 2001; Rousseva, 2010; Shangguan et al., 2014). The transformations were performed using the R package “*soiltexture*” from Moeys (2014).

3.2.1.1.6.3 Soil pH (H₂O, KCl, and CaCl₂)

The standard reference method for reporting pH for the *GlobalSoilMap* project is ISO 10390:2005 (GlobalSoilMap, 2015). This standard specifies an instrumental method for the routine determination of pH using a glass electrode in a 1:5 (volume fraction) suspension of soil in water (pH in H₂O), in 1 mol L⁻¹ potassium chloride solution (pH in KCl) or 0.01 mol L⁻¹ calcium chloride solution (pH in CaCl₂). Nevertheless, methods and practices of pH measurement are highly variable from one laboratory to another. Methods are employed, depending on the needs and objectives of the study. For example, the most common method for analyzing pH in North America is a 1:1 soil/water suspension (Miller and Kissel, 2010). The standard field pH measurement is performed with a 1:1 soil/water mixture so that comparisons of pH readings are done on an equivalent basis, and more dilute samples such as 1:5 soil/water ratio generally have a higher pH value, while less dilute samples generally have lower pH values (Kome et al., 2018b). In most laboratories of soil analysis in Cameroon, Kome et al. (2018) observed that routine soil pH measurements are regularly performed following the AFNOR standard (X31-103, 1988), which recommends a 1:2.5 soil/water ratio, and the International standard (ISO-10390, 1994) which recommends a 1:5 soil/water ratio. Accordingly, it is not surprising that pH data values from soil analysis in Cameroon are with different methods. This problem is common to several countries and the harmonization of soil pH data for filling the databases is of prime interest, given the preponderant role of pH in soils. Several functions have been developed to convert soil pH values with acceptable margins of error (Ahern et al., 1995; GlobalSoilMap, 2015; Kome et al., 2018b; Miller and Kissel, 2010; Minasny et al., 2011). Depending on the situation, the most suitable equation was used to standardize the data.

3.2.1.1.6.4 Soil available phosphorus (P)

There are quite some methods for available P extraction, which vary in principle and technical details. The choice of a specific method is dependent on several factors, first among them is the soil pH, which determines the acidity or alkalinity of soils. Clay content, organic matter concentration, and soil management such as fertilizer input to soil might also be considered in the choice of P extraction method (Perrott et al., 1993; Qian et al., 1992; Tran and Giroux, 1985). Since extracting agents have different abilities to extract different forms and amounts of P, the choice of an ideal method has been based on the regional understanding of soil properties and the solubility of the forms of P prevalent in the region. Accordingly, Olsen extracting solution, 0.5 N sodium bicarbonate solution with pH adjusted to 8.5, was developed for mildly acidic to alkaline soils and has been widely used for calcareous soils (Olsen et al., 1954). For the highly weathered acid to neutral soils, with low cation exchange capacity, Mehlich-1 extracting solution (0.05 N hydrochloric acid and 0.025 N sulphuric acid) has been developed (Mehlich, 1953). Mehlich-3 extractant is a combination of acids (acetic and nitric acids), salts (ammonium fluoride and ammonium nitrate), and a chelating agent (ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid) and is appropriate for extracting P and other elements from a wide range of soils, from acid to calcareous soils (Mehlich, 1984). Thus, Mehlich-3 is considered to be a universal extractant (multi-nutrient extractant) for a wide range of soils, including calcareous soils (Mallarino and Blackmer, 1992). Furthermore, methods such as Bray II and Mehlich-1 are designed to extract P from non-calcareous soils, with Bray I and Mehlich-3 for extracting available P from acidic, slightly acidic, and slightly alkaline soils, respectively (Ara et al., 2018). Significant relationships were reported among the methods, which makes it possible to convert the results from one method to another (Ige et al., 2006). Using soils with widely varying physicochemical properties in South Africa, White (2019) noticed a strong linear relationship between Bray II, Olsen, and Mehlich III methods, and thus suggested possibilities to convert from one method to another. As such, to convert from Olsen to Bray II and Bray I the factors are 5.20 and 3.88 respectively. For the conversion from Bray II to Mehlich-3, a factor of 1.10 should be considered (White, 2019). Correlation coefficients between methods (Bray-II, Olsen, and Mehlich-3) were strongly dependent on the soil pH of the samples included in the analyses (Mallarino, 1995).

3.2.1.1.7 Data quality control

Setting up a soil database usually involves the inclusion of data from a variety of sources. The diversity of data sources brings in abundant data types sometimes with complex data structures, which often increases the difficulty of data integration and the complexity of the database.

Considering that the initial or original data collection process was marred by some errors, consciously or unconsciously including additional errors would negatively impact the usage of these data. Data need to be of high quality so that reliable decisions can be made out of them, and any serious data collection or rescue should include well-defined procedures and processes that apply data control measures to ensure and preserve the quality of the data. As good quality data are the precondition for analyzing and using data in a way of guaranteeing their values (Cai and Zhu, 2015), data control measures were applied at every stage of the data rescue process. Thus, while collecting, processing, interpreting, and entering data into the database, the data were verified and validated. Verification is a process in which different types of data are checked for accuracy and consistency and validation is a process that follows prescribed rules about the value of data elements. In this study, the quality control process was carried out following the procedures described by Leenaars et al. (2014). The later identified three levels of quality control, corresponding with the three levels of value standardization.

3.2.1.1.7.1 Basic quality control upon entry of original values

Upon data entry, original values were subjected to basic quality control. This implies checks on one-dimensional attribute-values, irrespective of values for other attributes (e.g. total nitrogen content, irrespective of the organic carbon content or C/N ratio). The most important basic controls include the unit of expression (e.g. % or ‰, w% or v%, or cmol kg^{-1}), the domain or value ranges, the attribute definition, e.g. organic carbon, total organic carbon or total carbon, or sand fraction > 0.05 mm or sand fraction > 0.064 mm, etc.

3.2.1.1.7.2 Routine quality control of collated and standardized values

At this level, a set of criteria is assessed to decide on each value of the data. These criteria (Appendix A) are used in several international institutions (ISRIC, NRCS) for the management of quality control of databases (Leenaars et al., 2014). The criteria lead to three possible outcomes:

- Values do not meet the criteria for being included: revisit data source and correct value, if possible, or exclude value.
- Value meets the criteria for being included but is ‘flagged’ as ‘odd’: revisit data source and correct value, if possible, or maintain value.
- Value meets the criteria for being included.

3.2.1.1.7.3 Full quality control of harmonized values

Full quality control implies multidimensional checks on in pedon consistencies. It requires harmonized data that are complete and stratified. Nevertheless, the routine control described in the previous section includes some checks on within pedon consistencies. The criteria applied to reflect some oversimplified assumptions about the verifiability of within pedon consistency.

However, following a rigorous data quality control process does not guarantee that the database is free of errors (Leenaars et al., 2014). Thus, identifying possible erroneous values is still doable. The follow-up, to verify and maintain, correct, or exclude the erroneous values is a continuous process when it comes to database construction and maintenance (Muşlu et al., 2015).

3.2.1.1.8 Database structure

While developing and implementing a soil database model in Nigeria, Odeh et al. (2012) investigated existing soil profile database models and reported evidence of high diversity in their content, schemas, and setup. They suggested consider proceeding as pragmatically as possible and to create a simple database with metadata models. Following the same orientation, we used the simplified template of AfSIS (African Soil Information Services) as described in Leenaars et al. (2014), to built-up the general structure of Camsodat. The simplified database provides the basis for the compilation of the legacy soil data as a subset of the AfSIS database. The data tables were organized to avoid as much as possible data redundancy and very much mirrors the principles that were assumed when developing the data entry template, reflecting the process of data entry as i) source inventory (digital and/ or analog); ii) profile inventory; iii) profile layer property value entry; and v) metadata entry, aggregated at the appropriate level.

3.2.1.1.9 Samples density improvement

Sampling is a selection of a subset of individuals from within a population, to estimate characteristics of the whole population (Wang et al., 2012). Spatial sampling methods aim to get results of higher quality at a lower cost. Commonly applied constraints are the cost constraint that does not exceed a given budget and the quality constraint that the result meets a given minimum requirement (Cochran, 1977). For mapping or estimating the spatial distribution of a soil property, the accuracy of the result will usually be increased by dispersing the sample locations so that they cover the study area as uniformly as possible (Walvoort et al., 2010).

The purpose when soil data is generally diverse and the spatial coverage of the resulting collecting legacy soil databases is not always uniform. It is often necessary, when budgets permit, to consider collecting additional data to complete the spatial coverage to make predictions more accurate. This involves choosing a sampling strategy. In a design-based sampling strategy, the spreading of the sample locations can be achieved by sampling on a randomly placed regular grid. An alternative is stratified random sampling, using geographically compact subareas as strata. By using these compact sub-areas as strata, spatial clustering of the sample locations can be avoided, which usually increases the accuracy of the estimated spatial mean. In this study, we used the stratified random sampling approach strategy to propose the spatial localization of new potential soil profiles to be collected to spatially cover the country and thus increase the precision of future predictions. We performed the analysis in the “spcosa” R package (Walvoort et al., 2010).

3.2.1.2 Primary soil data collection in the cocoa and fallow systems

These data were collected during a field campaign in the municipality of Ayos, Centre Region. These data were collected to assess the comparative dynamics of carbon stock accretion in the two systems.

3.2.1.2.1 Sample size

Based on Yemefack's (2005) conceptual framework of land-use dynamics in the shifting agricultural landscape mosaic, four age classes corresponding to specific fallow types were used to identify plots for field data collection. These included young fallow (YF, 3–5 years old), bush fallow (BF; 8–10 years old), tree fallow (TF; 15–20 years old), and secondary forest (SF; 30–50 years old). CAF systems of corresponding ages, comprising respectively young cocoa farms (YCO), mature cocoa farms (MCO), old cocoa farms (OCO), and very old cocoa farms (VCO) were also identified and sampled. The end of the annual mixed crop (CL; 1.5 years old) was set as the beginning of the fallow and CAF systems. The fallow and CAF ages were determined through farmer interviews coupled with a field visit to determine vegetation types characteristic of each age range (Yemefack, 2005).

The sample size for each land-use type was calculated using preliminary data from the ASB Cameroon database with the following formula defined by Bartlett et al. (2001) and Dell et al. (1992):

$$n = \frac{z^2 \sigma^2}{d^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where n is the sample size for each of the land-use type, Z is the abscissa of the normal curve that cuts off an area α at the tails (Israel, 1992), σ is the estimated standard deviation in the population, and d is the desired level of precision, set at 5% for this study. In total, 147 plots were sampled for the study, distributed amongst treatments as follows: YF (13), BF (13), TF (10), SF (22), YCO (20), MCO (17), OCO (19), VCO (28) and CL (5).

3.2.1.2.2 Sampling design

The area (Figure 3.3) was first stratified to represent the distinct ecological and physiographic zones of the sub-division (Ayos), with at least two villages per area. In each village, data and sample collection were preceded by a village meeting with the chief and farmers, to identify and select homogeneous land-use types.

Figure 3.3: Villages where soil samples were collected in Ayos

Field data were collected using the rapid assessment (RA) method developed by Hairiah et al. (2010). Soil samples were collected at 30 cm depth in nested 1 m² sub-sub plots derived from a 200 m² subplot, nested in a 2 000 m² plot. This method has been extensively used in the tropics by several authors (Ekoungoulou et al., 2014; Kotto-Same et al., 1997; Magne et al., 2014; Njomgang et al., 2011).

3.2.1.2.3 Laboratory analysis

Soil samples were air-dried and sieved to 2 mm and 0.5 mm. Organic carbon was determined by Heanes' improved chromic acid digestion and spectrophotometric procedure (Heanes, 1984). Bulk density was determined following (Pauwels et al., 1992).

3.2.2 Environmental covariates gathering

Soils can be described by the main environmental soil-forming factors, which are: climate, organisms, relief, parent material, and time. Refinements of the modeling framework were made over the years, including the scorpan (Grunwald, 2010) framework with both spatially and temporally explicit Satellite products such as Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) and Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) which have been extensively used as representatives for the soil-forming factors. Thus, Remote sensing is offering possibilities for improving incomplete spatial and thematic coverage of current regional and global soil databases (Mulder et al., 2011). In this study, the selection of environmental variables (covariates) was based on criteria described by Chen et al. (2018): derived as far as possible from freely available geo-datasets at least at the Cameroon national level, and have a logical relationship with target soil properties according to the literature. These covariates included terrain attributes, derived from the SRTM 30 m digital elevation model (DEM). Climate data, such as mean annual rainfall and temperature, cloud cover, land surface temperature, etc. Land cover and vegetation indexes. The spatial layers obtained from the WorldGrids (vegetation cover index, the precipitable water vapour, the land temperature surface, RED reflectance, Landform, and the bare ground) have been extensively described and used for soil modeling (Hengl et al., 2017a, 2017b).

3.2.2.1 WorldGrids

The detailed description of the WorldGrids is provided in Reuter and Hengl (2012). It was developed as a component of the GSIF (Global Soil Information Facilities), which is the ISRIC's framework

for producing open soil data with global coverage. WorldGrids is a data portal, for collecting, storing, accessing, and interacting with gridded data, launched in 2012. It has been used to serve gridded maps and will allow overlay and subsetting operations for the grids available on the server (Web Processing Service). The main idea of the WorldGrids portal is to motivate Digital Soil Mapping teams in the world to use publicly available, standardized global soil covariate layers derived, for example, from SRTM DEM, MODIS Terra products, various climatic, land cover and geological maps. WorldGrids was designed as a (de)-central repository, which means that ISRIC will support submissions of new data to the repository via the network of users. The functionality and list of layers available on WorldGrids for production mapping will be continuously revised and extended.

Figure 3.4: Precipitable water vapour and land surface temperature derived from MODIS

3.2.2.2 Climatic data (WorldClim)

Climate data selected for this study mainly come from the WorldClim¹ program (Fick and Hijmans, 2017). The WorldClim contains datasets of spatially interpolated monthly climate data for global

¹ <https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>

land areas at high spatial resolution (approximately 1 km²). These data include monthly temperature (minimum, maximum, and average), precipitation, solar radiation, vapor pressure, and wind speed, aggregated across a target temporal range of 1970 – 2000, using data from between 9 000 and 60 000 weather stations around the world. Weather station data were interpolated using thin-plate splines with covariates. Only basic climate indicators such as monthly minimum, average and maximum temperatures as well as annual precipitation averages were used. Other climate data were obtained from the NASA MODIS² project (Table 3.1).

Figure 3.5: Mean annual rainfall and mean annual temperature derived from WorldClim

3.2.2.3 Terrain attribute data (STRM)

Terrain data was acquired from data from the Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM). The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) delivers an elevation value to the nodes of a 30 m x 30 m grid, which covers the whole country. From DTM data, several classic geomorphometric indicators were calculated to characterize relief properties likely to influence soil formation (Danielson and Gesch, 2011). The “Terrain Analysis” module of the SAGA GIS software (Conrad et al., 2015) was used

² <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/about/>

for the production of the following indicators: Valley Bottom Flatness (VBF), Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), Slope, Curvature Indices (PCU), Topographic Position Index (TPO and NTO), Deviation from Mean Value (DMV) and Valley depth (Vdepth).

Figure 3.6: Above sea level elevation and slope derived from STRM

3.2.2.4 Listing of covariates used

All the covariates used in this thesis are listed in Table 3.1. Each of them contains descriptive information, original resolution, and the main reference allowing to have more information on its technical specifications and its calculation methodology. In total, 36 covariates were used, mainly representing soil formation factors such as terrain attributes, climate, and vegetation. Not included, due to unavailability, but with a logical and sound relationship with soil properties, are environmental variables (covariates) that represent parent material and, other than vegetation index and bare ground, land cover/land use. Each of the covariates was resampled to 100 m resolution. In this study, we assessed the contribution of SoilGrids in predicting national soil properties. As suggested by Hengl et al. (2017a) we included SoilGrids maps as covariates to predict countrywide soil properties distribution in Cameroon. We also investigated the gap between the national estimate of SOCS and global SoilGrids and Harmonized World Soil Data (HWSD) estimates.

Table 3.1: Environmental covariates used to fit the DSM models

Code	Description	Resolution	Source	Citation
DEM	Digital Elevation Model	30 m	STRM	(Rabus et al., 2003)
VBF	Valley Bottom Flatness	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
TWI	Topographic wetness index	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
Slope	Slope	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
PCU	Profile curvature	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
DVM	Deviation from Mean Value	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
PTO	Positive topographic openness	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
NTO	Negative topographic openness	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
Vdepth	Valley depth	30 m	STRM	(Danielson and Gesch, 2011)
Temp	Mean annual temperature	1000 m	WorldClim	(Fick and Hijmans, 2017)
Rain	Mean annual rainfall	1000 m	WorldClim	(Fick and Hijmans, 2017)
Precip2	Temperature seasonality	1000 m	WorldClim	(Fick and Hijmans, 2017)
Precip1	Precipitation of wettest month	1000 m	WorldClim	(Fick and Hijmans, 2017)
GLC1	Global 30m tree cover	30 m	WorldGrids	(Sexton et al., 2013)
Lith	Rock types, basic volcanic	250 m	WorldGrids	(Hartmann and Moosdorf, 2012)
PWV	Precipitable water vapor	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Gao and Kaufman, 2003)
BARL	Bare ground	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Hansen et al., 2013)
Cloud1	Mean annual cloud cover	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Wilson and Jetz, 2016)
Cloud2	Mean monthly cloud cover	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Wilson and Jetz, 2016)
RED	Red reflectance, long term average	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Hansen et al., 2013)
EVI1	Long term monthly enhanced vegetation index	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Savtchenko et al., 2004)
EVI2	Mean monthly enhanced vegetation index	1000 m	WorldGrids	(Savtchenko et al., 2004)
Lform	Landform class, hills	250 m	WorldGrids	(Sayre et al., 2014)
GLC2	Global 30m grasslands	30 m	WorldGrids	(Sexton et al., 2013)
LST	Mean annual daily land surface temperature	1000 m	MODIS	(Wan, 2013)
PWV	Monthly precipitable water vapor	10 000 m	MODIS	(Gao and Yoram J., 1992)
LST3	Long term averaged mean annual nighttime surface temperature	1000 m	MODIS	(Wan, 2013)
LST2	Long term averaged mean annual daily surface temperature	1000 m	MODIS	(Wan, 2013)
LTC	Landsat tree cover	30 m	Landsat	(Gao and Yoram J., 1992)
SWIR1	Landsat short wave infrared (B4)	30 m	GFC	(Hansen et al., 2013)
SWIR2	Landsat short wave infrared (B7)	30 m	GFC	(Hansen et al., 2013)
NIR	Landsat Near Infrared 2014	30 m	GFC	(Hansen et al., 2013)
Sand	Global predicted sand fraction	250 m	SoilGrids	(Hengl et al., 2017a)
Silt	Global predicted silt fraction	250 m	SoilGrids	(Hengl et al., 2017a)
Clay	Global predicted clay fraction	250 m	SoilGrids	(Hengl et al., 2017a)
pH	Global predicted soil pH	250 m	SoilGrids	(Hengl et al., 2017a)

GFC = Global Forest Change; MODIS = Moderate-Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer; STRM = Shuttle Radar Topography Mission.

3.2.3 Soil data processing

3.2.3.1 Data splining for depth harmonization

During soil surveys, soil profiles are divided into horizons. The number of horizons and the position of each horizon is generally based on attributes observed in the field, such as morphological soil properties (Bishop et al., 1999). Soil profiles are described by the genetic horizon with the assumption that horizon observations of a given soil attribute represent its value for the corresponding depth interval (Odgers et al., 2012). Accordingly, a bulk sample or representative sample is usually collected from these horizons and also assumed to represent the average value for a given soil attribute over the depth interval sampled (Malone et al., 2017). Depending on the study objectives, there are other situations where samples are collected at fixed depths, without considering the differentiation of horizons. Samples for soil fertility tests, for example, are generally limited to the topsoil (0–15 cm, 0–25 cm or 0–30 cm). Therefore, in a typical legacy soil database, it is not uncommon to have different survey reports with data for different combinations of horizons and depths (Akpa, 2016a). To circumvent the challenge posed by varying horizon or sample depths, DSM techniques using continuous depth functions or splines have been developed to map soil properties at specified depth intervals (Bishop et al., 1999; Malone et al., 2009b).

Figure 3.7: Illustration of the mass preserving spline depth function

The vertical distribution of soil properties along the soil profiles was modeled with the mass preserving equal-area quadratic splines (Malone et al., 2009). It is a series of quadratic polynomials that join at the “knots” located at the horizon boundaries (Bishop et al., 1999). It passes through each soil horizon, and thus maintains the average value of the soil attributes (Figure 3.7). The “knots” are linear between horizons but quadratic within the horizons; giving a linear-quadratic smoothing spline. Detailed background knowledge of spline has been elaborated by Bishop et al. (1999) and Malone et al. (2009b), and a summary of the mass-preserving spline algorithm following Malone et al. (2009b) is provided.

For a given soil profile and a given soil property, the boundaries of the n horizons are denoted by $x_0 < x_1, \dots < x_n$. The soil property values, y_i ($i = 1 \dots n$) could be modeled mathematically as:

$$y_i = \bar{f}_i + e_i \quad (3.2)$$

where \bar{f}_i is the mean value of $f(x)$ over the interval (x_{i-1}, x) , and e_i represents the measurement error with mean 0 and variance σ^2 . Finally, $f(x)$ is the spline function, which is found by minimizing:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{f}_i)^2 + \lambda \int_{x_0}^{x_n} \hat{f}(x)^2 dx \quad (3.3)$$

The first term in Equation 3.3 represents the fit of the spline to the data while the second term is the roughness of the function $f(x)$. The lambda (λ) controls the trade-off between the fit and the roughness of the spline. Several (λ) values have been tested for various soil attributes but the value of 0.1 has been reported to give good results for some soil attributes (Bishop et al., 1999). However, spline function was reported to be limited in their capacity to estimate soil attributes with abrupt changes in the soil properties (Akpa, 2016a). In such conditions, including a quasi or pseudo horizon to the existing profile data could improve the result.

A useful feature of the spline function is that it is mass preserving, or in other words, the original data is preserved and can be retrieved again via integration of the continuous spline (Malone et al., 2009). Compared to exponential decay functions where the goal is in defining the actual parameters of the decay function, the spline parameters are the values of the soil attribute at the standard depths that are specified by the user. This is a useful feature because one can harmonize a whole collection of data. After using the spline function to determine values at standard GlobalSoilMap depth intervals (0 – 5, 5 – 15, 15 – 30, 30 – 60, 60 – 100, 100 – 200 cm), it is still possible to have the

value of a soil property at cumulative depth intervals (e.g. 0 – 30 cm) using the weighted averages of resulting splined values.

3.2.3.2 Soil organic carbon stock estimation

Soil profiles data required for assessing SOCS include geographic coordinates, soil depth, and individual depth intervals, SOC concentration, bulk density (BD), and volumetric coarse fragments content. The coarse fragment data were mainly derived through sieving and weighing and a few by visual estimation. Bulk density (BD) data were mainly determined using the core sampling method. Unavailable measurements of BD were estimated using a pedotransfert function (PTF). The one defined by Adams (1973) in Equation (3.4) was used as recommended for tropical soils by Minasny and Hartemink (2011).

$$BD = \frac{100}{\frac{OM}{BD_{OM}} + \frac{100-OM}{BD_{Min}}} \quad (3.4)$$

where BD ($g\ cm^{-3}$) is the bulk density, OM is the organic matter content (%), BD_{OM} is the organic matter bulk density ($BD_{OM} = 0.224\ g\ cm^{-3}$), and BD_{Min} the mineral bulk density ($g\ cm^{-3}$), defined in Equation (3.5) as follows:

$$BD_{Min} = 0.935 + 0.049 \text{Log}(\text{depth}) + 0.0055 S_a + 0.000065 (S_a - 38.96)^2 \quad (3.5)$$

with S_a the sand content (%), and $\text{Log}(\text{depth})$ the natural log of the corresponding soil depth (cm).

The SOCS was calculated for each point using Equation (3.6) as follows:

$$SOCS (M_g\ ha^{-1}) = (C \times BD \times h \times \frac{(100-CF)}{100} \times 10) \quad (3.6)$$

where C is the organic carbon concentration ($g\ kg^{-1}$), h is the thickness of the soil layer (m), CF is the fractional percentage (%) of coarse fragments (soil mineral particles $> 2mm$ in size), and BD the bulk density of the fine earth fraction ($g\ cm^{-3}$).

3.2.3.3 Spatial soil modeling methods

3.2.3.3.1 General framework of DSM

In this study, we developed Cameroon's first contribution to the GlobalSoilMap project using digital soil mapping algorithms and legacy soil data. The general structure and the steps to follow for a digital soil mapping project are illustrated in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: DSM framework for soil properties prediction (Hengl et al., 2017a)

3.2.3.3.2 Spatial modelling and predictions

We modeled and predicted soil properties separately for each depth interval together with the residuals at 100 m resolution. We compared the Random Forest (RF) and GBR model and their hybrids implementation with kriging and IDW, using the package *spm* in R (R Core Team, 2019). Although RF (section 2.4.4.4) and GBR (section 2.4.4.2) are both machine learning methods for prediction (regression or classification) by combining the outputs from individual trees, there are some major differences between the two methods. The boosting strategy for training in GBR takes care of the minimization of bias that the random forest lacks. RF overfits a sample of the training data and then reduces the overfit by simply averaging the predictions, while GBR repeatedly trains trees or residuals of the previous predictions. However, there are some major differences between these two methods; GBR uses regression trees for prediction purpose where RF uses a decision tree, the boosting strategy for training in GBR takes care of the minimization of bias which the random

forest lacks, and RF overfit a sample of the training data and then reduces the overfit by simple averaging the predictors while GBR repeatedly train trees on the residuals of the previous predictors.

3.2.3.3.3 Hybridization of prediction models by interpolation of residuals

We applied ordinary kriging (OK) and inverse distance weighting (IDW) as hybridization methods on the residuals of predicted estimates with RF and GBR models. Inverse distance weighted interpolation may be preferred over kriging-based techniques when there is a problem of making meaningful estimates of the spatial structure from sparse data or in case of weak spatial structure. Although generally more precise than IDW, OK requires certain expertise and acquaintance. We hypothesized that because of the poor spatial structure of residual after modeling soil data, IDW hybridization might produce results comparable to OK, which is practically more complex to deploy.

3.2.3.3.3.1 Ordinary kriging (OK)

Ordinary kriging predicts the values at the point of the region for which a description of the spatial continuity of the data (variogram) is known, using data in the neighborhood of the location. Thus, it provides prediction estimates at the unobserved location of a regionalized variable z , based on the weighted average of adjacent observations within a given area. The theory can be briefly described by considering z to be a realization of a stationary random function Z , which has constant mean and spatial correlation characterized by a variogram (Webster and Oliver, 2007). The ordinary kriging prediction of Z at an unsampled site s_o is defined by equation (3.7):

$$\hat{Z}(s_o) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z(s_i) \quad (3.7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1 \quad (3.8)$$

where the λ_i are weights assigned to each of the observations (Equation 3.8) and derived from the variogram and the spatial configuration of the sampling and prediction locations. They are chosen such that the expected squared prediction error is minimized, under the condition of unbiasedness. The nugget to sill ratio as described by Táany et al. (2009) was used to analyze the spatial structure of the residuals. A variable is said to have strong spatial dependence if the ratio is less than 0.25 and has a moderate spatial dependence if the ratio is between 0.25 and 0.75; otherwise, the variable has weak spatial dependence.

3.2.3.3.3.2 Inverse distance weighting (IDW)

The inverse distance weighting or inverse distance weighted (IDW) method predicts the values of an attribute at unsampled points using a linear combination of values at sampled points weighted by an inverse function of the distance from the point of interest to the sampled points. Inverse distance weighting (IDW) is a deterministic interpolation method with a known scattered set of points. The assigned values to unknown points are calculated with a weighted average of the values available at the known points. It is one of the simplest and most popular interpolation techniques (Setianto and Triandini, 2013) and calculated as in equation (3.7) however, the weights are estimated differently. In IDW, the weights are determined as in equation (3.9);

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{d_i^p}\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{d_i^p}\right)} \quad (3.9)$$

$i = 1, \dots, n$. where d_i is the Euclidian distances between the prediction location and sampling location s_i , and exponent p is the power or distance exponent value chosen based on cross-validation. In this study, we used $p = 2$ based on the cross-validation statistics. Note that the inverse distance weights also sum up to 1 as in equation (3.8).

3.2.3.3.4 Assessment of predictive accuracy

Uncertainties are essential for understanding and dealing with risk in decision-making. The model performances were evaluated with 10-fold cross-validation. The commonly used accuracy metrics were used: the mean error (ME), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the root mean squared error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the coefficient of efficiency (E_1) of Legates and McCabe (1999). The spatial uncertainty of predicted SOCS was estimated by computing maps of lower and upper limits of a 90% prediction interval. We verified that prediction errors (residuals) were normally distributed and derived the lower and upper limits by subtracting and adding 1.96 times the kriging standard deviation from and to the kriging prediction maps. This approach only works for kriging and was recently described and applied in several SOCS uncertainty assessment studies (Vitharana et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Liang et al., 2019).

3.2.3.5 Modeling SOCS dynamics in cocoa and fallow systems

SOCS were plotted against time and the best-fitted functions were identified using CurveExpertProfessional2.0.4 software (Hyams, 2014a). The goodness-of-fit of the parameterized

function to the data were assessed with the coefficient of determination (R^2). The GraphExpertProfessional 1.1.3 software (Hyams, 2014b) was used to plot these functions, and for testing (t-test) the comparison of SOCS accretion between the two systems. Function Growth parameters were then estimated from the resolution of these functions. According to (Prodan et al., 1997), an increase in the SOCS can be defined using equation 3.10:

$$ICC = \frac{\Delta(SOCS)}{\Delta t} \quad (3.10)$$

where $\Delta SOCS$ ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}$) is the variation of SOCS, and Δt is the variation of time (years). Based on this concept, the first derivative of the fitted functions thus expressed its SOCS growth coefficient (GC) as follows (Equation 3.11):

$$GC = \frac{dSOCS(t)}{dt} \quad (3.11)$$

where $SOCS(t)$ ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}$) is the fitted SOCS growth function with time, and $dSOCS(t)$ its first derivative over a time dt . GC is expressed in $Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$.

3.2.3.6 Soil suitability assessment for cocoa production

Cocoa is a major perennial cash crop predominantly cultivated in the humid forest zone of Cameroon (Yemefack et al., 2006b). It represents an important source of national income and has been a leading sub-sector in the economic growth and development of the country (Duguma et al., 2008; Tabi and Mukete, 2017). However, just a few and sparse investigations have been reported on soil fertility assessment in cocoa production areas so far in Cameroon. Our concern in this study was to assess the spatial distribution of the topsoil (0 – 15 cm) properties in the cocoa-growing area in Cameroon to evaluate their specific capability based on DSM outputs. Cocoa was considered in this study as an example of agricultural speculation for the application of digital mapping methods in soil capability assessment. This approach can be extended to all other types of crops grown in Cameroon. Soil properties considered are those which are been consistently reported important for cocoa production. The suitability of individual topsoil (0 – 15 cm) properties were assessed using a set of criteria for cocoa production.

3.2.3.6.1 Relevance of the prediction depth (15 cm)

The cocoa root system is composed of a pivot which sinks vertically into the soil and horizontal tracing lateral roots (Mbondji, 2010). Lateral roots develop in the topsoil layer, where they draw

both nutrients and water necessary for the life of the plant. According to Sys et al. (1993), about 80% of cocoa roots are concentrated in the upper 15 cm of the soil. Likewise, Muñoz and Beer (2001) showed that 50 – 60% of fine cocoa roots are found in 0 – 15 cm depth. In the humid tropical agroforestry system, the roots of cocoa have been consistently reported to be superficial (De Almeida and Valle, 2007; Nygren et al., 2013), likely because cocoa trees capture nutrients from the thick litter layer of the soil (Nygren et al., 2013). Since the majority of the feeding roots of cocoa (80%) are located in the surface soil layers, an analysis of the top 15 cm is likely to be particularly informative. It is also probably the reason why several studies on fertilizer recommendations for cocoa production were limited to the topsoil layer (Snoeck et al., 2010, 2007a, 2007b). Nevertheless, when selecting cocoa soils, the chemical properties of deeper horizons should not be ignored (Buggenhout, 2018), because the taproot is often divided into several secondary roots, and its length at maturity varies between 80 cm and 150 cm (Mbondji, 2010). We appraised the spatial distribution of soil properties at 15 cm depth. Soil depth was harmonized using the equal area quadratic spline function, as described in section 3.2.3.1.

3.2.3.6.2 Suitability criteria

Soil property maps derived from the digital soil mapping process were grouped according to specific capability classes. For each of the properties, three cluster levels were illustrated (High, Moderate, and marginal). The criteria used for clustering the classes for each of the properties are shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Criteria of soil properties suitability

Soil properties	Factor of suitability rating				Reference
	High (S1)	Moderate (S2)	Marginal (S3)	Currently not (N)	
pH	6.0 – 7.5	6.0 – 5.0	< 5	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Total N (g kg ⁻¹)	1.5 – 2.0	1.0 – 1.5	0.5 – 1	< 0.5	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Av.P (mg kg ⁻¹)	> 15	5 – 15	< 5	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
OM (g kg ⁻¹)	> 35	25 – 35	< 25	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Ex. K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	> 0.31	0.11 – 0.31	< 0.11	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Ex. Ca (cmol kg ⁻¹)	6 – 12	3 – 6	< 3	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Ex. Mg (cmol kg ⁻¹)	6 – 12	3 – 6	< 3	any	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
Soil texture	Loam	Clay Loam	Clay	/	(Ahukaemere, 2018)
CEC (cmol kg ⁻¹)	> 24	20 – 24	16 - 20	< 12	(Ayorinde et al., 2015)

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 CAMEROON SOIL PROFILE DATABASE (Camsodat 0.1)

Our investigations to compile legacy soil data in Cameroon led to the version 0.1 of the Cameroon soil Database "Camsodat 0.1". The main features and contents of Camsodat 0.1 are here presented.

4.1.1 Main data sources

The majority of the legacy data from soil surveys in Cameroon are still being held by the survey institutions across the country and abroad. Old soil studies resulted in a large number of legacy soil data from various sources. We collected most of the available soil data from national and international (online) libraries. The main sources contributing to our data rescued are:

4.1.1.1 Internet (Online library)

Several institutions having collaborated with Cameroon within the framework of bilateral cooperation currently have online databases where the legacy soil studies reports are stored. As far as pedological studies are concerned, the IRD online library is the most significant and contains most of the work carried out by IRCAM and ORSTOM in Cameroon. Several other reports, theses, and scientific journals containing relevant soil data from Cameroon were found on the internet.

4.1.1.2 Research Centers

Several national and international research institutions hold Cameroon soil data. Most of the data were collected in the libraries of the Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD), particularly at Yaoundé, Ekona, and Garoua stations. A significant part of the soil data from Cameroon (461 soil profiles) already existed in the World Soil Information Service (WoSIS) at ISRIC's. Indeed, these data were rescued within the framework of the Africa Soil Information System (AfsIS) project and used for soil properties assessment at global (Hengl et al., 2017a, 2014) and continental scale (Hengl et al., 2017b) using DSM procedures. These data were collected and checked for duplication (about 317 location duplicates were recorded). IITA-Cameroon library has also contributed significantly to obtaining several study reports.

4.1.1.3 Universities

The University of Dschang was leading in terms of legacy soil data holding, although these data were stored on analog copies. This observation seems obvious, because it is the first University in Cameroon specializing in agronomic training with a soil science department, and which has also been very active in the past in the framework of international cooperation in soil science. Several other thesis study reports and dissertations containing soil data were obtained from other universities, such as University of Yaoundé I and University of Ngaoundéré.

4.1.1.4 Key informants

Some senior soil scientists from Cameroon and abroad, having participated in soil surveys in Cameroon were consulted. They thus contributed with relevant documents and/or giving precise indications on the projects in which they were involved. We also sometimes received data from them on studies they had conducted in a personal setting.

4.1.2 Spatial location of soil data

In total, 53% of the soil profiles had GPS coordinates, 33% were localized based on sampling maps (SM), and 12% of locations were estimated from the field description (FD) (Figure 4.1). The process of coordinates assignments cannot be carried out free of errors. The quality of the location description in the source report determines the accuracy of estimated coordinates (Samuel-Rosa et al. 2020). When the coordinates were indicated on sampling locations maps, Borůvka et al. (2018) observed that the original marks in those maps were designed mostly by hand and might not be as precise as expected. As a consequence, the estimation of the profile position is generally biased. Localization of the sampling locations is also very complex in the case of composite samples, particularly in the situation when the support area for the composite sample is bigger (Borůvka et al., 2018). The corresponding positioning error will surely propagate while using the data for spatial analysis, as in the process of overlaying the soil data with the gridded environmental covariates for digital soil mapping. Likely, in some cases, the corresponding soil attribute data will not overlay with the corresponding pixel values of the covariates at its real position in the field. This will have the effect of reducing the goodness of fit of the model and in the most extreme situation, could even influence the overall quality of the prediction. Large positional errors were reported to negatively impact soil prediction outcomes (Samsonova et al., 2018). However, investigations are still necessary to understand

how in such conditions, the error on the spatial location of the soil profiles will propagate and hamper the entire process. The spatial stochastic simulation (e.g. Monte Carlo) is a good strategy for such investigation. Samuel-Rosa et al. (2020) recommended further efforts to be invested in assessing the quality of the geospatial data of legacy soil observations, which should ultimately increase the potential of these soil data to be reused.

Figure 4.1: Proportion of profiles whose coordinates were obtained from GPS, sampling map (SM), and field description (FD)

4.1.3 Laboratory methods harmonization

Original SOC concentration data were mostly determined by wet oxidation/digestion using Walkley Black (WB) method (Walkley and Black, 1934) and some with a modified version (Heanes, 1984). Almost 97% of the data was analyzed by the WB method. Only a few (3%) were analyzed using the dry combustion and lost on ignition methods. The standard reference method for reporting soil organic carbon for the GlobalSoilMap project is dry combustion, to at least 900°C (ISO 10694), with values reported in g kg^{-1} . For tephra soils in Cameroon, this proposition has been corroborated by the study of Enang et al. (2018), who reported that the WB method should be used with caution, especially when many different soil types are involved. They also raised attention to consider the position of the sample within the profile (surface or subsurface samples) while conducting the WB method and highly recommended using calcination methods. This was likely because the latter is economically profitable when SOC stocks have to be determined or when organic matter contents have to be compared in different soils.

Many countries in the world have developed national soil texture triangles with specific classes. Nonetheless, the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) soil texture triangle is internationally most widely used, including by international institutions such as FAO (Van

Meirvenne and Van Cleemput, 2010). The standard reference method adopted by the GlobalSoilMap project for reporting particle size classes of sand, silt, and clay (g kg^{-1}) is the USDA Soil Survey Laboratory Methods (GlobalSoilMap, 2015). We transformed soil texture data accordingly (Minasny and McBratney, 2001; Rouseva, 2010; Shangguan et al., 2014). All soil profiles obtained in this study were analyzed using the hydrometric method.

In Camsodat 0.1, soil pH data essentially consists of pH H_2O and pH KCl. Only a few studies have determined the pH CaCl_2 . Figure 4.2 illustrates the representativeness of the different methods of pH analysis. About 99% pH H_2O (Figure 4.2 a) and 90% pH KCl (Figure 4.2 b) were analyzed in 1:2.5 suspensions of the soil/solution ratio respectively. Only a few numbers of samples were analyzed with 1: 5.0 soil/water suspension for pH H_2O (~1%) and 1: 1.0 soil/KCl suspension for pH KCl (~10%). This is in agreement with Kome et al. (2018b) who observed that routine soil pH measurements in Cameroon are often performed following these methods. In the absence of a more adequate model, the soil pH data were converted using the local models (Kome et al., 2018b) developed for volcanic soils in Cameroon.

Figure 4.2: Proportion of analytical methods in the database

Available phosphorus (P) data were essentially estimated using Bray II (91%), Olsen (7%), and others (1%), such as Mehlich-3, Truog and Bray I (Figure 4.2c). This is likely because most of the soil samples analyzed were acidic. However, situations have been reported where Olsen extractant was useful for both acid and calcareous soils (Maghanga et al., 2012). Olsen and the Mehlich-3 methods were also reported to be more reliable than Bray-II for estimating available P on calcareous soils or across soils varying in soil pH and suggested that either the Olsen or Mehlich-3 methods would be much better than the Bray-II test when a single soil-test for P is used for routine analysis in calcareous soils (Mallarino, 1995). For soils rich in free aluminum

oxides, Bray I and II methods were more effective in extracting P than those of Mehlich-3 and Olsen (Tran and Giroux, 1985). This last observation reinforces the use of Bray II as a method for analyzing available phosphorus because of the high level of soil weathering and the probable presence of Metal Oxides. Likewise, the extraction efficiency was reported in the order of Bray II > Mehlich-3 > Olsen in both acidic and alkaline soils (Ara et al., 2018). The data were harmonized to Bray II, using procedures from White (2019).

4.1.4 Trends of soil data collection in Cameroon

Figure 4.3 shows the temporal evolution of soil samples analysed, more or less reflecting the intensity of soil surveys carried out in Cameroon. First soil samples were analysed around 1950 when soil surveys started in Cameroon. These surveys slowly evolved until 1960, and a significant increase followed, reaching the first peak around 1965. Most of the work in French-occupied Cameroon was carried out during this period, especially concerning fieldwork activities.

Figure 4.3: Trend in the number of soil samples analyzed

The presence of a soil analysis laboratory and several soil experts from abroad certainly helped to speed up the investigations, which had a purely agricultural vocation. The period that led to the first peak corresponds to the period of intensified French involvement in soil investigation in Cameroon. Afterward, there is a slight transition period with a decrease in the intensity of activities toward the end 1960s. The highest intensity was observed between 1970 and 1975.

This corresponds to the period of combined activities of ORSTOM and FAO (PNUD) for soil studies in Cameroon. With funding from UNDP in 1974, soil survey activities started and accelerated in the British Cameroon. French pedologists stopped their activities, and the intensity decreased significantly until 1980. These results echo that of Hartemink (2008) and Eswaran et al. (1997) who noticed that until the 1980s, there were active soil survey programs in many tropical countries. With UNDP support, a few studies persisted until 1990, when a sharp drop in activities was observed. More than 15 years after 1990, soil studies remained forgotten, coinciding with the period of the structural adjustment plans (SAP) of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Yengoh and Ardo, 2014). Since the 2000s, the interest in soil assessment restarted and is growing again. The intensity of investigation is again gradually increasing. With the interest recently observed at the level of Cameroon's bilateral partners, it is possible to envisage that this growth will progress in the coming years with projects such as PRESS II (German cooperation) and partners such as OCP.

Many soil chemical and physical analyses in these survey programs were undertaken to characterize and classify soils in surveyed areas. Data from composite samples and soil pit descriptions are available. Also, a considerable amount of soil information is available from soil fertility research of thousands of experimental plots. Both the soil survey and soil fertility data can be used to predict soil properties in areas where no data are available or can be used to predict for a given area (Minasny and Hartemink, 2011). It should be noted that the temporal distribution does in no way imply that the data are necessarily outdated, as is argued by some without a scientific basis, as most soil properties are quite stable over time, and hardly significantly measurable over years if not impacted by severe land degradation (Leenaars et al., 2014). Though some of these data are old and the soil properties may have changed (e.g. pH, organic carbon), they are still, however, the best and only raw soil data available in many countries, as well as in Cameroon (Minasny and Hartemink, 2011).

4.1.5 Database main features

Camsodat 0.1 contains soil morphological and chemical information along with a wide range of physiographic information all organized into tables. The number of measured data for each property varies between profiles and with depth, generally depending on the purpose of the initial studies, as Camsodat is being populated using data produced for different types of studies ranging from reconnaissance soil surveys to more specific soil assessments, each having their specific quality requirements. The fundamental soil record in Camsodat 0.1 is the soil profile

information, which is a specific point on the Earth's surface around which the site is described. The profile consists of a column of soil extending downwards from the soil surface through all its horizons. Each profile is uniquely identified by its number and geographic location. To take into account most of the information, Camsodat has been structured into 4 main tables. The main features of these tables are that of AfSIS.

4.1.5.1 Profile table

Figure 4.4 shows the general information contained in the profile table. The keys information are; the profile ID, profile ID in the initial report, page corresponding to the profile in the initial report, information on field and laboratory manuals and methods, geographical coordinates of the profile, year of profile description, depth of the profile, altitude, slope and parent material of the place of description, region, locality and the soil class in a given classification system.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	PrObj	ProfileID	SrcRep	PridInRep1	PageInRep	FldMnl_ID	LabMnl_ID	Methd X_LonDD	Y_LatDD	oX_LonDD	
2	1	CM_DOC001_001	DOC001	BA012	151	NA	NA	NA	10,293056	5,131944	NA
3	2	CM_DOC001_002	DOC001	BA031	152	NA	NA	NA	10,270833	5,145000	NA
4	3	CM_DOC001_003	DOC001	BA030	162	NA	NA	NA	10,241667	5,145000	NA
5	4	CM_DOC001_004	DOC001	BA149	148	NA	NA	NA	10,301389	5,106944	NA
6	5	CM_DOC001_005	DOC001	BA151	149	NA	NA	NA	10,243056	5,097222	NA
7	6	CM_DOC001_006	DOC001	BA263	150	NA	NA	NA	10,238889	5,123611	NA
8	7	CM_DOC001_007	DOC001	BA021	157	NA	NA	NA	10,270000	5,168056	NA
9	8	CM_DOC001_008	DOC001	BA109	155	NA	NA	NA	10,308333	5,126389	NA
10	9	CM_DOC001_009	DOC001	BA201	158	NA	NA	NA	10,306944	5,159722	NA
11	10	CM_DOC001_010	DOC001	BA025	158	NA	NA	NA	10,240278	5,158333	NA
12	11	CM_DOC001_011	DOC001	BA007	161	NA	NA	NA	10,256944	5,141667	NA
13	12	CM_DOC001_012	DOC001	BA065	164	NA	NA	NA	10,252778	5,177778	NA
14	13	CM_DOC001_013	DOC001	BA079	162	NA	NA	NA	10,250000	5,175000	NA
15	14	CM_DOC001_014	DOC001	BA020	168	NA	NA	NA	10,255560	5,166667	NA
16	15	CM_DOC001_015	DOC001	BA184	167	NA	NA	NA	10,293056	5,180556	NA

Figure 4.4: Profile table information

4.1.5.2 Layers table

It is the largest table, which contains information and properties for each layer in the profiles (Figure 4.5). Data such as profile ID, layer ID, layer number, layers upper and lower depth, horizon name, dry and moist Munsell color, and Physico-chemical soil properties are available.

LyrObj	ProfileID	LayerNr	UpDpth	LowDpth	UpDpthSamp	LowDpthSamp	HorDes	ColorM	oColorM	ColorD	CfLabPc	Sand	Silt	Clay
1	CM_DOC001_001	1	0	15	0	15	Ap	5 YR 3/3	NA	NA	1	51	31	18
2	CM_DOC001_001	2	15	140	120	140	B2	2.5 YR 3/6	NA	NA	0	52	30	18
3	CM_DOC001_002	1	0	10	0	10	Ap	5 YR 3/2	NA	NA	0	43	29	28
4	CM_DOC001_002	2	10	30	30	40	B1	5 YB 3/3	NA	NA	0	37	20	43
5	CM_DOC001_002	3	30	170	150	170	B2	5 YB 3/4	NA	NA	0	5	23	72
6	CM_DOC001_003	1	0	30	0	30	NA	5 YR 3/4	NA	NA	1	38	21	41
7	CM_DOC001_004	1	0	20	0	20	Ap	10 YR 3 / 4	NA	NA	0	70	21	9
8	CM_DOC001_004	2	20	160	140	160	C	7,5 YR 5/6	NA	NA	1	50	21	29
9	CM_DOC001_005	1	0	10	0	10	A	10 YR 3/2	NA	NA	1	79	15	6
10	CM_DOC001_005	2	10	40	30	40	B	10 YR 3/3	NA	NA	0	69	17	14
11	CM_DOC001_005	3	40	90	70	90	C	10 YR 4/4	NA	NA	3	69	14	17
12	CM_DOC001_006	1	0	10	0	10	Ap	7,5 YR 4/2	NA	NA	0	68	23	9
13	CM_DOC001_006	2	10	30	20	30	B	7,5 YR 4/4	NA	NA	0	74	12	14
14	CM_DOC001_006	3	30	80	60	80	C1	10 YR 5/4	NA	NA	0	59	15	26
15	CM_DOC001_006	4	80	100	90	100	C2	10 YR 5/4	NA	NA	0	41	21	38
16	CM_DOC001_007	1	0	10	0	10	Ap	5 YR 3/3	NA	NA	0	55	19	26
17	CM_DOC001_007	2	10	40	30	40	B1	5YR 4/6	NA	NA	0	35	21	44
18	CM_DOC001_007	3	40	180	160	180	B2	2.5 YR 4/8	NA	NA	0	32	14	54
19	CM_DOC001_008	1	0	10	0	10	Ap	3 YR 3 / 4	NA	NA	0	67	19	14

Figure 4.5: Soil layers table information

4.1.5.3 Reference table

Figure 4.6 shows general information contained in the source report table. These are; source report ID, availability of the source report, number of profiles in the source reports, number of horizons or samples, authors, year of publication, the title of the report, report series, report publisher, and the URL of the report when applicable.

N°	SrcRep_ID	SrcRepAvail	nber of profiles	RepAuthor	RepPubYr	RepTitle	RepSerie
1	DOC001	Y	33	Aboubakar Y	1974	Etude pédologique à 1/50 000 du terroir de	Technical report
2	DOC002	N	28	Brian	/	/	Unpublish
3	DOC003	N	17	ALPICAM	2012	Reconnaissance soil survey	
4	DOC004	Y	3	Enang et al. 2016	2016	Soil physico-chemical properties and land s	Journal article
5	DOC005	Y	7	Yerima B.P.K. and Van Ranst E	2005	Major soil classification systems used in the NA	
6	DOC006	Y	121	Tchienkoua M. -/- Murtha G.G.	1991	Reconnaissance soil survey in the Humid FNA	
7	DOC007	Y	48	Gemerden, B.S. van-/- Hazeu,	1999	Landscape Ecological Survey (1: 100,000) cNA	
8	DOC008	Y	76	KIPS Ph. A., P. Faure, Awah E	1987	Soils, land use and land evaluation of the NT	Technical Report N° 37
9	DOC009	Y	23	Siefferman, G,	1964	Carte pédologique du Nord Cameroun au 1NA	
10	DOC010	Y	52	FAO	1965	The soils and ecology of West Cameroun	FAO, No. 2083
11	DOC011	Y	19	FAO/UNDP1	1977	Soil Surveys and land evaluation for the de	Technical report N° 7
12	DOC012	Y	5	Ndjib, G., Awah, E.T., Tchuent	1996	Soils and land suitability of the Ekundu Kur Soils Programme	Technical Re
13	DOC013	Y	15	Vallerie, M.	1973	Contribution a l'etude des sols du Centre S Travaux et Documents de L' O	
14	DOC014	Y	55	Brabant. P. and Humbel. F.X.	1974	Notice Explicative No. 51. Carte pedoloiq	Notice explicative 51

Figure 4.6: Sample of the list reference table

4.1.5.4 Table of laboratory methods

This table contains information on the laboratory analysis methods (Figure 4.7). The main columns of this table are; the name of laboratories where the analyses were performed, specific analytical methods used for each of the properties contained in the report.

SrcRep_ID	Laboratory	OrgC	Total_N	Av.P	pH	pH_KCl	CF	Texture	Ca	Mg	Na	K	BD
DOC004	UDS	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.0	1:2.0	Sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC007	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	Sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC008	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	Sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC011	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	Sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC012	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	Sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC014	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC015	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC017	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC018	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC019	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC022	ORSTOM_FL	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC023	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC024	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC025	ORSTOM_YD	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC026	Dschang	WB	Kjeldahl	Olsen	1:2.5	1:2.5	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC027	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:1.0	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD
DOC028	IRAD_EK	WB	Kjeldahl	Bray II	1:2.5	1:1.0	sieve	HM	SC+EDTA	SC+EDTA	SC+FP	SC+FP	OD

Figure 4.7: Laboratory methods table

4.1.5.5 Other tables

The other tables essentially contain the metadata on the data existing in the tables presented above. Most of them are code dictionaries, units of soil properties, etc.

Although the design of the tables provides for easy migration to a relational database system, this aspect was not addressed in this work. The design of a relational structure could be elaborated at the time of setting up a more complex soil information system, integrating not only point data from soil profiles but also existing soil maps in Cameroon.

4.1.6 Spatial coverage of rescued legacy soil data and potential

In Camsodat 0.1, soil observations and measurements are currently compiled from over 70 data sources, and include values for approximately 35 soil attributes, with the soil analytical attribute values measured in over 4 laboratories. Currently, the complete dataset contains a total of 5 250 layers distributed over 1 600 georeferenced points. This study has led to a significant contribution in terms of legacy soil data rescue in Cameroon.

Figure 4.8: Spatial distribution of soil profile (Camsodat 0.1) in Cameroon

Despite these efforts, there is almost as much untapped information from other sources (mostly private) that is not freely available as Paterson et al. (2015) noticed in South-Africa. Our observations from soil analysis laboratories in Cameroon suggest that there are thousands of other data privately available. It is trickier to include these data into the national database, as there are client confidentiality clauses and intellectual rights which currently prohibit the sharing of most of them. The reasons for the unavailability of legacy soil data are varied. Mostly they concern the private nature of the data, as the fact that it has been paid for by someone. Although the purpose for which the data were paid for would already be achieved, the data could be useful for other purposes. Therefore, it might be necessary to explore with laboratories, possibilities of collaborations with private individuals to obtain their consent if their data could be used to populate the national database. Besides, soil survey information held by private agricultural companies, private soil consultants, forestry companies, etc. is often subject to limitations on intellectual property rights. Innovative ways to archive these data such that they are accessible and open to both the private and public sectors must be established. While the right of private individuals to protect information needs to be understood and respected, it remains true that these data represent an invaluable source of information for the production and updating of soil information, making it possible to envisage solutions to the great challenges of our era (Paterson et al., 2015). The sharing of data, at least for the enrichment of the national database, should be considered as a civic duty.

Theoretically, with the current amount of data (soil and environmental) already available, we can potentially elaborate very good baseline soil maps for the entire country. At the continental level, ISRIC developed soil maps for sub-Saharan Africa at a 1-km resolution using about 12 000 observation points (1 profile per 2 500 km²), and later at 250-m resolution using around 18 000 observation points (1 profile per 1 600 km²) each with about 450 profiles from Cameroon. Particle size distribution and national carbon stock were estimated at 1-km resolution using 978 observation points (1 profile per 930 km²) in Nigeria (Akpa, 2016a; Akpa et al., 2016, 2014). In China, Chen et al. (2018a) predicted the national distribution of topsoil pH with 4700 observation points (1 profile per 930 km²) and Liu et al. (2020) estimated the national particle size distribution with 4 579 profile observations in the same country. Similar studies have been intensively carried out in countries with a denser spatial coverage such as France with 1 profile per 16 km² (Mulder et al., 2016a) and Denmark with 1 profile per 23 km² (Adhikari et al., 2013). New data (both newly acquired legacy data and newly collected data) added to the database are necessary to periodically update and improve the baseline soil maps.

Improvement of the sample density and spatial coverage will require a sound sampling network strategy.

4.1.7 Distribution density of legacy soil data and identification of gaps

The spatial distribution of the rescued profiles across the country (Figure 4.8) illustrated a heterogeneous density distribution with areas of high and low density. The densest areas are those in the West, North-West, South and South-West regions (Table 4.1). The regions of Adamaoua, Littoral have very low densities. Supplementary efforts are needed in these regions for additional sample collection.

Table 4.1: Regional distribution density of soil profiles in Cameroon

Regions	Profiles	Area ($\times 1000 \text{ km}^2$)	Density (Profile/1000 km^2)
Far Norh	112	34.263	3.3
North	304	66.09	4.6
Adamaoua	37	63.701	0.6
North-West	176	17.3	10.2
South-West	140	25.41	5.5
Littoral	18	20.248	0.9
West	178	13.892	12.8
Centre	79	68.953	1.1
East	131	109.002	1.2
South	257	47.191	5.4

The current national average density is one profile per 325 km^2 . However, in 2016 according to Batjes et al. (2016), the density of soil profiles coverage was ~ 1 profile per 1000 km^2 in Cameroon (AfSIS database). In a recent ranking, the value rose to ~ 3 profiles per 1000 km^2 (Batjes et al., 2020), thanks to the efforts from this study. Based on their ranking, Cameroon has thus moved from 12th to 7th position in Africa in terms of profile coverage per unit area of the national territory. Additional efforts would further improve this result. However, although this rank is indicative, it should be considered with caution as not all African countries have contributed to the WOSIS database. Some data may exist in national databases and regulations such as that of France could restrict the sharing of soil data (Mulder et al., 2016c). Moreover, Arrouays et al. (2017) noticed that large numbers of soil profiles stored in many countries databases are yet not standardized and harmonized according to a global standard and cannot be shared. This result shows that it is important to consider a programming guide for new field data collection to complement this database, in order to produce better national soil maps. The location of new sample collection points can be assisted by using simulation tools to identify new sampling networks.

4.1.8 Sampling Network simulation

In DSM applications, the input soil data are usually from legacy sources, which measurements may have left large spaces unsampled, and we would like to fill in because there, the greatest gain in accuracy can be achieved. Several methods for optimization of the pattern of sample locations have been described in the literature. The methods differ concerning the objective function, and in the way, the method searches for the optimal pattern (optimization algorithm). In model-based sampling, the objective function explicitly defined in terms of the prediction error variance is minimized (Van Groenigen et al., 1999), whereas in spatial coverage sampling, an objective function is defined in terms of the distance between the sample locations and the nodes of a fine interpolation grid (Royle and Nychka, 1998).

The key elements to consider when developing a sampling strategy are budget and accuracy. Although these two parameters are distinct, one often very significantly influences the other. Without having a priori information on these two parameters, we completed the existing observations to 2 000 points by simulating an additional 600 locations, as to maintaining also the representativeness of the spatial coverage of these profiles. If budget or accuracy are defined, then the model can be modified to meet the new requirements. The process consists in dividing randomly the entire country into 2 000 uneven surface geographical strata, a priori containing existing locations (Walvoort et al., 2010). Figure 4.9 illustrates the spatial location of the new profiles to be collected and those existing already.

Figure 4.9: Simulation of the new sampling location in Cameroon

4.2 COUNTRYWIDE DISTRIBUTION OF SOME SOIL PROPERTIES

4.2.1 Summary statistics of splined soil data (Clay, Sand, Silt, and pH)

Splined particle size fractions (PSF) and soil pH data from profiles in the six depths are summarized in Table 4.2. The mean clay content at 0 – 5 cm was 30%, which was slightly higher than silt content at the same depth and increased to 41% at 60 – 100 cm where silt was only 18%.

Table 4.2: Descriptive statistics of splined soil particle size fractions (%)

	Depth	Min	Mean	Median	Max	CV	Skew	Kurt	N
Clay	0 – 5	0.56	30.40	28.57	95.34	58	0.06	1.20	1217
	5 – 15	1.00	32.41	31.22	95.43	55	0.02	1.23	1217
	15 – 30	1.23	36.13	36.00	91.01	51	0.05	1.13	1210
	30 – 60	0.03	40.18	40.79	90.69	48	0.08	1.17	1116
	60 – 100	0.01	41.49	41.74	90.99	51	0.06	1.05	833
	100 – 200	0.98	38.10	36.45	88.65	55	0.08	1.15	569
Sand	0 – 5	0.87	47.87	51.36	96.24	51	-0.17	1.21	1217
	5 – 15	1.45	46.45	49.29	96.60	50	-0.12	1.26	1217
	15 – 30	1.03	43.89	44.77	98.99	52	-0.02	1.26	1210
	30 – 60	0.83	41.62	40.29	97.23	52	-0.10	1.33	1116
	60 – 100	0.96	40.17	37.54	95.42	56	0.16	1.35	833
	100 – 200	0.97	40.88	40.30	97.36	57	-0.07	1.10	569
Silt	0 – 5	1.00	21.72	15.42	85.68	70	0.50	1.50	1217
	5 – 15	1.14	21.20	15.01	86.30	69	0.55	1.52	1217
	15 – 30	0.50	20.01	15.00	87.86	70	0.40	1.59	1210
	30 – 60	0.26	18.22	15.00	87.06	68	0.21	1.53	1116
	60 – 100	0.15	18.33	14.79	85.13	73	0.22	1.16	833
	100 – 200	0.57	20.96	17.62	98.38	62	0.30	1.22	569
pH	0 – 5	3.20	5.52	5.46	9.08	18	0.03	1.17	1463
	5 – 15	3.23	5.51	5.41	9.94	19	0.09	1.16	1463
	15 – 30	3.54	5.53	5.39	10.30	19	0.06	1.22	1442
	30 – 60	3.39	5.67	5.41	10.19	20	0.18	1.21	1281
	60 – 100	3.34	5.96	5.66	10.20	21	0.19	1.43	936
	100 – 200	3.34	6.12	5.79	10.15	22	0.26	1.64	590

Skew = Skewness; Kurt = Kurtosis, N = Sample size

The sample size also gradually decreases from the topsoil layers (N = 1217 for PSF data and N = 1463 for soil pH data) to the subsoil layers (N = 569 for PSF data and N = 590 for soil pH data). Mean sand content was always higher than clay and silt content for all soil depths. The soil pH varies from strongly acid in the three first soil layers (mean = 5.5) to moderately acid in the lowest layers (mean = 5.9). Overall, the PSF distributions showed high variability at all depth, with the coefficient of variation (CV) always above 50%, whereas the soil pH was

moderately variable with coefficients of variation between 18 – 22% (Table 4.2). Silt showed the highest heterogeneity (with CV between 61 and 73) at all soil depths followed by clay and sand. The greatest variability was recorded between 60 – 100 cm depth for PSF components. The frequency distribution of the PSF data is typical and corroborates other studies reports (Adhikari et al., 2013; Akpa et al., 2014; Poggio and Gimona, 2017) given that clay and silt are positively skewed whereas sand is skewed slightly negative. The clay content increases gradually from the topsoil layer to the lower depth with a peak between 60 and 100 cm, likely caused by clay illuviation. The same trend was reported in Nigeria (Akpa et al., 2014; Ayuba et al., 2007; Osei and Okusami, 1991; Sharu et al., 2013) and Denmark (Adhikari et al., 2013). The increase in clay content with depth is the diagnostic of the argic horizon, which is a diagnostic characteristic of subsoils clay enriched majors soil groups types (Acrisol, Lixisol, Alisol, Luvisol) in the World Reference Base for soil resources (WRB, 2015). The mean sand content is higher than the clay and silt contents for each depth, which is commonly found in most of the soils in Africa as reported by Akpa et al. (2014).

4.2.2 Prediction performances

Evaluations were performed comparing the observed values of the subset, with the estimated data, based on the average over 100 repetitions of 10-fold cross-validation and calculating the Coefficient of determination and the RMSE. Table 4.3 summarizes model performance assessment parameters (R^2 and RMSE). Results showed that the combination of the various predictor variables could explain 62 to 64, 26 to 37, 25 to 44, and 21 to 53% of the variation in soil pH, clay, sand, and silt contents, respectively (Table 4.3). Model predictions accuracy of PSF for the upper three depths were relatively better than the three lower depths with higher R^2 and lower RMSE values. This might be due to a higher texture variability in the deeper layers (Adhikari et al., 2013). Clay had the lowest R^2 values for the upper three depths, whereas the highest R^2 was associated with silt, and R^2 values were within the range reported by Adhikari et al. (2013) for silt and sand contents, but outside the range reported for silt content. These values are also greater than the values shown by Padarian et al. (2017) in Chile soils for PSF. The highest RMSE values were associated with the sand fraction, and silt content exhibited the lowest RMSE compared to other PSF at equivalent depths as was reported in Nigeria by Akpa et al. (2014). Zhang and Shi (2019) obtained root mean squared error (RMSE, sand: 15%, silt: 14 %, clay: 6%), and coefficient of determination (R^2 , sand: 53%, silt: 46%, clay: 54%) for PSF in China. Moreover, R^2 was between 0.47 and 0.50 for PSF in the study from Ballabio et al.

(2016) and prediction accuracy (R^2) for sand was 41 – 49 % with RMSE of 15.4 – 17.9%; R^2 of silt varied from 29 to 49 % for different depth intervals (Martins et al., 2019). The clay prediction accuracy from Shabou et al. (2015) was $R^2 = 0.64$ and RMSE of about 10% respectively. Despite the relative similarity of the accuracy estimates in these various studies, the observed disparity can be explained successively by the quantity of data used, the quality and importance of the covariates, and the extent of the areas mapped.

Table 4.3: Evaluation of model performances

		RF with SoilGrids						RF without SoilGrids					
		RF		RF_IDW		RF_OK		RF		RF_IDW		RF_OK	
		R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE
Silt	0 – 5	49.48	10.72	47.97	11.00	50.37	10.85	45.61	11.24	43.81	11.43	45.85	11.22
	5 – 15	53.11	10.07	50.54	10.33	52.07	10.16	48.04	10.48	46.28	10.76	49.83	10.50
	15 – 30	52.51	09.69	46.43	10.19	51.86	09.56	47.38	10.09	44.64	10.34	47.58	10.08
	30 – 60	46.27	09.04	42.77	09.42	47.09	09.15	40.17	09.63	39.89	09.65	40.94	09.56
	60 – 100	37.36	10.54	33.36	10.87	39.45	10.36	32.74	10.92	28.15	11.29	33.57	10.86
	100 – 200	21.21	11.54	18.03	11.77	21.85	11.49	17.31	11.82	12.91	13.13	19.21	11.68
Sand	0 – 5	44.05	18.08	40.38	18.66	44.11	18.07	42.74	18.29	40.09	18.71	42.13	18.38
	5 – 15	42.56	17.80	38.51	18.42	42.30	17.85	40.34	17.84	39.22	18.31	41.65	18.10
	15 – 30	38.50	17.88	36.25	18.06	39.72	17.99	35.50	17.74	32.75	18.55	37.94	18.10
	30 – 60	28.00	18.30	24.31	18.76	28.33	18.26	27.96	18.31	22.57	18.98	28.18	18.28
	60 – 100	24.00	19.65	22.07	19.90	24.89	19.54	24.08	19.64	19.91	20.17	25.00	19.78
	100 – 200	26.50	19.99	20.28	20.82	26.16	20.17	24.13	20.31	21.84	20.61	24.02	20.45
Clay	0 – 5	35.91	14.21	32.56	14.45	35.77	14.23	31.91	14.34	31.60	14.51	32.71	14.51
	5 – 15	34.57	14.34	32.79	14.57	36.21	14.16	35.26	14.27	28.87	14.85	35.83	14.28
	15 – 30	36.50	14.79	33.08	15.18	36.81	14.75	43.89	14.97	29.47	15.58	44.43	15.26
	30 – 60	33.87	15.74	32.06	15.95	34.50	15.66	31.10	16.06	28.86	16.32	31.57	16.01
	60 – 100	33.85	17.11	32.62	17.27	33.49	17.15	33.07	17.46	26.54	18.03	33.93	17.35
	100 – 200	25.59	18.01	25.51	18.02	26.43	17.91	25.36	18.40	22.97	18.33	26.45	18.48
pH	0 – 5	59.89	0.64	57.01	0.66	59.43	0.64	56.88	0.67	55.76	0.68	57.49	0.66
	5 – 15	62.77	0.62	61.04	0.63	62.72	0.62	59.04	0.64	59.19	0.65	59.53	0.65
	15 – 30	60.74	0.65	58.87	0.68	61.32	0.67	59.28	0.68	57.63	0.69	59.76	0.68
	30 – 60	60.72	0.72	57.72	0.75	61.61	0.74	60.40	0.73	56.18	0.77	61.32	0.74
	60 – 100	60.23	0.81	58.66	0.83	60.38	0.80	59.77	0.81	57.80	0.82	60.32	0.80
	100 – 200	63.72	0.79	61.23	0.82	63.77	0.79	62.78	0.80	61.13	0.82	62.41	0.81

RMSE = Root mean square error; R^2 = Coefficient of determination; RF = Random Forest; RF_OK = Random forest and ordinary kriging hybridization; RF_IDW = Random forest and inverse distance hybridization.

Soil pH showed the best performance on model evaluation at all depths. Our result was comparable to many other reports. Indeed, R^2 was reported to vary between 0.35 and 0.46 and RMSE between 0.27 and 0.35 for the fifth first topsoil layers in the Serra da Mantiqueira, Brazil (Costa et al., 2020). Our RMSE estimates were better (< 0.71) than those reported by Chen et al. (2018) for topsoil pH prediction in China. Likewise, the topsoil R^2 for pH prediction was also between the range (43 – 74%) reported in the tropical afro-montane landscape (Otieno et al., 2020) and higher than that reported (8 – 23%) in the Northern Karnataka Plateau (Martins

et al., 2019). However, variability in the soil pH prediction accuracy is mainly attributed to soil pedological factors and land management, because soil pH distribution is influenced by soil intrinsic (pedogenic) and extrinsic (land management) factors.

Performances of random forest (RF) and random forest hybrids with ordinary kriging (RF_OK) and inverse distance weighing (RF_IDW) were similar, likely for reasons discussed earlier (section 4.2.3). However, the inclusion of SoilGrids as covariate consistently improved the prediction performance (R^2) for up to 10% increases. This finding corroborates that of Liang et al. (2019), who reported SoilGrids to be the best predictors for defining the soil-landscape relationship in China. In addition to being useful sources of information in countries where national estimates of soil properties don't exist (Hengl et al., 2017b), global models such as SoilGrids could thus be very helpful and relevant for improving national and likely local estimates of soil properties.

4.2.3 Spatial distribution of soil properties

4.2.3.1 Summary statistics of predicted soil properties

The statistics of predicted soil properties (clay, sand, silt, and pH) with the random forest algorithm and ordinary kriging hybridization (RF_OK) from different soil depths are displayed in table 4.4. The distribution of the predicted soil properties almost follows a similar pattern as the original spline fitted data, with lesser variability. The model accurately and consistently estimated the average clay, pH, and sand values with a low shift. However, there is a distortion on the prediction of extreme values (minimum and maximum). The minimum clay values, in particular, are increased and the maximum values are decreased as was reported by Silatsa and Yemefack (2019) while predicting soil properties for the North and South-West regions in Cameroon. The increase in the minimum sand values is observed only in deep horizons, and the effect on the distortion of the maximum sand values was slight. This could be attributed to the smoothing out of outliers as prediction models tend to have a smoothing effect (Akpa et al., 2014; Odeh et al., 2003b). Likewise, the reduction of model overfitting could also explain the distortion observed, as the RF algorithm grows a large number of unpruned trees and makes a final prediction using the average prediction of the entire trees (Breiman, 2001). Figures 4.10 to 4.12 show the maps of predicted particle size fractions. The spatial prediction of soil properties suggested that the distribution of soil properties on the surface followed the variation in environmental factors controlling their distribution as was early noticed by Martins et al.

(2019). However, the most striking features of the PSF distribution maps can be described by referring to the geological history of the country as was reported at the continental scale in Europe (Ballabio et al., 2016) and national scale in China and Nigeria (Akpa et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2020) respectively. Thus, our estimates could be significantly improved by including the covariate such as high-resolution parent material (geology) map. Besides, higher sample density would be required for better results as mentioned by Carvalho Junior et al. (2014) for tropical countries where soil pattern is complex due to the geological uplift than other regions.

Table 4.4: Summary statistics of predicted soil properties

	Depth	Min	Mean	Median	Max	CV	SD	Skew	Kurt
Clay	0 – 5	3.68	31.11	31.52	82.45	28	8.73	0.02	1.46
	5 – 15	4.98	33.60	34.06	79.36	28	9.28	0.06	1.43
	15 – 30	2.92	37.98	37.99	78.48	27	10.47	0.13	1.61
	30 – 60	3.38	42.91	42.61	82.56	26	11.00	0.15	1.30
	60 – 100	4.42	45.02	44.50	82.26	27	12.45	0.22	1.35
	100 – 200	5.35	41.13	43.75	80.51	23	9.39	0.32	1.34
Sand	0 – 5	0.00	50.04	41.87	97.13	20	9.88	-0.10	1.41
	5 – 15	0.00	48.51	48.30	89.73	20	9.69	0.06	1.39
	15 – 30	0.00	45.73	45.11	98.13	21	9.51	0.08	1.22
	30 – 60	2.03	42.17	40.71	85.02	22	9.22	0.23	1.08
	60 – 100	4.41	40.66	39.14	91.84	23	9.48	0.17	1.06
	100 – 200	4.86	42.71	41.87	97.13	20	8.70	0.10	1.27
Silt	0 – 5	1.09	18.84	17.33	70.04	44	8.22	0.19	0.94
	5 – 15	0.00	17.89	16.57	70.59	44	8.03	0.15	0.87
	15 – 30	0.00	16.28	15.36	69.86	47	7.65	0.08	0.88
	30 – 60	0.00	14.91	14.40	82.89	50	7.45	0.04	0.87
	60 – 100	0.00	14.32	13.85	64.61	50	7.09	0.03	0.80
	100 – 200	0.00	16.15	15.01	67.61	33	5.45	0.19	1.08
pH	0 – 5	3.67	5.51	5.36	8.31	11	0.62	0.27	1.71
	5 – 15	3.60	5.48	5.31	9.23	12	0.65	0.30	1.81
	15 – 30	3.62	5.44	5.23	9.60	13	0.69	0.31	1.94
	30 – 60	3.63	5.50	5.25	9.50	14	0.75	0.33	2.19
	60 – 100	3.65	5.68	5.38	9.08	14	0.82	0.37	2.30
	100 – 200	3.89	5.76	5.50	9.05	15	0.88	0.08	2.70

*Skew = Skewness; Kurt = Kurtosis

4.2.3.2 Spatial distribution of predicted clay content

Clay distribution seems to be more related to the presence of sedimentary rocks in the substrate, especially in areas where limestone and claystone are common (Hrischeva and Gier, 2002; Santos and Varajão, 2004; Vaculikova and Plevova, 2005; Weaver, 1956). There is an increase in the clay content with depth especially in the southern part of the country (Figure 4.10).

Figure 4.10: Predicted clay content distribution in Cameroon

The variability of the clay content is high in the surface horizons (0 – 30 cm) and gradually decreases with the soil depth, and magnitude of the vertical increase in clay content differs from one location to another as was also reported in Nigerian soils (Akpa et al., 2014). At some locations this is steady and gradual while it is abrupt in others, giving rise to a bulge of clay with depth, characteristic of clay enriched horizons (FAO, 2006). As such, clay content was, for example, reported significantly affected by soil depths (higher in subsoil) in the western highlands of Cameroon, (Takoutsing et al., 2016a; Takoutsing et al., 2018).

There are also patches of high-to-medium clay content around the Lake Chad (Møberg and Esu, 1991) and the banks of rivers (Dja, Nyong, Sanaga, etc .) which was also found by previous studies (Fadil-Djenabou et al., 2015; Nzeugang et al., 2013; Nzeukou et al., 2014). Likewise, heterogeneous clayey materials were revealed in the Douala sub-basin as thick clay deposits at the upper slopes (Ngon Ngon et al., 2012). Diko and Ekosse (2012) also reported Ediki sandstone as kaolin clay host occurrence in the Douala sedimentary basin. Figure 4.10 reveals an increase of clay content with depth in the southern part of the country, as compared with the northern part, same as Akpa et al. (2014) observed in Nigeria. This supports the work of Yerima and Van Ranst (2005a) who reported an increase in the clay content with depth in majors soils groups of southern Cameroon. The vertical clay movement (eluviation and illuviation), faunal perturbation, and the movement of clay particles caused by soil erosion are generally used to justify the clay migration from one location to another (Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005b), as they significantly affect the ongoing pedogenetic process. The prevalence of Quaternary volcanic rocks (basalt, lava flows, and ash deposits) might account for the high clay content in some spots of the volcanic line of Cameroon as Olowolafe (2002) also showed on the Jos Plateau in Nigeria.

4.2.3.3 Spatial distribution of predicted sand content

The sand content (Figure 4.11) is relatively high compared with clay and silt content across the country. This can be attributed to variation in the parent material and is partly due to the aeolian deposition of sands from the Sahara Desert in the northern regions.

Figure 4.11: Spatial distribution of predicted sand content in Cameroon

Figure 4.12: Spatial distribution of predicted silt content in Cameroon

The sand content, however, decreased gradually southward with latitude and also with soil depth. This certainly corroborates the enrichment of the deep horizons with clay as reported in the previous section (Section 4.2.3.2). The soils are predominantly sandy in the northern part of the country, which could be attributed to the coarse nature of the predominant parent materials in these regions. They are overlain by weathered sandstones and the late and early cretaceous sedimentary, with Neoproterozoic to Cambrian plutonic and volcano plutonic complex (Dumort, 1968). It is also known that land cover change might affect the sand content in the soil. Sand content increased when converting natural forest to cropland, and this is most likely resulting from preferential removal of clay and silt and residual accumulation of sand in soil surface resulting from preferential segregation and evacuation of the smaller silt and clay particles, by accelerated water erosion (Abad et al., 2014; Ayele et al., 2013). This was also consistently observed and reported in the North-West region of Cameroon (Tellen and Yerima, 2018).

4.2.3.4 Spatial distribution of predicted silt content

The silt content of the soils in Cameroon is relatively low (Figure 4.12). However, soils with medium silt content occur in the North-West, and Adamaoua regions. Most soils of the Waza plains are silty, likely derived from wind sorted desert sands or Aeolian drifts as was reported in Nigeria (Akpa et al., 2014). The South and East regions have very low silt rates.

4.2.3.5 Spatial distribution of textural classes in Cameroon

Soil texture, as an intrinsic soil property, mostly reflects the parent material characteristics rather than the environmental conditions (Tellen and Yerima, 2018). It is the result of physicochemical processes acting on rocks and minerals (in situ or after transportation), influenced by external factors like climate, topography, and living organisms. Soil texture is the proportional measure of the particles of sands, silts, and clays contained in the soil and as such, represents a summary of the combination of information from the three previous maps (Figure 4.10 to 4.12) while respecting a defined textural triangle. Figure 4.14 illustrates the distribution of textural soil classes in Cameroon according to the USDA classification (Figure 4.13).

Figure 4.13: USDA soil texture triangle (Groenendyk et al., 2015)

There is a high variability of the textural classes (Figure 4.14) in the surface horizons (0 – 5 cm, 5 – 15 cm, and 15 – 30 cm). The variability gradually increases from the surface horizon (0 – 5 cm) and reaches its maximum between 15 and 30 cm in depth. Several factors might justify such variability of textural classes. Parental material is likely overriding and might justify most of the variability. However, several factors could also further account. Urbanization was reported to strongly influenced soil particle fractions distribution in Hong-Kong for over 5 decades (Sun et al., 2013). Land cover and land-use change were also reported to affect soil texture variability (Tellen and Yerima, 2018). In situations where land-use change includes agriculture with soil tillage, the effect on soil texture is exacerbated (Abad et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2017). Soil erosion was also reported to significantly shape the spatial distribution of soil textural classes, in the sense that sediments near the source are enriched in sand-size particles, whereas farther away, sediments are enriched in clay-sized particles (Ayele et al., 2013). With such high variability, soil texture has often been reported as a component of minimum data set (MDS) indicators in many soil quality studies (Ayoubi et al., 2011; Brejda et al., 2010; Shukla et al., 2006; Singh et al., 2014).

Figure 4.14: Soil texture classes in Cameroon

The importance of soil texture on land capability, water, and nutrient storage, and vegetation distribution and composition are also well documented globally (Fernandez-Illescas et al., 2001; Pinheiro et al., 2018).

In the first two surface horizons (0 – 5 cm and 5 – 15 cm), the succession of textural soil classes as we move from south northward is dominated by sandy clay, sandy clay loam, clay loam, and clay, with some clay spots distributed all over the country in particular near rivers. At the third depth (15 – 30 cm) the same trend is recorded. However, there is a significant increase in the clayey classes southern of the country typical of the major's pedogenic processes related to the highly weathered soil in the area (Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005a). Deeper horizons (> 30 cm) all have the same characteristics with varying proportions of clayey classes.

4.2.3.6 Spatial distribution of soil pH

Figure 4.15 shows the maps of soil pH distribution in Cameroon. The gross pattern is clear, with the pH ranging from 3.7 to 8.3 in the topsoil and 3.9 – 9.1 in the subsoil (Table 4.4). There is also a trend of soil acidity in the south of the country with the opposite feature in the north where most soils are mostly alkaline. The same characteristics are observed when going deeper into the soil profile, with the difference that the pH rises slightly. The observed trend is partly due to parent material (Madsen and Munk, 1987) and largely to the trend in climate from the dry northward to the wet southward as has also been reported in Chinese soils (Chen et al., 2018a). (Tellen and Yerima, 2018) showed that soil pH could significantly change with land-use and elevation in the North-West region of Cameroon.

The soils under natural forest cover had a relatively lower pH value ($\text{pH} < 5.5$), likely because low pH slows down the breakdown of litter due to low microbiological activity (Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005a). Moreover, secondary forests and fallows showed significantly lower pH ($\text{pH} < 6.4$) than those in mixed cropping and cocoa plantation in the humid forest zone of Cameroon (Takoutsing et al., 2016b). The later highlighted that high pH on cultivated lands was related to the slash and burn effect.

Figure 4.15: Spatial distribution of predicted soil pH in Cameroon

4.2.3.7 Spatial distribution of soil pH classes

Soils in southern Adamaoua are mainly acidic, from very strongly acidic to slightly acidic. A transition zone is observed in the North region with neutral soils, then alkaline soils are widespread in the far North (Figure 4.16). The southern part of the country had relatively low soil pH values, probably due to higher precipitation and leaching. Areas of high soil pH were located north of the country, possibly associated with the arid climate as was noticed in China (Liu et al., 2013).

Previous studies indicated several factors explaining the decrease in soil pH. Malhi et al. (1998) showed that long term N fertilization reduced soil pH by as much as 3 units in the 0 – 5 cm layer, but much less in the 5 – 10 cm underlying layer. In some peats, pH was reported to drop significantly (< 4) because of the formation of organic or sulphuric acids (Madsen and Munk, 1987). According to Slessarev et al. (2016), Climate controls many aspects of soil chemistry, as well as soil pH. Indeed, they noticed an abrupt transition from alkaline to acid soil pH that occurs at the point where mean annual precipitation begins to exceed mean annual potential evapotranspiration. As a result, alkaline soils are known to be common in arid climates, while acid soils are known to be common in humid climates (Slessarev et al., 2016). Njukeng and Baligar (2016) reported the soil in the South-West region to be generally acid.

Soil pH is the expression of soil genesis that in turn is a function of soil-forming factors. As such, it's variability and prediction might be significantly influenced by soil intrinsic (pedogenic) and extrinsic (land management) factors (Martins et al., 2019). Core soil sampling followed by laboratory analysis is the traditional method used to collect soil pH data. A recently developed automated soil sampling system capable of measuring soil pH on-the-go has significantly increased sampling resolution with higher relative time and cost benefits in a study from Adamchuk et al. (2004). This is likely an option to explore for a quick update and high-resolution mapping of soil pH in Cameroon. However, a specific combination of covariates and techniques of parameterization that gives the best prediction of pH variation might better capture the pH variation and highly enhance the estimates as showed by Sulaeman et al. (2012).

Figure 4.16: Soil pH class in Cameroon

4.3 SOIL ORGANIC CARBON STOCKS IN CAMEROON

4.3.1. Soil organic carbon stock data

Table 4.5 shows the summary statistics of SOCS data computed from Camsodat 0.1 for the five soil layers. Coefficients of variation vary from 67% in the topsoil to 92% in the subsoil, showing a high variability of SOCS in each layer.

Table 4.5: Summary statistics of SOCS data (Mg ha⁻¹)

	Soil depth (cm)				
	0 – 15	15 – 30	30 – 100	0 – 30	0 – 100
Min	4.4	2.7	1.2	7.0	9.2
Mean	35.2	23.7	64.5	58.7	123.2
Median	30.7	17.9	49.1	24.3	41.7
Max	121.5	118.7	439.4	139.3	578.7
CV (%)	67.0	91.0	92.0	91.0	92.0
Skewness	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
<i>N</i>	1 386	1 348	1 201	1 348	1 201

SOCS values also show a large range within each layer and a positive skewness with coefficients varying between 0.2 and 0.3 at all depth. The mean of each variable is slightly greater than the median (Table 4.5). However, no transformation was done on the SOCS data since the machine learning methods used are rather insensitive to slight shifts from normality (Figure 4.17) (Nisbet et al., 2018).

Figure 4.17: Histograms of SOCS data for various soil depths

4.3.2 Prediction performance of SOCS

Performances of the prediction models are presented in Table 4.6. All models acceptably predicted SOCS distribution in the upper layers (0 – 15 cm and 15 – 30 cm) by capturing at least 52% of the variation based on the average over 100 repetitions of 10-fold cross-validation. In the subsoil layer (30 – 100 cm), the R^2 was slightly lower compared to the upper layers and varied from 44% to 52%.

Table 4.6: Prediction performances of the models derived using 10-fold cross-validation

Models	0 – 15 cm					15 – 30 cm					30 – 100 cm				
	ME	RMSE	MAE	R ²	E ₁	ME	RMSE	MAE	R ²	E ₁	ME	RMSE	MAE	R ²	E ₁
GBR	0.01	14.55	10.58	52.87	35.20	-0.02	12.72	8.52	57.19	38.63	-0.03	39.08	24.09	44.71	33.27
GBR_IDW	-0.04	13.90	9.77	56.96	40.09	-0.04	11.61	7.27	64.30	46.67	-0.26	38.96	22.37	45.03	38.06
GBR_OK	-0.14	13.76	9.65	57.79	40.82	-0.15	11.57	7.38	64.54	46.88	-0.49	37.15	21.67	50.02	39.98
RF	-0.24	13.27	9.20	60.79	43.62	-0.16	11.18	7.16	66.93	48.45	-0.95	36.86	20.97	50.81	41.93
RF_IDW	-0.09	13.13	9.13	61.62	44.03	-0.09	11.10	7.03	67.35	49.41	-0.55	36.47	20.86	51.84	42.25
RF_OK	-0.21	13.04	9.06	62.08	44.43	-0.18	11.07	7.13	67.54	48.68	-0.62	36.28	20.71	52.33	42.66

GBR; Generalized Boosted Regression, GBR_IDW; Generalized Boosted Regression and Inverse Distance Weighting, GBR_OK; Generalized Boosted Regression and Ordinary Kriging, RF; Random Forest, RF_IDW; Random Forest and Inverse distance Weighting, RF_OK; Random Forest and Ordinary Kriging, ME; Mean error, MAE; Mean absolute error, RMSE; Root mean square error, R²; Coefficient of determination and E₁ = Legates and McCabe's coefficient of efficiency.

The coefficient of efficiency (E₁) exhibited prediction efficiencies varying from 35% to 49% in the upper layers and between 33% and 43% in the subsoil layer. In general, the R² values suggest that approximately 60% of the SOCS variability is explained by the models. The RMSE ranged from 11 to 13 Mg C ha⁻¹ of SOCS in the upper layers and varies between 36 and 39 Mg C ha⁻¹ in the subsoil.

The RF model outperformed the GBR model with an average of 10% improvement on the R² value at each depth. This corroborates with other studies on predicting soil properties and other environmental variables, that consistently show the superiority of RF over GBR (Akpa et al., 2016; Cutler et al., 2007; Deng et al., 2018; Ließ et al., 2012). The performance of the RF model could be ascribed as reported by Akpa et al. (2016), to its capability in detecting and dealing with nonlinear and hierarchical relationships between SOCS and predictive variables. However, Yang et al. (2016) in alpine plateau environment and Wang et al. (2018) in semi-arid rangelands of eastern Australia observed a contradicting trend and showed that, by integrating high-resolution spatial data in the model, GBR could surpass RF performance in predicting SOCS in their respective sites.

4.3.3 Hybridization with OK and IDW

Overall, the combination of RF with OK performed best, although performances are similar. Figure 4.18 shows the empirical variogram (dots) and the fitted variogram model (line) for each soil depth. The nugget to sill ratios exhibited moderate to weak spatial dependence of residual data (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7: Nugget to sill ratios (%) of residual semi-variograms

	Soil depth (cm)		
	0 – 15	15 – 30	30 – 100
GBR	89	70	35
RF	75	75	40

GBR; Generalized Boosted Regression RF; Random Forest

Since the residual spatial correlation is weak, residual kriging did not lead to a large improvement compared to just RGB or RF. Kriging interpolation is known to be powerful when there is a strong spatial autocorrelation. However, in our study, the semi-variogram showed a moderate to weak spatial dependence of residuals.

Figure 4.18: Empirical variograms (dots) and fitted variogram models (line) of residuals for RF and GBRM at various depths.

This is likely due to point data spacing density in some parts of the country where sample points were too far apart to capture the locally occurring spatial autocorrelation since SOCS and other soil parameters usually exhibit short-distance spatial variation as reported by Yemefack et al. (2005). Goidts et al. (2009) also recognized the requirement of the high density of point data distribution to detect the spatial changing pattern as SOCS displays complex variation patterns, from field to global scales. This result suggests the need to densify soil sampling data in Camsodat for both improving the spatial autocorrelation of SOCS and the performance of prediction models. The current dataset could, however, allow the models to capture about 60% of the SOCS variability in the country. The usefulness of legacy data thus confirms that new soil data collection must be cost-prohibitive and justifiable after having made optimal use of earlier collected data (Arrouays et al., 2017).

4.3.4 Variable of importance for SOCS prediction

SOCS modeling in this study has shown a strong dependence on covariates used, leading to fairly accurate performances of prediction models (RF and GBR) with our legacy soil dataset. Each model selected terrain attributes, climate, and vegetation indices as important covariates to predict SOCS. Terrain attributes (elevation; DEM, 46%) and climate variables (Precipitable Water Vapor, PWV; 25%); Rainfall (Rain; 10%) and Temperature (Temp; 8%)) control the GBR prediction outputs with about 89% of their relative influence (Figure 4.19). The RF model integrates the contribution of all covariates at varying and more evenly distributed levels of importance (Figure 4.19). In addition to terrain attributes and climatic variables, vegetation indices (EVI) were also important for prediction with RF. The large spatial heterogeneity of these factors across Cameroon led to a large predicted spatial variation in SOCS.

Random forest and GBR models revealed that environmental factors controlling the variability of SOCS in Cameroon include terrain attributes (elevation, valley bottom flatness) and climate variables (rainfall, precipitable water vapor, and temperature). The influence of these factors on the distribution of SOCS is well known and has also been recognized in other studies at global, regional, and national scales (e.g. Adhikari et al., 2014; Hengl et al., 2017a, 2015; Martin et al., 2011; Wiesmeier et al., 2019). Kempen et al. (2019) reported the influence of elevation and temperature on predicting SOCS for Tanzania. Akpa et al. (2016) also showed the relevance of climate data (precipitation and temperature) on assessing the SOCS distribution in Nigeria using legacy soil data compiled in the Africa Soil Profile database. From more local studies in Cameroon, Silatsa et al. (2015) showed that elevation and climate variables (rainfall,

temperature, and insolation) better contributed to SOCS prediction in the shifting agricultural landscape of Cameroon, while Tsozué et al. (2019) reported changes in SOCS along the elevation gradient on Mount Bambouto, in the West Region of the country.

Figure 4.19: Variables of importance for GBR and RF models

It is well known that precipitation plays a key role in biomass production, which in turn, determines litter input to the soil (Martin et al., 2011). Meanwhile, temperature influences the decomposition of litter in the soil as well as the organic matter mineralization rate. The importance of elevation in SOCS estimation is likely caused by its strong correlation with other factors such as temperature, parent material, and land cover (Chen et al., 2018b). The decrease in temperature with increasing elevation reduces the organic matter decomposition rate, inducing, therefore, an accumulation of SOC (Choudhury et al., 2016). Climate and vegetation in Cameroon vary more or less along the altitudinal gradient. That is why, all over the country, the difference in SOCS spatial distribution between the altitudinal positions is explained well by differences in temperature, which play a major role in the decomposition of deposited residues (Meliyo et al., 2016). However, as suggested by Chen et al. (2018), the contribution of covariates should be treated with caution, as covariates are cross-correlated and high contributing covariates might represent contributions of less contributing covariates.

4.3.5 National SOCS estimate

The spatial distribution pattern of SOCS based on the best prediction model (RF_OK) is shown in Figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Maps of SOCS predictions with lower and upper limits

Maps of the predicted SOCS for the three depth layers show similar spatial patterns of SOCS distribution across the country, exhibiting moderate countrywide variability. From our estimates, half of the total SOCS stored in the top 1 m is in the top 30 cm. This agrees with the 45% and 52%, reported respectively by Batjes (2008) for Central Africa and Henry et al. (2009) for African soils in general. The total values of SOCS in Cameroon were 2.80 Pg and 5.67 Pg for 0 – 30 cm and 0 – 100 cm soil depth, respectively, a bit slightly higher than to the values (2.4 and 5.1 Pg) estimated by Henry et al. (2009) for Cameroon using the HWSD and soil profiles data from Africa. Other studies have also reported the results from Henry et al. (2009) to be realistic estimates of the national SOCS in African countries (Akpa et al., 2016; Kempen et al., 2019).

For Tanzania, the national estimate derived by Henry et al. (2009) was not very different from the one derived from national datasets and advanced statistical modeling (Kempen et al., 2019). This suggests that a modest national soil profile database could provide reasonable countrywide estimates of SOCS and allow a quick update of the carbon stock estimate in African countries with poor soil data infrastructures. However, such studies only provide national estimates, while our approach also produces maps of the spatial distribution of SOCS at a fine spatial resolution as a baseline for sustainable land management and climate change mitigation, from local to the national scale.

4.3.6 Agro-ecological pattern and SOCS distribution

The distribution of SOCS in the two derived layers (0 – 30 and 0 – 100 cm) showed a pronounced trend correlating with the agro-ecological zones (AEZ) across the country. The strong correlation between SOCS density distribution and agro-ecological pattern should also be linked to the influence of climate and elevation as reported by Sreenivas et al. (2014). Change in elevation is also associated with slope processes such as soil erosion (Schwanghart and Jarmer, 2011; Tang et al., 2019), causing spatial heterogeneity of SOCS at different scales. The SOCS gradually increases northwards from the humid forest with a bimodal rainfall agroecological (HFBR) zone in the south up to the high guinea savanna zone (HGSZ). A decreasing feature of SOCS variation then shows the lowest values in the Soudano-Sahelian agro-ecological zone (SSZ) in the far north of the country. It might be explained chiefly by a semi-arid climate that does not favor SOC accumulation (Zhang et al., 2013), and by anthropogenic effects for food crop and cotton productions by a very large population of small-holder farmers. Sreenivas et al. (2014) reported in the semi-arid type of climate in Southern

India an average SOC density ranging between 30 – 40 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 30 cm depth. In this study, we recorded a comparable value of 34.4 Mg C ha⁻¹ at the same depth.

Table 4.8: Mean of SOCS in the agroecological zone

AEZ	Area (×10 ⁶ ha)	SOC stock (Mg ha ⁻¹)			Total storage (Tg)		
		Depth (cm)			Depth (cm)		
		0 – 15	15 - 30	30 – 100	0 - 15	15 - 30	30 - 100
SSZ	9.03	20.68	13.72	36.22	186.89	124.03	237.39
HGSZ	9.26	47.35	38.80	87.45	438.54	303.76	809.85
WHZ	4.01	55.31	40.71	107.85	218.54	160.88	425.90
HFMR	5.90	37.82	22.80	69.20	223.35	134.66	408.67
HFBR	18.17	33.63	21.83	49.69	611.15	396.78	902.92

AEZ; Agroecological zone, SSZ; Soudano-Sahelian zone, HGSZ; High guinea savanna zone, WHZ; Western highland zone, HFMR; Humid forest with monomodal rainfall, HFBR; Humid forest with bimodal rainfall.

The two agroecological zones located in the west of the country (Western highlands zone (WHZ) and humid forest with monomodal rainfall (HFMR)) have the highest SOCS. The Western highlands agro-ecological zone (WHZ), with the highest average SOCS of 96 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 30 cm depth (Table 4.8 and Figure 4.21), has a sub-humid climate and accordingly, the growing period is longer and favors SOC accumulation, which stock is also comparable to the 90 Mg C ha⁻¹ reported by Sreenivas et al. (2014) in a comparable AEZ in India. In addition to SOC accumulation under high elevation and low temperature, humidity and temperature decrease with altitude contribute also to a low rate of SOM decomposition at a higher elevation (Ramifehiarivo et al., 2017). Generally, mean temperature and annual rainfall are usually strongly correlated with SOC accumulation.

Figure 4.21: Average SOCS accumulation by soil depth for all agro-ecological zones

The high Guinea Savanna zone (HGSZ) showed about 86.2 Mg C ha⁻¹ on average stored in the top 30 cm of soil. The elevation of the area varies between 500 and 1500 m above sea level, rainfall ranges between 1500 – 1800 mm, and the mean temperature is 23 °C. The climatic conditions are similar to WHZ. The zone is climatically in transition between WHZ in the west, SSZ in the north, and HFBR in the south. The Humid forest with bimodal rainfall (HFBR) showed an average SOCS of 60 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 0 – 30 cm and 117.4 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 0 – 100 cm, values that corroborate the findings by Akpa et al. (2016) in the humid forest agroecology in Nigeria. Silatsa et al. (2015) estimated the average SOCS under the shifting agricultural landscape of central Cameroon at 0 – 30 cm depth at only 44.5 Mg C ha⁻¹, showing a SOCS loss of about 26%.

Figure 4.22: Predicted SOCS in the top 30 cm (a) and 100 cm (b) of soil in Cameroon

This estimate corroborates the result from Guillaume et al. (2018), who reported a SOCS loss of about 21% after forest conversion into agriculture in the Sumatra-Rainforest, Indonesia. Yemefack et al. (2006) also reported such dynamics of SOC content within the agricultural landscape mosaic systems in the forest area in Cameroon. This leads to conclude, in agreement with Van Noordwijk et al. (1997), that conversion of natural forests to agriculture in the humid

tropics leads to a reduction in ecosystem carbon storage due to the immediate removal of aboveground biomass and a gradual subsequent reduction in SOC. This also confirms the importance of land cover and land use covariates in SOCS predictions. Cameroon has a high diversity of soils within its territory, which is to a large extent explained by the large diversity of parent materials including volcanic deposits and deep deposits of high activity clays (Van Ranst et al., 2019). The observed relationships with AEZs may be further improved by an overlay with the major soils in the country.

Total SOCS in the 1 m soil layer under each AEZ (Table 4.8) showed the following sequence: WHZ (203.9 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HGSZ (173.6 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HFMR (129.8 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HFBR (105.2 Mg C ha⁻¹) > SSZ (70.6 Mg C ha⁻¹). The same trend is maintained for all other soil depths (Table 4.8 and Figure 4.22).

Table 4.9: National and global (HWSD and SoilGrids) estimates of SOCS (Mg C ha⁻¹)

Soil depth (cm)	This study					SoilGrids						HWSD						
	Min	Mean	Max	CV	Total*	Min	Mean	Max	CV	Total	POD ⁺	Min	Mean	Max	CV	Total	PUD ⁻	
0 – 15	06.2	36.2	108.1	35	1679	0.0	44.2	302.0	41	2045	22							
15 – 30	03.9	24.2	107.4	41	1121	0.0	26.5	275.0	53	1225	9							
30 – 100	09.5	62.1	276.4	47	2875	0.0	65.7	1244.0	91	2990	4	0.00	38.0	165.5	42	1782	38	
0 – 30	11.1	60.4	210.1	37	2799	0.0	72.0	571.0	45	3213	15	0.00	43.9	185.2	41	2059	26	
0 – 100	21.3	122.5	467.9	41	5674	0.0	136.3	1815.0	66	6203	9	0.00	82.0	327.3	39	3841	31	

* Total values are expressed in Tg, with 1Tg = 10¹² g; ⁺ Percentage of overestimated difference; ⁻ Percentage of underestimated difference.

The predicted SOCS shows a similar trend as the original data (Table 4.9). A total of about 5.67 Pg of SOCS is contained in the first meter of soil in Cameroon, of which 50% is stored in the top 30 cm soil layer (Table 4.9).

4.3.7 National versus global SOCS estimations

Our national SOCS predictions were compared with the two most often used national SOCS estimates from global products SoilGrids (Hengl et al., 2017a) and the Harmonized World Soil Database (Wieder et al., 2014). National SOCS estimate was in between the two global estimates (Table 4.9), following the generally reported trend that HWSD underestimates while SoilGrids overestimates SOCS (Henry et al., 2009; Liang et al., 2019; Mulder et al., 2016; Tifafi et al., 2018) (Figure 4.23).

Figure 4.23: Gap between national and global SOCS estimates

In addition to estimation errors in the order of 30% at the scale of the African continent, HWSD data on SOCS map makes use of look-up tables assigning SOCS values to specific soil polygons, ignoring the fact that SOCS is not constant within a soil polygon, but varies with environmental covariates (McBratney et al., 2003; Liang et al., 2019). The SOCS overestimation of SoilGrids may be explained by the limited number of soil profiles (Mulder et al., 2016c). SoilGrids was calibrated using some 150,000 soil profiles from around the world, with only a small portion (461 points) from Cameroon. Moreover, data distribution for SoilGrids was clustered towards the South of Cameroon, with very few observation points in the North. In this study, we used 1 432 points, with a relatively better spread across the country. Thus, a better inventory and harmonization of soil profile data, combined with relevant environmental covariates included in the spatial prediction, will have contributed to better predict SOCS in this study.

As for almost all national estimates of SOCS, the prediction accuracy of the results reported here was constrained by the limited number of available SOCS profile observations and their inconsistent distribution across Cameroon. There were also variations in the time of observation (most of the samples were taken in different periods) and differences in laboratory analysis procedures, as the samples were analysed in different laboratories using different laboratory

methods. The reliability of the estimates could further be increased by expanding the input data. Likewise, all relevant soil-forming factors were not included for spatial modeling, since not all could be represented by generally available, high-resolution covariates for Cameroon. Future work should address how these other factors could contribute to improving SOCS mapping in Cameroon.

4.4 SOIL ASSESSMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE COCOA PRODUCTION

4.4.1 Comparative analysis of SOCS dynamics under fallow and cocoa systems

4.4.1.1 Carbon stocks in fallow and CAF systems

Soil organic carbon stock (mean and standard error) in both systems (fallow and CAF) are shown in Table 4.10. The sample size required for cocoa dynamic assessment was higher likely because of the management differences between the two systems. Indeed, as fallows are abandoned pieces of land with no or just little human activities, cocoa farms, on the contrary, need a lot of human activities all over the year. Accordingly, the management of the cocoa plot might vary from one plot to another inducing a high soil variability. This is the reason why the sample size for the cocoa system is almost twice the number required for fallow system assessment. The mean carbon stock gradually increases from 33 Mg C ha⁻¹ in cropland to 57 Mg C ha⁻¹ in the secondary forest for fallow and 62 Mg C ha⁻¹ for CAF systems. It should be emphasized that SOCS in our study was only estimated for the top 30 cm of soil. Chiti et al. (2014) reported similar results from Ghana after 34 years under CAF. Our values are lower than those reported from Indonesia (Smiley and Kroschel, 2008) and Brazil (Gama-Rodrigues et al., 2010), likely because these studies explored the SOCS at 100 cm soil depth.

Table 4.10: Soil organic carbon stock (Mg C ha⁻¹) in a chrono-sequence of fallow systems

	Initial stage	Fallow system			
	CL	YF	BF	TF	SF
Soil (30 cm)	33.1 (5.1)	35.6 (4.5)	40.3 (2.4)	42.2 (3.2)	56.6 (6.2)
<i>N</i>	5	13	13	10	22
	Initial stage	CAF system			
	CL	YCo	MCo	OCo	VCo
Soil (30 cm)	33.1 (5.1)	39.1 (5.3)	43.7 (4.9)	45.3 (4.8)	62.4 (7.6)
<i>N</i>	5	20	17	19	28

CL = Crop Land; YF = Young fallow; BF = Bush fallow; TF = tree fallow; SF = Secondary forest; YCo = young cocoa; MCo = mature cocoa; OCo = Old cocoa; VCo = Very old cocoa. Values in parentheses indicate standard errors. *n* is the number of plot sampled

4.4.1.2 SOCS accretion functions

The logistic model (LM) provided the best-fit model for describing the SOCS accumulation for both systems (Table 4.11). It is one of the more popular equations used to model real-life quantities whose growth levels off because of the rate of growth decrease over time to the extent growth levels off (Forys and Marciniak-Czochra, 2003; Matis and Al-Muhammed, 2010). Here, the logistic growth function grows quickly at first, and then more slowly and finally levels off.

To the left of its point of maximum growth (PMG), defined by $(\frac{\ln b}{c}; \frac{a}{2})$, the rate of C sequestration in the system increases with time, while to the right of its PMG, this rate decreases with time.

Table 4.11: Mathematical model and function defining SOCS accretion in the systems.

Systems	Models	Parameters				R ²	S _E	P(t)
		<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>			
Fallow system	<i>LM</i>	78.01	1.31	0.02	-	0.79	6.29	0.00 (5.2)
CAF system	<i>LM</i>	111.7	2.05	0.02	-	0.75	6.7	

Logistic growth function (LM) [$C = a/(1 + be^{-cx})$] best fitted the SOCS accretion. C = carbon stock (Mg ha⁻¹)
S_E = Standard error; R² = Coefficient of determination; *a*, *b*, *c* and *d* are function parameters. P = probability, *t* =Independent t-test value; x = time (year)

Parameters of functions defining the SOCS accretion in soil systems are shown in Table 4.11. The sequences of SOCS accumulation were best fitted with coefficients of determination (R²) 0.79 and 0.75 for fallow and cocoa systems respectively. The trend of SOCS accumulation in the chrono-sequences of fallow and CAF systems is shown on the curves (Figure 4.24). The shape of the curves was similar for the two systems. However, the SOCS accretion was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in the CAF system throughout the referred period as compared to the fallow system (Figure 4.24).

Figure 4.24: Curves (LM) of soil C stock accretion (30 cm depth) in the systems

4.4.1.3 Trend of SOCS accretion in the systems

Application of the logistic growth functions illustrated a general trend of SOCS accretion in both CAF and fallow systems. This highlights that there is an accelerated increase in C accumulation during the first successive stages, followed by a decrease and stabilization at advanced stages of succession, approaching equilibrium and stability. The same structure was also observed by Fonseca et al. (2011) in Costa Rica, and by Kenzo et al. (2010), using a logarithmic function in a secondary tropical rainforest in Malaysia.

The growth rate coefficients (GC) of SOCS sequestration in different systems are summarized in Table 4.12. The PMG rate in the fallow system is reached after 14 years and up to 36 years in the CAF system (Table 4.12). The coefficient of the maximum growth rate at PMG varies from 0.4 to 0.56 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ respectively for fallow and CAF. This indicates a quick accumulation of SOCS in the two systems, which is then followed by a gradually decreasing SOCS accumulation rate.

Table 4.12: SOCS accretion rates (Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) as derived from the functions

Systems	Years						At PMG	
	1	7	at PMG	25	45	50	YPMG	C stock
Fallow	0.39	0.39	0.40	0.38	0.34	0.32	14	39
CAF	0.49	0.51	0.56	0.55	0.55	0.54	36	56

PMG = Point of maximum growth; YPMG = Year at the Point of maximum growth; n.e = not estimated

Our rates of SOCS accretion ranging from 0.38 to 0.55 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ at 25 years (Table 4.12) are lower than those reported by Fonseca et al. (2011) from secondary humid tropical forests in Costa Rica (1.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). As plant species differ in their potentials for improving soil quality, the difference in accretion rates may reflect the differences in the floristic composition of the fallows between these geographic locations.

Our study corroborates that of Yemefack et al. (2006), reporting that SOC accumulation remained significantly higher over a longer period in the CAF system as compared to fallow systems within the shifting agricultural landscape of Cameroon. The times required for 80% SOCS recovery after forest clearing for food crops (25 and 10 years, respectively in CAF and fallow systems) found by (Yemefack et al., 2006b) is comparable to the leveling off time obtained in this study. As these studies were conducted in different areas within the humid forest zone of Cameroon, the compatibility of the results suggests a common behavior of SOCS recovery throughout the Congo forest basin for CAF and fallow systems. These results support

the use of CAF systems as a viable option for enhancing long-term SOCS recovery after shifting agriculture (Nounamo and Yemefack, 2001; Yemefack et al., 2006b).

The optimum fallow period required for soil recovery after shifting agriculture appears to be around 12 (Nounamo and Yemefack, 2001) to 14 (this study) years for this region. The greater SOC accumulation in CAF throughout the modeling period (50 years) as compared to fallow reflects the difference in management. To maintain productivity in the CAF system, understory vegetation is cut yearly, which along with harvest residue (husks from the cocoa pods) is left in place as mulch. These inputs are assumed to play an important role in improving soil C and bulk density (Yemefack et al., 2006b).

As reported by Duguma et al. (2001) for biodiversity conservation, CAF systems remain environmentally sustainable for up to 50 years, at a level comparable to long-term fallow. Our study demonstrated a similar comparison between CAF and fallow systems for C sequestration potentials. Moreover, the benefits of using CAF systems as climate-smart production strategies have been reported in other publications (George et al., 2012; Saj et al., 2013; Schroth et al., 2013). Both crop yields and SOC sequestration have the potential to be increased through better design and management (Magne et al., 2014; Somarriba et al., 2013). The findings from our study, along with these other reports, support an expanded use and management of CAF systems as a REDD+ mechanism for emission reduction; especially as CAF can serve as versatile production systems; producing supplementary products (such as cash, fruits and/or medicines) that further improve local livelihoods (Bisseleua, 2007).

If additional payment can be generated to the farmers for additional SOCS storage, the establishment of such CAF systems on the current fallow lands may contribute to reducing the new expansion of perennial plantations into primary forest lands. This would be a suitable alternative for implementing the current rural development strategy of cocoa farms extension (by fifty thousand hectares) in this area where the current observed field expansion (194 ha per year) is happening at the expense of primary forest clearance (Yemefack et al., 2013).

4.4.2 Soil properties distribution and suitability for cocoa production

4.4.2.1 Statistical summary of soil properties in the cocoa production area

The spatial location of the soil profiles is illustrated in figure 4.25. The distribution of samples does not equitably cover the study area. There is respectively area with high, medium and low sample densities. However, major spots of cocoa-growing areas are spatially covered.

Figure 4.25: Spatial location of sampling sites in the cocoa production area

Table 4.13 shows the summary statistics of soil properties data computed from the topsoil layer (0 – 15 cm). Apart from clay (CV = 47%), all the others soil properties are highly variables (with CV > 50%). This is consistent with Adeniyi (2019) who reported soils to generally possess high variability in macronutrient properties in similar areas. This can also be explained by the high biophysical diversity of cocoa production areas in Cameroon. Indeed, cocoa production in Cameroon is conducted within three contrasting agroecological zones. The soil properties

variability is expected to increase in such a large and diverse sampling area (Momtaz et al., 2009; Waswa et al., 2013).

Table 4.13: Summary statistics of soil properties in the cocoa production area at 15 cm

	SOC (g/kg)	N	P (mg/kg)	Ca	CEC (cmol kg ⁻¹)	K	Mg	pH H ₂ O	Sand	Silt (%)	Clay
Min	0.85	0.12	0.01	0.01	2.60	0.01	0.01	3.21	0.15	1.00	0.75
Mean	29.40	2.29	10.38	3.27	17.47	0.33	1.53	5.09	43.75	21.97	34.27
Median	21.67	1.74	6.00	1.83	13.26	0.19	0.83	5.10	46.37	17.20	33.00
Max	217.37	22.39	172.74	28.74	82.06	4.04	19.56	9.61	92.78	84.00	82.79
CV	86.42	87.39	148.56	123.20	69.26	135.80	129.20	14.55	49.35	69.14	46.84
SD	25.40	2.00	15.42	4.03	12.10	0.45	1.97	0.74	21.59	15.19	16.05
N	931	915	698	897	746	902	891	927	895	895	895

SD = standard deviation; CV = Coefficient of variation; N = Sample size

Overall, these soils are slightly acidic (average pH = 5.09). This may have resulted in leaching from high rainfall, organic acid formation, and also from the oxidation of sulfidic material as was reported by Tabi et al. (2012). The average textural composition of the soils is sandy loam with mean sand, silt, and clay fractions of 43.75%, 21.97, and 34.27, respectively. Exchangeable Ca content ranged from 0.01 – 28.74 cmol kg⁻¹, while Mg and K ranged between 0.01 – 19.56 and 0.01 – 4.04 cmol kg⁻¹, respectively (Table 4.13). With an average of 3.27 cmol kg⁻¹, Ca was the dominant cation. This was followed by Mg and K with average concentrations of 1.53 and 0.33 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively.

Organic C and total N contents of soils ranged between 0.85 – 217.37 g kg⁻¹ and 0.12 – 22.39%, respectively. The mean total nitrogen (0.23 %) is slightly higher than the world average (0.18%) (Singh et al., 2019). Available P content in the soils ranged from 0.01 to 172.74 ppm, with a mean value of 10.38 ppm and a marked variability across the area. This also showed that the mean available P content is below the reported optimum value, in agreement with other studies (Kongor et al., 2019). The cation exchange capacity ranged from 2.6 to 82.6 cmol kg⁻¹ with an average of 17.47 cmol kg⁻¹. Based on the median value, the data revealed that 50% of the soils in the area are with CEC ≥ 13.26 cmol kg⁻¹ (Table 4.13). This is similar to the average CEC values in cocoa producing areas in Ghana (CEC ≥ 13.26 cmol kg⁻¹) as reported by (Kongor et al., 2019).

Figure 4.26 illustrates histogram of soil properties distribution in the cocoa production area in Cameroon. Several properties such as OC, CEC, Exchangeable basis (Ca, K, Mg) and N, P, and Silt showed a positive skewness, while Clay, pH, and Sand expressed distributions close to the normal.

Figure 4.26: Histogram of soil properties distribution in the cocoa production area

4.4.2.2 Correlation between soil properties

SOC was positively correlated with CEC ($r = 0.67$, $p < 0.001$) and total N ($r = 0.75$; $p < 0.001$) (Figure 4.27). These correlations were expected because these properties are related to the amount of organic matter in the soil (Kahle et al., 2002; Takoutsing et al., 2013). Calcium was positively correlated with CEC ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$), K ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$), Mg ($r = 0.74$, $p <$

0.001), total N ($r = 0.2$, $p < 0.001$), Available P ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$), and pH ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$). Cation exchange capacity was positively correlated with almost all soil properties likely because most of the soil chemical properties depend on the CEC values as Takoutsing et al. (2016b) reported in the humid forest zone of Cameroon. On the other hand, negative correlations were found between sand and clay ($r = -0.75$; $p < 0.001$), as well as for sand and OC ($r = -0.30$, $p < 0.001$), CEC ($r = -0.31$, $p < 0.001$), K ($r = -0.30$, $p < 0.001$). Most of these correlations trend was also reported in Nigeria and Ghana respectively by Adeniyi (2019) and Kongor et al. (2018) in cocoa production areas. Clay was negatively correlated with almost all the soil properties as was reported in the western highlands (Takoutsing et al., 2016a).

Figure 4.27: Correlation between soil properties

4.4.2.3 Models fitting and variables of importance

The model fitting and cross-validation results for target soil properties are shown in table 4.14. For most of the soil properties, successful models were fitted using the current set of covariates with R^2 at cross-validation points ranging from 19 to 61%. The concordance coefficient varied between 10 and 37%. Our model explained 61% of the variation for the prediction of CEC.

Similar results were observed in other studies (Chagas et al., 2018; Gallo et al., 2018; Ghaemi et al., 2013). The RMSE for K (0.58), Mg (0.33), and Ca (1.77) were reported in a field-scale soil assessment in Russia (Aşkın et al., 2012). Likewise, Li et al. (2019) showed that the prediction performance was scale-dependent at field level and required a high-density sample to better express the variability in soil Ca and Mg distribution. In China, Zhou et al. (2019) and Gu et al. (2018) obtained a similar R^2 (57% and 51% respectively) while predicting the soil total Nitrogen. For P prediction, while being the worst, our R^2 estimate (19%) was slightly higher than that reported by Hengl et al. (2017) at the sub-Saharan African level (12%). This reveals the complexity of mapping available phosphorus in African soils. These soil properties are affected by several factors, including those related to the origin and nature of soil parent materials, slope position, and water movement within the soil. Accuracy of their spatial predictions could be improved by investing in new and/or more detailed covariates (Hengl et al., 2017) as they become available.

Table 4.14: Target soil properties results of model fitting and cross-validation

	OC	Ca	CEC	Clay	K	Mg	N	P	pH	Sand	Silt
R^2	60.33	39.57	60.52	37.45	37.50	41.42	52.25	18.76	53.32	48.87	58.77
RMSE	17.89	3.38	8.50	13.66	0.33	1.63	1.52	14.72	0.55	16.87	10.86
E_1	35.41	20.46	37.46	19.16	19.13	20.48	31.18	10.05	28.23	26.09	34.58
MAE	11.33	2.20	33.89	10.47	0.21	1.01	0.91	7.25	0.42	13.09	7.83

The model-fitting results show that the most important predictors (Table 4.15) of investigated soil properties are usually climatic variables (precipitation and temperature, cloud cover), terrain parameters (DEM, Slope, valley bottom flatness, negative and positive topographic index, Topographic wetness index, valley depth) and land cover (Enhanced vegetation index, Global land cover). The order of importance varies from one soil property to another with the main trend in the order climate > Terrain attribute > Landcover. A similar trend was reported by Hengl et al. (2017b) while predicting soil nutrients in the whole sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 4.15: Topmost important covariates per soil properties

Properties	Most important covariates
OC	PWV, Precip2, LST3, DEM, LST, Cloud1, LFM, Rain, Precip1, VBF, Cloud2, Lith, GLC2, Slope, LST2
Ca	Cloud1, Cloud2, Precip2, DEM, LST2, Precip1, LFM, GLC2, EVI1, PWV, LST, LST3, Rain, Vdepth, TWI
CEC	PWV, DEM, LST3, LST, Precip2, Lith, Cloud1, Cloud2, Rain, Precip1, EVI1, NTO, VBF, EVI2, LFM
Clay	PWV, Cloud1, DEM, Cloud2, Precip2, EVI2, GLC1, LST3, Vdepth, Rain, LTC, LST, Precip1, EVI1, PTO
K	PWV, Cloud1, DEM, Cloud2, Precip2, EVI2, GLC2, LST3, Vdepth, Rain, LTC, LST, Precip1, EVI1, PTO
Mg	Cloud1, Precip2, Cloud2, DEM, Precip1, LST2, EVI1, Rain, PWV, Vdepth, LST, LST3, TWI, Lith, GLC2
N	Cloud1, Precip2, Cloud2, DEM, Precip1, LST2, EVI1, Rain, PWV, Vdepth, LST, LST3, TWI, Lith, GLC2
P	Cloud1, Precip2, Cloud2, DEM, Precip1, LST2, EVI1, Rain, PWV, Vdepth, LST, LST3, TWI, Lith, GLC2
pH	Cloud1, Precip2, Cloud2, LST, LST2, LFM, LTC, PWV, DEM, Precip1, LST3, Precip, GLC1, RED, Lith
Sand	Cloud1, Precip2, Cloud2, LST, LST2, LFM, LTC, PWV, DEM, Precip1, LST3, Precip, GLC1, RED, Lith
Silt	LST, DEM, Precip2, PWV, Cloud1, LFM, LST2, Rain, LST3, Precip1, Cloud2, GLC1, Vdepth, LTC, EVI1

4.4.2.4 Soil pH distribution and suitability

The topsoil pH distribution map (Figure 4.28) illustrates the pH variation in the cocoa production area. The pH ranged from 3.5 to 7.8 representing different levels of suitability and indicating that the soils are mostly acidic. There is a gradient of soil pH values, increasing from the South towards the North, and varying from very strong to moderately acidic. There is also neutral tendency of pH in the east, which could be justified by the high concentration of calcium in that area (section 4.4.2.5). The soil pH suitability (Figure 4.29) is mainly moderate ($5 \leq \text{pH} \leq 6$) and marginal ($\text{pH} < 5$) for cocoa production. About 35% of the study area is highly suitable; 62% is moderately suitable, and only 3% marginally suitable. As soils are acidic, they usually pose a problem for macronutrient uptake for cocoa plants, such as available phosphorus (P), which becomes unavailable. Halving et al. (2005), reported pH values less than 6 to affect and limit the availability of essential macronutrient elements, while Ajiboye et al. (2011) showed that, pH values above 6 may as well limit the availability of micronutrients such as Fe, Zn, Mn, and Cu, although the second option is not applicable in our case.

Figure 4.28: Soil pH distribution in the cocoa production area

Phytotoxic concentrations of micronutrients (Al, Mn) were also reported to occur in acidic soils and the major nutrients (basic cations) on the other hand, become less available for cocoa plants when the soil becomes too acidic (Buggenhout, 2018). These observations illustrate the preponderant role of soil pH for soil fertility management in cocoa systems. Thus, soil pH reported in our area of interest may limit the availability of macronutrients, as the soil is mostly acidic. Acid soils are known to have low fertility, due to a combination of mineral toxicities (aluminum and manganese) and deficiencies (phosphorus, calcium, magnesium). Nonetheless, Buggenhout (2018), observed that cocoa is more tolerant of soil acidity than many other tropical crops. Cocoa was also earlier reported to grow in a variable range of soil pH which may fall between very acid (pH 5) to very alkaline (pH 8) (Ibiremo et al., 2010).

The marginal pH suitability area is likely to exhibit Aluminum toxicity, which is a major constraint for crop production on acid soil if soil pH values fall below 5.5 (Hede et al., 2001). This was also reported to be the main cause of low cocoa yield on acid soils (Baligar and

Fageria, 2005). By varying the level of soil Aluminum saturations on cocoa trees, Baligar and Fageria (2005) showed that higher soil Aluminum saturations reduced root biomass and root length and such reduction might have contributed to a reduced nutrient influx of slow diffusing cations such as Ca, Mg and to some extent K beside the root-soil interphase. Additional analyzes of Ribeiro et al. (2013) allowed to understand that, increasing Al concentration decreased photosynthetic rate, stomatal conductance, and leaf transpiration rate of the cocoa tree. In agreement with Shamsuddin et al. (2004), and at odds with Buggenhout (2018) these are pieces of evidence that cocoa is very sensitive to soil acidity.

Figure 4.29: Soil pH suitability

The acidity of the soil for cocoa production should, therefore, be addressed to straighten the yield curve. Several options are possible. Application of lime is the most used and recommended option (Baligar et al., 2006; Delhaise and Ryan, 1995; Hede et al., 2001). However, it is often not economically or physically feasible as was reported by Hede et al. (2001). The usage of the organic amendment has also been successfully tried for the correction

of soil acidity in cocoa production (Shamshuddin et al., 2004). This approach requires an abundance of organic materials at affordable costs, which is practically difficult to obtain currently in Cameroon. The development of toxic elements-tolerant cocoa cultivars seems to be an option on which research might have to invest.

4.4.2.5 Soil exchangeable calcium (Ca) distribution and suitability

In general, soils assessed have low exchangeable calcium content (Mean = 3.69 and median = 3.37). A slightly variable distribution is observed throughout the area, with some spots of relatively high concentration (Figure 4.30). In the south-east of the area, for example, a high concentration of soil exchangeable calcium is noticed and coincides with the area under limestone deposit at Mintom (Caron et al., 2010). This suggests that the calcium deposit would have a direct significant influence on topsoil properties in the area. This hypothesis nevertheless requires further investigations for its verification, to exploit this calcium reserve for agricultural purposes, as we highlighted in the previous section (section 4.4.2.4) to correct soil acidity.

Figure 4.30: Soil Exchangeable Calcium (Ca) distribution in the cocoa production area

Exchangeable Calcium suitability (Figure 4.30) is mainly moderate ($3 \leq \text{Ca} [\text{mol/kg}] \leq 6$) and marginal ($\text{Ca} [\text{mol/kg}] < 3$) for cocoa production in Cameroon. This study shows that 55% of

the area is moderately suitable; 42% is marginally suitable, and only 3% highly suitable. Exchangeable calcium was reported to be among the most variable soil properties in the shifting agricultural landscape of Cameroon (Ngo-Mbogba et al., 2015). Moreover, Tamfuh et al. (2018) noticed a very low and low Ca content ($1.43 - 3.6 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) in the mountainous ecosystem of North-West Cameroon, which however was reported not limiting for annual crop production in the area (Tellen and Yerima, 2018). This suggests that cocoa is likely more calcium demanding than annual crops. Similarly, the proportions of exchangeable calcium were rated low to moderate in the cocoa production area South-Western of Nigeria by Ahukaemere (2018). Likewise, Ibiremo et al. (2010) also reported Calcium values below the critical threshold in the cocoa production area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Although Ibiremo et al. (2011) found adequate exchangeable calcium content for cocoa production in Adamaoua State Nigeria, there seems to be a critical concern of exchangeable calcium in cocoa-producing areas. As suggested by Adeoye and Agboola (1985), an application of calcium fertilizer or calcium-enriched fertilizer would be required to upgrade the Ca level.

Figure 4.31: Exchangeable Calcium (Ca) suitability

Calcium is made available to plants by the dissolution of Calcium-rich minerals or in the long term through weathering of primary minerals such as feldspars and micas. Calcium deficiency

can lead to the death of a growing point for the cocoa plant in extreme situations, or may also cause blossoms and buds to drop prematurely as observed for many other plants (Taylor and Locascio, 2004). Low exchangeable Calcium content in the soil as reported in this study often implies acidity problems, with low base saturation. Therefore, as long as acidic pH problems are corrected and managed, Calcium supply will be sustainably maintained and at amounts more than removed with crop harvest. Our result reinforces the inclusion of calcium oxide in the formulation of special cocoa fertilizer in many countries such as Cameroon (6 N – 15 P₂O₂ – 28 K₂O + 6 CaO + 3 MgO), Ivory Coast (0 N – 15 P₂O₂ – 14 K₂O + 28 CaO + 5.5 S + 2.5 MgO + 0.9 Zn + 0.24 B₂O₃), and Ghana (0 N – 22 P₂O₂ – 18 K₂O + 9 CaO + 7S + 6 MgO). However, this formulation has the weakness of not considering the spatial variability of soil Calcium as we reported in this study. There is, therefore, a need to contextualize the formulation of cocoa fertilizers in Cameroon by taking into account the inherent soil variability.

4.4.2.6 Soil exchangeable magnesium (Mg) distribution and suitability

Exchangeable magnesium is the fraction of the magnesium held by clay particles and organic matter in the soil. The spatial distribution of Mg (Figure 4.32) majoritarilly exhibited moderate Mg content (1 – 3 cmol kg⁻¹) in the coca production area (Mean = 1.34 cmol kg⁻¹ and Median = 1.23 cmol kg⁻¹) according to the classification of (Hazelton and Murphy, 2007). Gransee and Führs (2013) suggested two main reasons for exchangeable magnesium deficiency to occur in soils: Absolute deficiency and cation competition. They further explained that absolute deficiency can be a consequence of (i) Low Mg contents in the source rocks, (ii) Mg losses from the soil e.g. by mobilization and subsequent leaching, and (ii) Long-term unbalanced crop fertilization practice neglecting Mg depletion of soils through crop Mg removal. Cation competition is a consequence of nutrient imbalances in soils, as the uptake of Mg is strongly influenced by the availability of other cations like NH⁴⁺, Ca²⁺, and K⁺ (Jacoby, 1961). Thereby, magnesium deficiencies generally occur when the other cations dominate the soil exchange complex along with low Mg concentrations.

Magnesium is one of the vital nutrients required by cocoa for optimum growth and maximum yield (Aikpokpodion et al., 2015). One of the magnesium's well-known roles is in the photosynthesis process, as it is a building block of the Chlorophyll, which makes leaves appear green.

Figure 4.32: Soil Exchangeable Magnesium (Mg) distribution

Thus, Magnesium deficiency might be a significant limiting factor in cocoa production. Magnesium being the only cation in chlorophyll is at the core center of the molecule and it is an essential ingredient for healthy plants (Gransee and Führs, 2013). Furthermore, soil texture has also influence on the level of available magnesium in soils. For example, clayey soils generally contain adequate magnesium for plant requirements, whereas sandy soils are frequently magnesium-deficient. However, the general concern is that many soils are too low in available magnesium to sustain intensive cropping without the use of magnesium fertilizers (Metson, 1974).

Exchangeable magnesium suitability (Figure 4.33) is mainly marginal ($3 \leq \text{Mg} [\text{mol/kg}]$) for cocoa production in Cameroon covering 97% of the area. There are some few spots with moderate suitability ($3 < \text{Mg} [\text{mol/kg}] \leq 6$) and very few with high suitability. Many studies reported exchangeable magnesium deficiency to be common in tropical and sub-tropical soils (Aikpokpodion et al., 2015; Hailes et al., 1997).

Figure 4.33: Exchangeable Magnesium (Mg) suitability

Ibiremo et al. (2010) and Ahukaemere (2018) found soil Mg values far below the critical value in the cocoa production area in Nigeria. Buggenhout (2018) also reported exchangeable magnesium to be mainly beneath the minimum in Sao-Tomé. In Cameroon, Mg was reported low and within the topmost variable soil properties in the shifting agricultural landscape of Cameroon from (Ngo-Mbogba et al., 2015), while Tamfuh et al. (2018) highlighted a low Mg content ($0.39 - 1.5 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) in the North-West region. Tellen and Yerima (2018) and Takoutsing et al. (2016b) did not find a significant difference in Mg content between land use types in the western highlands. It could simply be ascribed to the generally low level of available Mg, also as it is highly sensitive with rainfall which is high in the study area. The relatively low Mg in cultivated systems was attributed to their continuous removal with crop harvest, and soil erosion could also account for the lower Mg content in cultivated systems. Considering the vital role of magnesium in plant nutrition, its application is recommended in cocoa plantations as its more often limiting. Our result thus justifies and corroborates the inclusion of Magnesium oxide in the special cocoa fertilizer in Cameroon ($6 \text{ N} - 15 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 28 \text{ K}_2\text{O} + 6 \text{ CaO} + 3 \text{ MgO}$). Likewise, Jadin and Snoeck (1985) found a strong Mg deficit in cocoa soils of Côte d'Ivoire (Jadin and Snoeck, 1985). They advised Mg to be applied either as dolomite (if calcium is also

required) or kieserite (magnesium sulphate). Fertilizers enriched with Mg were also formulated in Ivory Coast ($0\text{ N} - 15\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 14\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 28\text{ CaO} + 5.5\text{ S} + 2.5\text{ MgO} + 0.9\text{ Zn} + 0.24\text{ B}_2\text{O}_3$), and Ghana ($0\text{ N} - 22\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 18\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 9\text{ CaO} + 7\text{ S} + 6\text{ MgO}$). Site adsorption capacity of magnesium is a prerequisite and must precede magnesium application to the soil as was recommended by Gransee and Führs (2013) to avoid unnecessary applications.

4.4.2.7 Soil exchangeable potassium (K) distribution and suitability

The spatial distribution of exchangeable potassium (K) (Figure 4.34) showed low ($0.2 - 0.3\text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) potassium content in the area (Mean = 0.28 cmol kg^{-1} and Median = 0.25 cmol kg^{-1}) based on the classification after Hazelton and Murphy (2007). Our result agrees with contradicting observations from the literature on soil exchangeable potassium in other countries.

Figure 4.34: Soil Exchangeable Potassium (K) distribution in the cocoa production area

Indeed, Ogunlade et al. (2012) reported K to be among the major soil constraint for cocoa production in some Nigerian cocoa growing-area, while Buggenhout (2018) observed topsoil K concentrations mostly above the soil minimum in Sao-Tomé. The former finding is consistent with the views expressed by Ipinmoroti et al. (2005) in which K was not at a deficient level in

Oyo state Nigeria. Exchangeable potassium deficiency was reported on about 30% of soils in the western region and 90% of soils in the southern region (Ngachie, 1992). Higher K values were recorded in soil under cocoa plantation and mixed cropping in the Southern Cameroon, likely because of the practice of slash and burn agriculture (Takoutsing et al., 2016b). Likewise, Tellen and Yerima (2018) observed high K concentrations under protected forest.

Exchangeable potassium suitability for cocoa production was classified 59% moderately suitable, 33% highly suitable, and 8% marginally suitable (Figure 4.35). High K levels in the soil usually express high K stocks in vegetation and subsequent litter (Hartemink, 2005). This is likely because K is not linked to organic compounds in the plant, and can easily be released from decaying straw, becoming available for crops (Rosolem et al., 2005). To speed up the process of decomposition, the role of exchangeable potassium on soil microbial activity stimulation in tropical systems remains not well established. Mori et al. (2019) observed that K was not limiting for soil microbial activity in the Chinese subtropical forest ecosystems. The action of potassium on microbial stimulation in the humid tropical climate remains undetermined and could significantly change because of the heterogeneity of tropical forest ecosystems.

Figure 4.35: Exchangeable Potassium (K) suitability

The only source of potassium in the soil apart from fertilizers is the primary minerals rich in potassium (feldspars, muscovites, etc.) in which K is characterized by activation energy greater than 15 Kcal/mole (Pedro, 1973). This is why only strongly hydrolyzing climates, like hot and humid climates, are then likely to release potassium. Melo et al. (2001) noticed highly weathered kaolinitic tropical soils in Brazil to often have adequate levels of K to support plant growth. However, a large amount of K is lost through leaching in the soils and the nutrient holding capacity is low (Hartemink, 2003b) in tropical systems. Furthermore, Hartemink (2005) reported that K loss due to rain wash under cocoa ecosystems might vary from 38 to more than 100 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. This could be the reason why the accumulation of potassium was reported to be low in cocoa ecosystems. Likewise, Van Villet et al. (2015) noticed that under high rainfall conditions, K effect should be better evaluated through plant analysis since most of K is stored in cocoa and shade tree biomass rather than in soils.

When potassium fertilization is necessary, it should take into consideration the dose, timing, and method of application to minimize losses, as well as to avoid depletion of K thereby ensuring an increase in yield per unit K applied to the soil (Bernardi et al., 2013). Therefore, because of the considerable leaching potential, splitting the applications of K is an important management strategy to minimize losses and improve the efficiency of K used in tropical soil with small clay contents (Rosolem and Steiner, 2017). Potassium chloride coated with humic acids is a good alternative source of K in low CEC soils with very low K levels when applied in a single application at planting, as opposed to regular KCl that must be split (Rosolem et al., 2005). We should also raise attention to the fact that in many soils, it is generally recognized that the response of the crop to K and applied K fertilizer can be affected by many factors, such as climate, water deficit and limiting nutrient supply other than K (Bar-Yosef et al., 2015). Various levels of potassium doses are generally considered in the formulation of generic cocoa fertilizers in several cocoa producing countries.

4.4.2.8 Soil organic carbon (SOC) distribution and suitability

The topsoil Organic carbon (OC) distribution map (Figure 4.36) illustrates the OC variation in the cocoa production area. The OC ranged from 2 to 200 g kg⁻¹ representing variable levels of suitability. Climate (PWV, precipitation, and land surface temperature) and elevation (DEM) variables controlled the distribution of OC distribution in the area. Accordingly, there is a high SOC concentration along the highlands and the high rainfall areas (Tsozué et al., 2019). Tematio et al. (2004) noticed the presence of organic matter-rich andosols (80 – 230 g kg⁻¹) in

the upper part of the massif that extends between 2 000 and 2 740 m altitude around the Mount Bambouto. Spots of high OC concentrations are also identified along the rivers throughout the area (Sanaga, Nyong, etc..).

Figure 4.36: Soil organic carbon (OC) distribution in the cocoa production area

In general, low OC is a reflection of poor recycling of organic matter as well as the loss of oxidized organic matter from the soil as was observed in Nigeria (Ahukaemere, 2018). The result of the analysis shows that 52% of the study area is highly suitable; 36% is moderately suitable, and 12% marginally suitable for cocoa production in the area (Figure 4.37). Buggenhout, (2018) reported topsoil to be well furnished (above the optimum values) in OC in Sao-Tomé cocoa producing area.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) exerts a major influence on many other soil properties such as water-holding capacity, retention, infiltration, pH, the exchangeable capacity of the soil, and source of nitrogen (Ayorinde et al., 2015). SOC is an indicator of soil quality and affects soil physical, chemical, and biological characteristics. Increased SOC in weathered tropical soil improves the cation exchange capacity.

Figure 4.37: Soil organic carbon suitability

The contribution of SOC to the soil CEC was reported significantly higher than the contribution of the clay fraction in a Brazilian highly weathered soils (Soares and Ferracciú, 2008). SOC also acts positively on nutrients supply and provides a good soil structure. As such, SOC plays a central role in maintaining tropical soil fertility and Its conservation and maintenance in tropical cultivation systems is imperative if soil degradation is to be halted and cropping made sustainably. Where organic matter contents are high, so are the total N contents (Buggenhout, 2018). Thus, the rate of organic matter also controls the distribution of nitrogen and low level of SOC indicates that the soils cannot supply N adequately and continuously to optimally sustain cocoa requirement without fertilizer application (Ibiremo et al., 2010).

4.4.2.9 Soil total nitrogen (N) distribution and suitability

The total nitrogen (N) distribution map (Figure 4.38) illustrates its variation in the cocoa production area. The distribution of N follows the characteristics of that of soil organic carbon, as the N content of the soils is a reflection of the OC content (Buggenhout, 2018).

Figure 4.38: Soil nitrogen (N) distribution in the cocoa production area

Climate (Cloud cover and precipitation) and elevation (DEM) variables also controlled the distribution of N. However, the suitability pattern is a bit different as compared to that of OC (Figure 4.39). The N concentration in the study area ranged from 0.2 to 20 g kg⁻¹ representing the levels of suitability. Tellen and Yerima (2018b) reported that soil N do not vary significantly with land-use types, but varied significantly with elevation in the North-West region of Cameroon. However, studies have consistently shown that N is generally not a major problem for cocoa production. Ayorinde et al. (2015) found N content of soil ranging from 0.04 to 1.5% indicating that 74.5% of their study area was highly suitable, 10.4% moderately suitable, 8.8% is marginally suitable and just 4.3% unsuitable for cocoa production in Nigeria. Ajiboye et al. (2015) reported soil N content to be slightly higher (0.11 - 0.267%) in most soils in Nigeria. Though some soil total N content was below the critical level (0.9 g kg⁻¹), these N levels were reported to be still fine for cocoa production at Oyun Offa, and Ifelodun localities in Nigeria (Ibiremo et al., 2010).

National cocoa fertilizer formulations generally do not contain N. In Ivory coast, "cocoa fertilizer" ($0\text{ N} - 23\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 19\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 10\text{ CaO} + 5\text{MgO}$) and Teractiv cocoa ($0\text{ N} - 15\text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 - 14\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 28\text{ CaO} + 5.5\text{ S} + 2.5\text{ MgO} + 0.9\text{ Zn} + 0.24\text{ B}_2\text{O}_3$) do not recommend nitrogen for cocoa fertilization (Koko, 2014). The same is true in Ghana, where the main fertilizers recommended for cocoa such as Asaase Wura ($0\text{ N} - 22\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 18\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 9\text{CaO} + 7\text{S} + 6\text{ MgO}$) and Cocofeed ($0\text{ N} - 30\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 20\text{ K}_2\text{O}$) do not contain nitrogen (Afrifa et al., 2009).

Figure 4.39: Soil total nitrogen suitability

Only a few liquid cocoa fertilizers such as Potassium Rich Sidalco Liquid fertilizers ($6\text{ N} - 0\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 20\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 1\text{ MgO} + \text{trace elements}$) and Balanced Sidalco Liquid fertilizer ($\text{N } 10 - 10\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 10\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 1\text{MgO} + \text{trace elements}$) for farmers contain nitrogen in their formulation (Afrifa et al., 2009). In Cameroon, cocoa fertilizer contains low doses of N ($6\text{ N} - 15\text{ P}_2\text{O}_2 - 28\text{ K}_2\text{O} + 6\text{ CaO} + 3\text{ MgO}$). These results corroborate ours, indicating that almost 88% are highly suitable, 11% moderately suitable, and only 1% marginally suitable (Figure 4.39). This observation suggests that nitrogen is not a constraint for cocoa production in Cameroon and the entire African cocoa production belt.

4.4.2.10 Soil texture

Soil texture is very useful for cocoa growth, as it provides information about the soil porosity of the soil (Ayorinde et al., 2015). According to Wayne et al. (2014), soil texture influences numerous soil properties such as drainage, water holding capacity, aeration, organic matter, soil erodibility, and the cation exchange capacity (Kome et al., 2019). The particle sizes distribution maps of the soil in the cocoa production area are illustrated in Figure 4.40 (a, b, c).

Figure 4.40: Particle size Sand (a), Clay (b) and Silt (c) fractions distributions

The particle sizes distribution across the cocoa production area showed a low to moderate spatial heterogeneity with coefficients of variation between 15% and 44%, and values ranging from 0.1 to 86% for sand, from 2.5 to 78.2% for clay, and from 2.5 to 76.1 for silt. The climate (Cloud cover, land surface temperature, and rainfall) and elevation (DEM) variables control the distribution of particle size fractions in the area. Including parent material as covariate could have improved the prediction performances as was reported in Nigeria (Akpa et al., 2014) because the differences in soil texture are more often related to a variation in the parent material.

The textural class of soil is determined by the percentage of sand, silt, and clay content. The most representative soil textural classes in the area (Figure 4.41) are Sandy clay (39 %), sandy

clay loam (34%), clay (14%), and clay loam (12%). Ayorinde et al. (2015) reported sandy loamy texture as the most dominant soil while clay loamy had the smallest coverage in the Osun State, Nigeria. They also pointed out that clay loam, sandy clay loam, sandy loam, and silt loam to be suitable texture classes for cocoa production. Ipinmoroti and Ogeh (2014) indicated that cocoa soils were texturally sandy clay loam in Edo State, Nigeria. Buggenhout (2018) reported that the optimum soil textures for cocoa are loamy and sandy (loamy) clayey soils.

Figure 4.41: USDA soil texture class in the cocoa production area

4.4.2.11 Soil available phosphorus (P)

The topsoil available phosphorus (P) distribution map illustrates (Figure 4.42) the spatial variability of P in the cocoa production area. Just as for the other soil properties, the P distribution is controlled by climate (Cloud cover, rainfall, and land surface temperature) and elevation (DEM) variables. The P of the study area ranged from 0.1 to 115 ppm representing various levels of suitability. These values ranged from very low to high as was reported by Ajiboye et al. (2015) in major cocoa growing areas of Nigeria. The soil P values were below the critical value of ideal soils for cocoa in Adamawa State, Nigeria (Ibiremo et al., 2010). Ahukaemere (2018) reported P to be the second most important nutrient limiting crop yield and to be also deficient in most Nigerian soils due to the high P fixation capacity (acidity) of these soils (Ahukaemere, 2018). In Ghana, soil P significantly contributed explaining variation in the

yield gap in the cocoa production area (Abdulai et al., 2020). Most soils were also reported to have low amounts of available P in Sao-Tomé Buggenhout (2018).

Figure 4.42: Available Phosphorus (P) distribution in the cocoa production area

In this study, the P suitability is 30% marginal, 56% moderate, and 14% high (Figure 4.43). This finding corroborates the report from Atemkeng and Begoude (2014) who stated that P was low in the topsoil of the South region of Cameroon. Available topsoil (0 – 20 cm) phosphorus was also reported to be low (22.1 to 30.9 ppm) in the mountainous ecosystem of North-West Cameroon (Tamfuh et al., 2018), varying significantly with elevation (Tellen and Yerima, 2018). Likewise, Nguemezi et al. (2020) noticed that the major soil fertility problem around Tombel is the low levels of available phosphorus while Ngachie (1992) observed that P deficiency was reported on about 80% of soils in the Southern region and 47% in the Western region. Ngo-Mbogba et al. (2015) also observed P to be among the most variable soil properties in the shifting agricultural landscape of Southern Cameroon. Volcanic soils on the slope of mount Cameroon are as well reported to be deficient in P resulting in low yields (Tening et al., 2013) and according to Tchuenteu (1994), P is one of the major constraints to agricultural production in the largely acid soils of Cameroon. Thus, the phosphorus deficiency problem is

general in Cameroonian soils, as well as in cocoa soils. The deficiency could be due to inherent low P concentration in the parent material, P-fixation, as well as high rainfall especially on acidic and clay-rich soils as noticed by Takoutsing et al. (2016a) in the Western Highlands of Cameroon.

As a component of every living cell, P is indispensable because no other element can replace it in its vital role in many physiological and biochemical processes. However, P addition to the soil is tricky depending on whether the initial P contains is below or above the required optimum. If the soil is below the required optimum for cocoa, the addition of phosphate enables an increase in production. On the contrary, if the soil is already provided with P, phosphate addition may harm the production and the addition of N should have been applied (Buggenhout, 2018). This raises the concern of N and P inter-relation. Indeed, within soil systems, N and P dynamics are interlinked since both are essential macronutrients to microorganisms. Adding large amounts of N to the system via fertilizer application or N fixation might have a significant effect on P transformations (Arenberg and Arai, 2019). Thus Soils containing insufficient amounts of plant-available P not only produce economically unacceptable yields but other inputs, particularly N, are also used less effectively (Syers et al., 2008).

Figure 4.43: Available Phosphorus (P) suitability

The greater need is, therefore, to increase and improve the use of P fertilizers where many soils are deficient in P. The most important factors controlling the P to plant roots are its concentration in the soil solution and the P-buffer capacity of the soil. The latter controls the rate at which P in the soil solution is replenished (Syers et al., 2008). At the broad scale, Batjes (2011) identified soil pH, soil mineralogy, and clay content as the factors controlling the soil P retention processes. According to Syers et al. (2008), strategies for improving the efficiency of use of soil and fertilizer P include: (i) modifying surface soil properties; (ii) managing surface soil; (iii) managing P sources; and (iv) optimizing P use through economically appropriate rates and timing. These strategies are generally site-specific and cropping system-specific. Although they may have only a small impact individually, in combination their benefits may be significant. Application and incorporation of a low cost competing for substance with the phosphate ion for adsorption sites within the soil have been also presented as a good strategy. Silica or silicate is such a competitor and may be available at low cost, e.g. in the form of rice-husk ash, where sufficient quantities are available (Syers et al., 2008).

In Cameroon, Yaya et al. (2015) showed that vivianite (hydrated iron phosphate mineral) from Hangloa (Ngaoundéré Cameroon) contains a very high amount of phosphorus oxide which can be dissolved in the soil, released and become available for plant nutrition. Besides field experiments with mineral and organic fertilizer, this is also a good option to explore in fertilization experiment for recommendations to improve P efficiency could start in Cameroon.

4.4.2.12 Soil cation exchange capacity (CEC)

The topsoil cation exchange capacity (CEC) distribution (Figure 4.44) illustrates the spatial variability of soil CEC in the cocoa production area. The CEC ranged from 3.2 to 77 cmol kg^{-1} . Accordingly, 52% of the area is marginally suitable, 37% moderately suitable, and 11% highly suitable for cocoa production (Figure 4.45). Ayorinde et al. (2015) reported a weak CEC suitability (31% marginally and 69% unsuitable) for cocoa producing areas in Osun State, Nigeria. Studies by Omotoso et al. (2007) showed low CEC in cocoa producing areas, South-Western Nigeria, and attributed it to the low clay and organic matter of the soil. Tamfuh et al. (2018) reported low to moderate (8.6 - 25.6 cmol kg^{-1}) in the mountainous ecosystem of North-West Cameroon. Our findings corroborate that of Ngachie (1992) who reported a 91% extent of soil CEC distribution constraint for crop production in general, in the Southern region, and only 30% in the Western regions.

Figure 4.44: Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) distribution in the cocoa production area

This implies a significant constraint to cocoa production concerning the soil CEC in Cameroon. Only the Cameroon western production belt is highly suitable (Figure 4.45). Almost everywhere else, it's moderate or marginal. CEC is an agronomic property of great importance as it measures a soil's ability to hold nutrients. Soils with high CEC can hold more cations, making them available for plants (Quirine et al., 2007). On the contrary, soils with low CEC are easily deficient in cations. Soils with high CEC have also high ability to hold water (eg. clay soils) while soils with low CEC have low ability to hold water. With low CEC, soils become very quickly acidic (for example sandy soils) and would need liming more frequently than soils with high CEC. Soils with high sand content have low holding capacity for cations compared to clayey and silty soils. Similar to clay particles, organic matter has negatively charged sites that attract and hold on to cations.

Although the type of clay is also important (Figure 4.46), in general, the more clay present, the higher the CEC. In many soils in the tropics, weathering has reached an advanced stage, resulting in clay minerals with low nutrient retention capacities. Large quantities of variable charge surface such as kaolinite and iron oxides minerals are likely to appear and the positive

charge on the soil surface may be significant (Yerima and Van Ranst, 2005b) with a negative effect on the soil CEC.

Figure 4.45: Cation exchange capacity (CEC) suitability

The CEC can directly influence the changes in soil pH because every time the clay particles capture cations they release H^+ and Al^{3+} ions, which in high concentrations acidifies the soil (Aprile and Lorandi, 2012).

Figure 4.46: Influence of organic and mineral particles on CEC (Carroll, 1959)

There are two main ways to improve soil CEC and both solutions will often improve the overall health of the soil. Adding lime to low pH soil and adding organic matter to the soil. The input of OC was responsible for 75 – 85% of the CEC of the highly weathered soils in the tropics (Oorts et al., 2003), and adding OC to soil was reported to doubles the CEC of soil in Brazil (Ramos et al., 2018). Therefore, adding organic matter to soil will increase the CEC and also, improve the structure which improves all aspects of soil health. Basaltic pyroclastic volcanic rocks of the Tombel graben used as natural agricultural inputs were also reported to improve certain Physico-chemical fertility of soils, including the CEC (Nkouathio et al., 2008).

4.4.2.13 Soil suitability for cocoa production in Cameroon

Individual soil properties were combined into soil suitability map for cocoa production in Cameroon (Figure 4.47).

Figure 4.47: Soil suitability for cocoa production

These classes also take into account the climatic, and elevation constraints for cocoa production. High suitability areas represent spaces with very limited soil constraints for cocoa production. A priori, in the strict sense no area is perfect for cocoa production. However, with some minor

corrections, cocoa production becomes highly suitable in some areas, as illustrated in Figure 4.47. Cameroon thus has a strip of land highly suitable for cocoa production covering mainly the South-West regions and extending eastwards through the North of the Centre region, while narrowing. Overall, 13% of the area has high suitability, 78% has Moderate suitability, and only 9% with marginal suitability. It should also be noted that in the moderate class zone, there are spots of highly suitable areas for cocoa production.

4.4.2.14 Soil properties and cocoa production

With the random forest algorithm, we predicted the cocoa production on areas-based soil properties. The model could explain 60% of the production level (Kappa coefficient = 0.6) based on input soil properties. As we know that cocoa production depends on several other factors such as climate (rainfall, temperature, and humidity), farm management, and pest and disease control, the prediction performance is promising and could significantly increase if the other factors are included in the model. The variable of importance function enabled us to rank the most contributing soil properties contributors to the production estimation. Figure 4.48 shows that all the soil properties consistently contributed to the prediction of the production classes, with levels of contribution varying from about 5% for P to ~ 20% for organic carbon.

Figure 4.48: Level of contribution (%) of soil properties to cocoa production

The 5 topmost topsoil properties most affecting cocoa production in Cameroon are respectively OC > Clay > Mg > pH > Silt. According to Yemefack et al. (2006) OC and pH are among the

minimum dataset that can be used to evaluate the soil quality in the shifting agricultural landscape of southern Cameroon. Ayorinde et al. (2015) showed that soil particle size distribution, OC, N, P, and CEC was constraint affecting soil suitability for cocoa production in Osun State, Nigeria. Adeniyi (2019) latter corroborated that finding showing that OC, pH, CEC, and Clay were among the minimum dataset for characterizing soil for cocoa production in the same State in Nigeria. Clay, OC, and pH were also noticed as limiting cocoa yield in Southern Nigeria (Ogunlade et al., 2012). Nonetheless, the importance of several other soil characteristics, such as pH and organic matter, is largely due to their influence on the availability of nutrients (Buggenhout, 2018). Takoutsing et al. (2018) reported the same trend in the western highland of Cameroon and conclude that SOC should control the production ability because it is coupled with most of the soil properties. Likewise, soil properties namely Ca, pH, OC, P were identified as important indicators for assessing the fertility status of the soil groups in the Tombel area, with Ca, Mg, pH, OC, P, N, and CEC as the principal indicators controlling soil quality (Nguemezi et al., 2020). These results corroborate those of our analyses and indicate the key soil properties on which management can be focused to increase cocoa production. However, soil scientists need to take into account local knowledge in formulating hypotheses on soil functioning that determine soil health, and then set up an approach that is integrative, systems-oriented, and multidisciplinary to ensure the sustainability of soil health in the cocoa production system (Takoutsing et al., 2018). Field experiments must be carried out to establish the balances linked to these different elements, to sustainably increase the cocoa production in Cameroon.

4.4.2.15 Soil properties and climate suitability

Analysis of variance shows the variability of soil properties between the climatic suitability classes in Table 4.16.

Table 4.16: ANOVA of soil properties according to production levels

	OC	N	P	Ca	CEC	K	Mg	pH	Sand	Silt	Clay
	(g/kg)		(mg/kg)	(cmol kg ⁻¹)				H ₂ O	(%)		
Very good	20.25 ^a	1.78 ^a	7.76 ^a	3.52 ^{ab}	11.2 ^a	0.28 ^b	1.54 ^a	5.32 ^a	55.00 ^a	16.66 ^a	27.4 ^b
Good	27.91 ^a	2.25 ^a	10.35 ^a	2.80 ^b	15.4 ^a	0.31 ^{ab}	1.24 ^a	4.80 ^a	48.96 ^{ab}	17.07 ^a	34.6 ^{ab}
Fairly good	26.65 ^a	2.04 ^a	12.93 ^a	3.94 ^{ab}	15.4 ^a	0.43 ^a	1.68 ^a	5.31 ^a	47.80 ^{ab}	21.39 ^a	32.8 ^{ab}
Fair	23.75 ^a	2.06 ^a	9.14 ^a	3.10 ^b	14.0 ^a	0.31 ^{ab}	1.27 ^a	5.01 ^a	49.33 ^{ab}	15.68 ^a	36.1 ^a
Poor	29.31 ^a	2.23 ^a	10.67 ^a	3.22 ^b	15.5 ^a	0.30 ^b	1.38 ^a	5.20 ^a	44.86 ^b	21.91 ^a	34.9 ^a
Very poor	24.66 ^a	2.10 ^a	10.09 ^a	4.19 ^{ab}	13.2 ^a	0.33 ^{ab}	1.42 ^a	5.03 ^a	45.27 ^{ab}	20.82 ^a	35.6 ^a
Unsuitable	25.63 ^a	2.62 ^a	9.00 ^a	4.85 ^a	15.2 ^a	0.34 ^{ab}	1.83 ^a	5.29 ^a	48.37 ^{ab}	17.95 ^a	35.5 ^a

Values in the same column with the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

There is no significant difference between several soil properties. Apart from exchangeable calcium (Ca), potassium (K) sand, and clay fractions, all the other soil properties are non-significantly different. This is likely because of the high variability of soil properties within the classes. Indeed, the different classes of climatic suitability cover several agroecological zones with different edaphic characteristics.

For example, the climatic suitability class "Good" extends over three agroecological zones (Humid forest with monomodal rainfall, humid forest with bimodal rainfall and western highlands) (Figure 2.11). The clay and sand fractions of the particle size distribution make it possible to justify most of the variability of the soil texture between the different suitability classes. Although calcium and potassium are significantly different, their values in these classes could not allow conclusions to be drawn on their contribution to the aptitude of these classes. As the same values belong both to suitable and unsuitable classes, it is difficult to establish the direction in which they contribute to the discrimination of those classes. This is an illustration of the complex relationships existing between these different properties of soils.

Figure 4.49: Proportions of soil suitability class within each climate suitability area (1 = Marginal, 2 = Moderate and 3 = High)

Figure 4.49 illustrates the distribution of soil suitability classes in the 5 climatic suitability zones for cocoa production in Cameroon. The soil suitability classes have varying proportions in different climatic zones. Only 1% of the soils in the "Very Good" climatic zone have a high capability, and 98% of these soils have a moderate capability, and the surface area under this climatic suitability class is very low (about 800 km²). In the "Good" climatic zone (about 16 000 km²), there are respectively 3% of highly suitable soils and 3% of marginal soils as well as 94% of soils with moderate suitability for cocoa production. The "Fairly Good" (about 82 000 km²) and "Fair" (about 43 000 km²) climatic zones show approximately the same trends, with about 13% of the soils having high and marginal suitability respectively.

The viable policy of sustainable intensification of cocoa production in Cameroon should first explore the possibilities of optimizing production and extending cocoa plots in the most favorable climatic zones, by providing required elements to correct the soil deficiencies identified for each zone. The establishment of management protocols and technical documents adapted to each zone seems urgent. Field trials, taking into account the proportions and variability and soil properties obtained in this study are strongly recommended. These studies should also consider the management of long-term soil restoration in these production systems. Furthermore, the establishment of CAF plantations on fallow lands rather than clearing forests could represent a significant and useful strategy for climate change mitigation and the improvement of farmers' livelihoods, particularly if additional payment can be generated to producers through incentive payments initiatives such as REDD +.

CHAPTER FIVE: MAIN FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

5.1.1 Legacy soil data compilation

Most of the legacy soil data from soil surveys in Cameroon are still stored in the libraries of the institutions having carried out the surveys. IRD's online library is the most significant and contains most of the soil studies reports carried out by IRCAM and ORSTOM in Cameroon. At the national setting, IRAD and the University of Dschang are leading in terms of legacy soil data holding, though these data are still mainly stored on reports and thesis. Senior soil scientists from Cameroon and abroad, having participated in soil surveys in Cameroon contributed with relevant documents and/or giving precise indications on the projects in which they were involved.

First conventional soil surveys started around 1946 in Cameroon. These surveys slowly evolved until 1960, and a significant increase followed, reaching the first peak around 1965. Most of the fieldwork activities in French-occupied Cameroon were carried out during this period. Afterward, there was a slight transition period with a decrease in the intensity of activities toward the end 1960s. The highest intensity was observed between 1970 and 1975. More than a decade after 1990, soil studies remained forgotten, coinciding with the period of the structural adjustment plans (SAP) of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF). Since then, the interest in soil assessment restarted and is growing again. The intensity of investigation is again gradually increasing.

Based on the sources and contributions enumerated, the first-ever national soil profile database for Cameroon (Camsodat 0.1) was compiled. Harmonization of laboratory results was mainly carried out according to the requirements of the GlobalSoilMap project. In total, 53% of soil profiles had GPS coordinates, 33% were localized based on sampling maps (SM), and 12% of locations were estimated from the field description (FD). The full dataset currently contains a total of 5050 layers distributed over 1432 georeferenced points, with an average density of one profile per 325 km². This is a significant basis in terms of legacy soil data rescue in Cameroon which should continue with additional legacy soil data rescue and or new field data collection. This analysis allowed us to identify the areas already surveyed in Cameroon. The spatial

coverage of soil surveys is not homogeneous, and showed areas of low density and very low density. The densest areas are those in the north-west and the northern regions (North and Far North). The regions of Adamaoua, Littoral, and parts of the Centre (North of the region), East and South-West regions are with very low spatial coverage densities. Areas with large gaps are those where the upcoming field campaigns could primarily investigate.

5.1.2 Countrywide spatial distribution of some soil properties

While processing the countrywide soil properties data (pH and particle size fraction) for DSM analysis, the sample size gradually and consistently decreased from the topsoil layers (~ 1463) to the subsoil layers (~ 590). Silt showed the highest heterogeneity (with CV between 61 and 73). All soil properties showed the highest variability at 60 – 100 cm depth and the combination of various predictor covariates could explain up to 64% of prediction modeling, which is an important result because of the complexity of the soil. Soil pH showed the best performance in model evaluation at all depths, while the least performance was observed on silt.

The random forest (RF) and associated hybrids with ordinary kriging (RF_OK) and inverse distance weighing (RF_IDW) yielded similar results and the inclusion of SoilGrids as covariate consistently improved the prediction performance (R^2) for up to 10% increases. The distribution of the predicted soil properties almost follows a similar pattern as the original data, though with lesser variability. The model accurately and consistently estimated the average clay, pH, and sand values with a low shift. However, there is a distortion on the prediction of extreme values (minimum and maximum). Thus, our estimates could be significantly improved by including additional soil data and covariates such as parent material, which has geological uplift for tropical areas than other regions and contribute to the complexity of soil pattern.

Countrywide clay distribution seems to be more related to the occurrence of sedimentary rocks in the substrate, especially in areas where limestone and claystone are common, and increases in with soil depth, especially in the southern part of the country. The sand content is relatively high compared with fine particles (Silt and Clay) across the country. Sand proportions decrease gradually southward with latitude and also with soil depth. The countrywide silt content is relatively low with spots of medium silt content in the North-West, and Adamaoua regions.

The soil texture class variability gradually increases from the surface horizon (0 – 5 cm) and reaches its maximum between 15 and 30 cm in depth. In the first two surface horizons (0 – 5

cm and 5 – 15 cm), the succession of textural soil classes as we move from south northward is respectively sandy clay, sandy clay loam, clay loam, and clay, with some clay spots distributed all over the country in particular near rivers.

The pattern of soil pH distribution is clear, with the pH ranging from 3.7 to 8.3 in the topsoil and 3.9 – 9.1 in the subsoil. There is a trend of soil acidity in the south of the country with the opposite feature in the north where most soils are alkaline largely due to the climate variation. Soils in southern Adamaoua are mainly acidic, from very strongly acidic to slightly acidic. A transition zone is observed in the North region with neutral soils, then alkaline soils are widespread in the far North. The southern part of the country had relatively low soil pH due to higher precipitation and leaching. Areas of high soil pH are located north of the country, possibly associated with the arid climate prevailing.

5.1.3 Soil organic carbon stock in Cameroon

Using rescued legacy soil data, the first spatially explicit national estimate of soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS) in Cameroon was provided. The models acceptably predicted SOCS distribution in the upper layers (0 – 15 cm and 15 – 30 cm) by capturing at least 52% of the variation based on the average over 100 repetitions of 10-fold cross-validation. The random forest (RF) model outperformed the generalized boosted regression (GBR) model with an average of 10% improvement on the R^2 value at each depth. The performance of the RF model could be ascribed to its capability in detecting and dealing with nonlinear and hierarchical relationships between SOCS and predictive variables.

Performances of RF and hybrids with ordinary kriging (RF_OK) and inverse distance weighing (RF_IDW) are similar. Overall, the combination of RF with OK performed best, although performances are similar. Since the residual spatial correlation is weak, residual kriging did not lead to a significant improvement compared to RGB or RF predictions.

Terrain and climate attributes are the key environmental covariates for SOCS spatial prediction and could be used to develop observation networks for monitoring changes in SOCS in Cameroon. Each model selected terrain attributes, climate, and vegetation indices as important covariates to predict SOCS. Terrain attributes (elevation; DEM, 46%) and climate variables (Precipitable Water Vapor, PWV; 25%); Rainfall (Rain; 10%) and Temperature (Temp; 8%) control the GBR prediction outputs with about 89% of their relative influence.

A strong relation between SOCS distribution and agroecological zones was noticed. The SOCS gradually increases northwards from the humid forest with a bimodal rainfall agroecological (HFBR) zone in the south up to the high guinea savanna zone (HGSZ). Total SOCS in the 1 m soil layer under each agroecological zone (AEZ) showed the following sequence: WHZ (203.9 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HGSZ (173.6 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HFMR (129.8 Mg C ha⁻¹) > HFBR (105.2 Mg C ha⁻¹) > SSZ (70.6 Mg C ha⁻¹).

A total of about 5.67 Pg of SOCS is contained in the first meter of soil in Cameroon, of which 50% is stored in the top 30 cm soil layer. Indeed, total SOCS in Cameroon is 2.80 Pg and 5.67 Pg for 0 – 30 cm and 0 – 100 cm soil depth, respectively. Compared to the national estimates, SOCS showed overestimation on SoilGrids and underestimation on harmonized world soil data (HWSD) with variable levels at different soil depths. The global models are useful for predicting soil properties on a national scale when used as covariates. Our result study suggests the need to densify soil data spatial coverage in Camsodat for both improving the spatial autocorrelation of SOCS and the performance of prediction models. The current dataset could, however, the models allowed to capture about 60% of the countrywide SOCS variability.

5.1.4 Cocoa system sustainability in the shifting agricultural landscape

Over 50 years, the mean SOCS gradually increases from 33 Mg C ha⁻¹ in cropland to 57 Mg C ha⁻¹ in the secondary forest for fallow and 62 Mg C ha⁻¹ for cocoa systems. The logistic model provided the best fit for describing the SOCS accretion for both systems with coefficients of determination (R^2) 0.79 and 0.75 for fallow and cocoa systems respectively. SOCS accumulation was significantly higher in the cocoa system throughout the referred period as compared to the fallow system.

The point of maximum growth (PMG) in the fallow system is reached after 14 years and up to 36 years in the CAF system. The coefficient of the maximum growth rate at PMG varies from 0.4 to 0.56 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ respectively for fallow and cocoa systems. This indicates a quick accumulation of SOCS in the two systems, which is then followed by a gradually decreasing SOCS accumulation rate. The optimum fallow period for soil recovery after shifting agriculture appears to be around 14 years. The greater SOC accumulation in cocoa throughout the referred period (50 years) as compared to fallow reflects the difference in the management of the two systems.

Our findings support the expanded use and management of cocoa systems as a REDD+ mechanism strategy for emission reduction, especially as cocoa can serve as versatile production systems, producing supplementary outcomes (such as cash, fruits, and/or medicines) that further improve local livelihoods. If additional payment can be generated to the farmers for additional SOCS storage, the establishment of such cocoa systems on the current fallow lands may contribute to reducing the new expansion of perennial plantations into primary forest lands.

5.1.5 Soil suitability for cocoa production

Soils in the cocoa production area in Cameroon are slightly acidic (average pH = 5.09) with the mean sand, silt, and clay fractions of 43.75%, 21.97, and 34.27, respectively. Exchangeable Ca content ranged from 0.01 – 28.74 cmol kg⁻¹, while Mg and K are between 0.01 – 19.56 and 0.01 – 4.04 cmol kg⁻¹. With an average of 3.27 cmol kg⁻¹, Ca is the dominant cation in the soil complex. This is followed by Mg and K with average concentrations of 1.53 and 0.33 cmol kg⁻¹ respectively. Organic C and total N contents of soils ranged between 0.85 – 217.37 g kg⁻¹ and 0.12 – 22.39%, respectively. The mean total nitrogen (0.23 %) is slightly higher than the world average (0.18%). Available P content in the soils ranged from 0.01 to 172.74 ppm, with a mean value of 10.38 ppm and a marked variability across the area. The cation exchange capacity ranged from 2.6 to 82.6 cmol kg⁻¹ with an average of 17.47 cmol kg⁻¹.

Successful models were fitted to soil properties using the set of covariates with R² between 19 and 61%. Accuracies of the spatial predictions could be improved by investing in new and/or more detailed covariates, as well as additional soil data. The model-fitting results showed that the most important predictors for investigated soil properties are climatic variables (precipitation and temperature, cloud cover), terrain parameters (DEM, Slope, valley bottom flatness, negative and positive topographic index, Topographic wetness index, valley depth) and land cover (Enhanced vegetation index, Global land cover). The order of importance varies from one soil property to another with the main trend in the order climate > Terrain attribute > Landcover.

The predicted soil pH values ranged from 3.5 to 7.8 indicating that soils are mostly acidic. The soil pH suitability is mainly moderate ($5 \leq \text{pH} \leq 6$) and marginal ($\text{pH} < 5$) and about 35% of the area is highly suitable, 62% is moderately suitable, and only 3% marginally suitable. As soils are acidic, they usually pose a problem of macronutrient unavailability and phytotoxic concentrations of micronutrients such as Aluminum and Manganese. Application of lime is the

most used and recommended option as well as organic amendments, and the development of toxic elements-tolerant cocoa cultivars seems to be an option on which research might have to further investigate.

Soils in the cocoa production area have low exchangeable calcium content (Mean = 3.69 and median = 3.37). Exchangeable Calcium suitability is mainly moderate ($3 \leq \text{Ca} [\text{mol kg}^{-1}] \leq 6$) and marginal ($\text{Ca} [\text{mol kg}^{-1}] < 3$) in cocoa production areas. About 55% of the area is moderately suitable, 42% marginally suitable, and only 3% highly suitable. Application of calcium fertilizer or calcium-enriched fertilizer would be required to upgrade the Ca level taking into consideration the current spatial distribution of soil Ca.

The spatial distribution of Mg predominantly exhibited moderate Mg content ($1 - 3 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) in the cocoa production area (Mean = 1.34 cmol kg^{-1} and Median = 1.23 cmol kg^{-1}). Exchangeable magnesium suitability is mainly marginal ($3 \leq \text{Mg} [\text{mol kg}^{-1}]$) for cocoa production in Cameroon covering 97% of the area. There are some few spots with moderate suitability ($3 < \text{Mg} [\text{mol kg}^{-1}] \leq 6$) and very few with high suitability. These soils are too low in available magnesium to sustain intensive cropping without the use of magnesium fertilizers.

The spatial distribution of exchangeable potassium (K) showed low ($0.2 - 0.3 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) potassium content in the area (Mean = 0.28 cmol kg^{-1} and Median = 0.25 cmol kg^{-1}). Exchangeable potassium suitability for cocoa production was classified as 59% moderately suitable, 33% highly suitable, and 8% marginally suitable. When potassium fertilization is necessary, it should take into consideration the dose, timing, and method of application to minimize losses, as well as to avoid depletion of K thereby ensuring an increase in yield per unit K applied to the soil.

We observed that 52% of the area is highly suitable, 36% is moderately suitable, and 12% marginally suitable for cocoa production in the area. Spots of high SOC concentrations are also identified along the rivers throughout the area (Sanaga, Nyong, etc.). Total N concentration in the area ranged from 0.2 to 20 g kg^{-1} representing the levels of suitability. N is generally not a major problem for cocoa production and national cocoa fertilizer formulations generally do not contain N. These results corroborate ours, indicating that almost 88% are highly suitable, 11% moderately suitable, and only 1% marginally suitable. This observation suggests that nitrogen is not a constraint for cocoa production in Cameroon and the entire African cocoa production belt.

The most representative soil textural classes in the area are Sandy clay (39 %), sandy clay loam (34%), clay (14%), and clay loam (12%). The available Phosphorus (P) of the area ranged from 0.1 to 115 ppm representing levels of suitability. P suitability is 30% marginal, 56% moderate, and 14% high. P is one of the major constraints to agricultural production in the largely acid soils of Cameroon. Thus, the phosphorus deficiency problem is general in Cameroonian soils, as well as in cocoa soils. The deficiency could be due to inherent low P concentration in the parent material, P-fixation, as well as high rainfall, especially on acidic and clay-rich soils. The application of phosphorus fertilizer as already recommended in many national generic cocoa fertilizers is a good option. Minerals such as vivianite have undergone encouraging agronomic trials and could also constitute strategies to address phosphorus deficiency for cocoa production.

The CEC ranged from 3.2 to 77 cmol kg⁻¹ and accordingly, 52% of the area is marginally suitable, 37% moderately suitable, and 11% highly suitable for cocoa production. This implies a significant constraint to cocoa production concerning the soil CEC in Cameroon. Only the Cameroon western production belt is highly suitable. Almost everywhere else, exhibited moderate or marginal suitability. Overall, Cameroon has a strip of land with varying levels of suitability for cocoa production. About 13% of the area has high suitability, 78% has moderate suitability, and 9% with marginal suitability.

Every soil property consistently contributed to the prediction of the production, with levels of contribution varying from about 5% for P to ~ 20% OC. The 5 topmost properties likely to most affect cocoa production in Cameroon are respectively OC > Clay > Mg > pH > Silt.

Soil properties are not significant variables between the different climatic zones, likely because of the high variability of soil properties within the classes. Indeed, the different classes are spread over several agroecological zones with different edaphic characteristics. The soil suitability classes are with varying proportions in different climatic zones, with moderate suitability, covering more than 75% of each zone.

5.2 CONCLUSION

We investigated the applicability of digital soil mapping methods with legacy soil data for inventorying soil resources, as input for sustainable intensification of agricultural production in Cameroon. From limited compiled soil data, many valuable predictions have been made for soil properties in national grids (100 m resolution). Rescued legacy soil data compiled in a soil

profile database showed a high potential for reliable national soil properties estimates. The current distribution of existing soil profiles provides guidance on the policy for the elaboration of a national guide for the upcoming pedological activities in Cameroon. The first spatially explicit national predictions of soil pH, sand, silt, clay, soil texture, organic carbon stocks in Cameroon were established. These grids are considered as a basis for agricultural development and land evaluation for development planning in Cameroon. Our results are also the first components of the GlobalSoilMap deliverables for Cameroon. They will enable the formulation of recommendations for sustainable intensification of agriculture, as well as supporting the revision of technical documents for the use of agricultural inputs such as fertilizers. Regional and local development planning, which is currently not adapted to the realities on the ground would also benefit from these data. These maps are also a benchmark against which to evaluate the impacts of changes in land use and climate on soils and can guide advisors and agencies who make decisions on remediation and prevention of soil.

Further, the soil properties grids in the cocoa production area, showed distinct levels of soil suitability, which are useful for site-specific implementation of sustainable intensification of cocoa production in Cameroon, offering a reference for soil properties distribution required for soil management and restoration. Prediction accuracies are promising for future national-scale digital soil mapping efforts in data-poor countries such as Cameroon, and the methodology adopted in this thesis is efficient and cost-effective. However, we do not claim to have estimated the exact values of soil properties examined. But we were able to get closer to up to 85% of the exact values. To improve these estimates, the sampling points must be densified and significant new covariates must be included. Although gaps exist in Cameroon's soil information, DSM showed the potential to close this gap.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The very first soil database in Cameroon has been established. However, being aware that the quality of the estimates depends on the quality and quantity of the data used, our observations suggest that there are thousands of other data privately available. To improve and optimize Camsodat for the production of further accurate maps to tackle the current and future soil information gaps in Cameroon, additional investigations should be carried out in the following thematic areas:

- Intensify the rescue of existing data and extension of the database to include digitized legacy soil maps;
- Assess the uncertainty on the spatial location of soils profiles and its propagation on predicted soil estimates;
- Improve the sampling network at set up the national soil monitoring system in Cameroon;
- Improve the spatial coverage network with a sound and cost-efficient sampling network and set up the national soil monitoring system in Cameroon;
- Develop an orientation guide for priority investigation zones for soil field activities in Cameroon.
- Migrate the current soil database into a relational system taking into account the country's current political orientations, such as decentralization;
- Set up the national soil information system in Cameroon;
- Propose local and adapted equations for the harmonization of soil properties analysis results and pedotransfert equations.

Optimization of the database will provide opportunities to improve the soil maps. Several approaches can be used for the elaboration of more precise soil maps. In this context, future studies should focus primarily on:

- Explore strategies for optimizing the prediction of soil properties;
- Extend soil property mapping to all those recommended by the GlobalSoilMap;
- Estimate the SOCS potential in Cameroon and propose strategies to fill the gap;
- Assess within and between agroecological soil properties variability and identify the main drivers;

With regard to the application of this methodology for the development of sustainable agriculture policy, the following studies need to be carried out:

- Extend this study to all the main agricultural speculations produced in Cameroon;
- Identify strategies for the efficient correction of deficiencies in each of the soil properties for cocoa production;
- Soil testing and fertilizer trials for the formulation of site-specific fertilizer recommendation

- Complete the land valuation analysis for cocoa production by including all other factors influencing cocoa production such as soil depth and terrain parameters;

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APPENDIX A: ROUTINE QUALITY CONTROL CRITERIA

- 1) **Referential integrity.**
- 2) **Data types.**
- 3) **Geo-location.**
 - a) Exclude: Identify, and subsequently check, profiles for which the geo-location (lat-lon) is unknown (0, 0) or not within the spatial domain of the profile's ISO country code. Correct coordinates, if possible, or exclude profile.
- 4) **Layer upper and lower depths** and sequential layer numbering.
 - a) Identify profile layers with upper depth equal to- or exceeding lower; correct depths and update sequential numbering of layers.
 - b) Identify sample layers with depth interval fitting within the depth interval of the associated horizon; adjust layer depths to horizon depths.
 - c) Identify sample layers with depth interval not fitting within the depth interval of the associated horizon; adjust layer depths to sampled depths and update sequential numbering of layers.
- 5) **Depth of profile observation.**
 - a) No routine controls applied.
- 6) **Coarse fragment content (v%).**
 - a) Identify Coarse fragment content values outside the range of 0-100%, and correct or exclude value.
- 7) **Coarse and fine sand.**
 - a) Identify values for the Sum of coarse and fine sand contents exceeding the Total sand content, permitting an inaccuracy of 1 %, and correct or exclude values for coarse and fine sand.
- 8) **Fine earth fractions.**
 - a) Identify Sand content values outside the range of 0-100%, and correct or exclude values.
 - b) Identify Silt content values outside the range of 0-100%, and correct or exclude values.
 - c) Identify Clay content values outside the range of 0-100%, and correct or exclude values.
- 9) **Sum of fine earth fractions.**
 - a) Identify reported values for Sum of sand, silt and clay fractions, different from re-calculated sum of Sand, Silt and Clay fractions, permitting an inaccuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$, and correct values.
 - b) Identify values for the Sum of sand, silt and clay fractions outside the range of 90-110%, and correct or exclude values (of sand, silt, clay and sum).
 - c) Subsequently, identify values for the sum of Sand, silt and clay outside the range of 98-102%, and flag values.
- 10) **Bulk density (BD).**
 - a) Identify Bulk density values outside the range of 0.1-2.7 kg/dm³, and correct or exclude values.
 - b) Identify Bulk density values outside the range of 0.5-2.0 kg/dm³, and flag values.
- 11) **Saturated hydraulic conductivity (KSat).**
 - a) Identify Saturated hydraulic conductivity values < 0 dS/m, and correct or exclude values.
- 12) **pH.**
 - a) Identify pHH₂O, pHKCl and/or pHCaCl₂ values outside the range of 2-12, and correct or exclude values.
 - b) Identify pHKCl and/or pHCaCl₂ values exceeding pHH₂O values, permitting an inaccuracy of 0.1 while excepting layers of profiles classified as having generic property, and

flag.

c) Flag pH value for layers for which base saturation value is flagged.

13) Electrical conductivity.

a) Identify Electrical conductivity values < 0 dS/m, and correct or exclude values.

b) Identify Electrical conductivity values exceeding 30 dS/m while $pH_{H_2O} < 7.5$ or $pH_{KCl} < 7$ or $pH_{CaCl_2} < 7$, and flag values.

c) Identify Electrical conductivity values exceeding 0 dS/m while $pH_{H_2O} < 6.5$ or $pH_{KCl} < 6$ or $pH_{CaCl_2} < 6$, and flag values.

14) Soluble cations and anions.

a) Identify Soluble cation and anion values outside the range of 0-2600 cmol/l, and correct or exclude values.

b) Identify Soluble cation and anion values exceeding 0.1 cmol/l while $pH_{H_2O} < 7.5$ or $pH_{KCl} < 7$ or $pH_{CaCl_2} < 7$, and flag values.

15) Exchangeable bases.

a) Identify Exchangeable calcium, magnesium, sodium or potassium values, of version 1 data outside the range of 0-200, 0-50, 0-200 and 0-20 cmol/kg, respectively, and of version 2 data outside the range of 0-100, 0-25, 0-100 and 0-10 cmol/kg, and correct or exclude values. If the data source is LREP then correct or exclude values by batch (district). Upper limits are based on visual outlier analysis.

b) Identify Exchangeable calcium, magnesium, sodium or potassium values exceeding 100, 50, 100 and 20 cmol/kg, respectively, and flag values.

c) Identify Sum of Exchangeable bases values exceeding 150 cmol/kg, and flag values.

The sum of exchangeable bases is defined here as the sum of minimally 3 out of 4 bases.

16) Exchangeable acidity.

a) Identify Exchangeable acidity values exceeding 50 cmol/kg, and flag values.

b) Identify Exchangeable acidity values where Exchangeable hydrogen value exceeds 0.1 cmol/kg while $pH_{H_2O} > 6.5$ or $pH_{KCl} > 6$ or $pH_{CaCl_2} > 6$, and flag values.

c) Identify Exchangeable acidity values where Exchangeable aluminum or the sum of Exchangeable aluminum and hydrogen exceeds 0.1 cmol/kg while $pH_{H_2O} > 5.5$ or $pH_{KCl} > 5$ or $pH_{CaCl_2} > 5$, and flag values.

17) Effective Cation Exchange Capacity.

a) Identify eCEC values (mineral soils) exceeding 150 cmol/kg and flag values.

b) Identify eCEC values exceeding 4 times CEC value, and flag values.

c) Flag eCEC values for layers for which the base saturation value or the exchangeable acidity value is flagged

18) Cation Exchange Capacity.

a) Identify Soil CEC values outside the range of 0-150 cmol/kg, and correct or exclude values for version 1 and 2 data. If the data source is LREP then correct or exclude values by batch (district). Upper limits are based on visual outlier analysis (often associated with peat soils).

b) Identify Soil CEC values less than 1 cmol/kg, and flag values.

c) Identify Soil CEC values exceeding 120 cmol/kg, and flag values.

d) Identify Soil CEC values outside the range as determined by type and content of clay and organic carbon, and correct or exclude values for version 1 data. Lower limit is defined as $[(\text{clay} (\%) * 1 (\text{cmol/kg}) / 100) + [\text{OrgC} (\%) * 100 (\text{cmol/kg}) / 1000] * 1/a]$, and upper limit as $[(\text{clay} (\%) * 150 (\text{cmol/kg}) / 100) + [\text{OrgC} (\%) * 600 (\text{cmol/kg}) / 1000] * a]$, with $a = 1.5$. Soil CEC values less than a lower limit of maximally 2.5 cmol/kg are maintained.

e) Identify Soil CEC values outside the range as determined by type and content of clay and organic carbon, and flag values. Lower limit is defined as $[(\text{clay} (\%) * 1 (\text{cmol/kg})$

/100] + [OrgC (%) * 100 (cmol/kg) / 1000] * 1/a], and upper limit as [[clay (%) * 150 (cmol/kg) / 100] + [OrgC (%) * 600 (cmol/kg) / 1000] * a], with a = 1.

19) Base saturation.

- a) Identify values for the ratio of Exchangeable calcium/CEC, magnesium/CEC, sodium/CEC or potassium/CEC outside the range of 0-5, 0-2, 0-5 and 0-1, respectively, and flag values. Upper limits are based on visual outlier analysis.
- b) Identify values for ExCa >0.5 cmol/kg and <ExMg, and flag values.
- c) Identify values for ExNa >0.5 cmol/kg and <ExK, and flag values.
- d) Identify base (over-) saturation values exceeding 300%, and flag values.
- e) Identify base saturation values exceeding 60%, while pH_{H2O}<5.5 or pH_{KCl}<5 or pH_{CaCl2}<5, or base saturation values less than 40%, while pH_{H2O}>5.5 or pH_{KCl}>5 or pH_{CaCl2}>5 and flag values. Flagged values indicate possible inconsistencies in the values for ExCa, ExMg, ExNa, ExK, ExBases, eCEC, CEC, clay content, organic carbon content, pH_{H2O}, pH_{KCl} and/or pH_{CaCl2}.
- f) Identify base saturation values exceeding 99%, while pH_{H2O}<6.5 or pH_{KCl}<6 or pH_{CaCl2}<6, or base saturation values less than 99%, while pH_{H2O}>6.5 or pH_{KCl}>6 or pH_{CaCl2}>6 and flag values. Flagged values indicate possible inconsistencies in the values for ExCa, ExMg, ExNa, ExK, ExBases, eCEC, CEC, clay content, organic carbon content, pH_{H2O}, pH_{KCl} and/or pH_{CaCl2}.

20) Free gypsum and lime.

- a) Identify CaSO₄ and CaCO₃ values outside the range of 0-1000 g/kg, and correct or exclude values.
- b) Identify CaSO₄ values exceeding 0.1 g/kg, while pH_{H2O}<6.5 or pH_{KCl}<6 or pH_{CaCl2}<6, and flag values.
- c) Identify CaCO₃ values exceeding 0.1 g/kg, while pH_{H2O}<6.5 or pH_{KCl}<6 or pH_{CaCl2}<6, and flag values.

21) Total carbon and inorganic carbon.

- a) Identify Total or Inorganic Carbon values outside the range of 0-1000 g/kg, and correct or exclude values.
- b) Identify Total carbon values exceeding organic carbon values, with >0.1 g/kg, while pH_{H2O}<6.5 or pH_{KCl}<6 or pH_{CaCl2}<6, and flag values.
- c) Identify Inorganic carbon values exceeding 0.1 g/kg while pH_{H2O}<6.5 or pH_{KCl}<6 or pH_{CaCl2}<6, and flag values.
- d) Identify Organic carbon values exceeding Total carbon values, and flag values.

22) Organic carbon and total nitrogen.

- a) Identify Organic carbon values outside the range of 0-580 g/kg (with ISRIC datasets as reference), and correct or exclude values.
- b) Identify Organic carbon values exceeding 140 g/kg, flag values.
- c) Identify Total nitrogen values outside the range of 0-40 g/kg (with ISRIC datasets as reference), and correct or exclude values.
- d) Identify Total nitrogen values exceeding 12 g/kg, and flag values.
- e) Identify C/N ratio values outside the range of 1-110, and correct or exclude values (of organic carbon and total nitrogen).
- f) Identify C/N ratio values outside the range of 4-45, and flag values.

23) Total phosphorus.

- a) Identify Total P values outside the range of 0-1,000,000 mg/kg, and correct or exclude values.
- b) Identify Total P values exceeding 1000 mg/kg and flag values.

24) Available phosphorus.

a) Identify Available P values outside the range of 0-1,000,000 mg/kg, and correct or exclude values.

25) Volumetric moisture content at suctions from pF 0.0 – pF 5.8.

a) Identify volumetric moisture content values outside the range of 0-98 %, and correct or exclude values (with values exceeding 98% set at 98%).

b) Identify Volumetric moisture content values exceeding volumetric moisture content values at lower suction (VMC_{pF00} >10 >15 >20 >23 >25 >28 >29 >30 >37 >42 >VMC_{pF58}), and correct or exclude value.

Note that the routine criteria applied on multiple attributes (e.g. inorganic carbon and pH, or base saturation and pH) are (too) simple. The criteria include cut off points (e.g. base saturation exceeding 60% while pH<5.5), yielding ‘squared corner’ selections out of clouds of data points. It is better, where the values of 2 attributes show some correlation, to assess the relationship ($Y = aX$) and to define the permitted inaccuracy or confidence interval as (user defined) criterium.

APPENDIX B: LIST OF REFERENCES IN THE CAMSODAT0.1 DATABASE

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APPENDIX C: CURRICULUM VITAE

	<h1 style="text-align: right;">Pedometrician</h1>
	PERSONNAL INFORMATIONS :
Name :	SILATSA TEDOU Francis Brice
Address 1:	Sustainable Tropical Solution (STS Sarl), Yaoundé Cameroon, email: tropical.solutions@gmail.com)
Address 2:	The University of Dschang, Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences (FASA), Department of Soil Sciences. P.O. Box 222 <i>Dschang</i> Cameroun
Phone :	(+237) 696138702
Email :	silatsat@yahoo.fr
Nationality :	Cameroonian
Date of birth :	August 1985
Marital status:	Married
	PERSONAL SUMMARY :
	<p>My goal is to empower the society with good quality and easily available and interpretable soil data and information. In this way, I could help serve, improve and achieve a very high level of service quality on the management of soil resources, as well as improving the performance in the productivity and sustainability of agricultural systems. I am excellent in communication, friendly, very committed, determined, ambitious and looking forward to playing a vital role in providing key soil information for sustainable intensification of agricultural production and climate change mitigation.</p>
	RESEARCH INTEREST :
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital soil mapping - Conventional soil mapping - Spatial soil modeling - Soil assessment - Soil fertility management - Sustainable intensification of agriculture - Soil organic carbon stocks and Dynamics - Biomass estimation - Soil pollution

	WORK EXPERIENCE :
Jun. 2019 to Dec. 2019 :	Local soil expert
Name and address of the employer:	Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR), (Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources), Geozentrum Hannover Stilleweg 2, D-30655 Hannover. Project on Soil and Subsoil Ressources of North and South-West Regions (PRESS NO & SW) in Cameroon.
Main activities and responsibilities :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning, coordination, preparation, and execution of soil-related project activities (e.g. report compiling, workshops, exchange fora) based on project objectives and internal deadlines; - Supporting the project team and external consultants with pedological expertise during project training and workshops; - Follow-up analysis and harmonization of acquired soil and soil relevant data for soil map development; - Development of spatial information products characterizing soil and land qualities and technical reporting; - Coordination and compilation of an applied handbook on soil mapping strategies and approaches in collaboration with relevant project partners; - Representation of the project on national and international soil-related platforms e.g. conferences, (project) workshops PRESS NO & SW's monitoring & evaluation and reporting; - Provision of pedological consultancy to partners concerning the execution of soil-related studies; - Supporting the realization of regular meetings of IRAD's soil coordination group.
Oct. 2018 to Nov. 2018 :	Development of the Cameroon ecosystems monitoring guide
Name and address of the employer:	Green Orange Group P.O. Box: 5396 Yaoundé – Cameroon;
Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of Soil Indicators for Soil Monitoring in Cameroon's Ecosystems - the proposition of methodologies for assessing and monitoring these indicators in each ecosystem in Cameroon
Sep. 2018 to Jan. 2019	Preparation, execution, and post-processing of a field training and a field campaign for data collection and soil assessment using WRB in selected pilot zones in the North Region of Cameroon
Name and address of the employer :	Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR), (Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources), Geozentrum Hannover Stilleweg 2, D-30655 Hannover Project on Soil and Subsoil Ressources of North and South-West Regions (PRESS NO & SW) in Cameroon.

Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Literature review on existing information, data for the pilot zone(s) and field methodology; - Review of existing data with Algorithms for Quantitative Pedology (AQP); - Identification and predetermination of the pilot zone(s) and sampling sites; - Feasibility and risk assessment; - Simulation of potential sampling locations; - Supervision of field workgroups; - Stand-by duty in turn with project staff; - Organization of transports (participants, material, samples, etc.) and professional sample storage; - Thematic mapping; - Reporting.
Apr. 2017 to Aug. 2017 :	Digital Soil Mapping as a Strategy for Regional Land Use Planning in the North and Southwest Regions in Cameroon.
Name and address of employer :	Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR), (Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources), Geozentrum Hannover Stilleweg 2, D-30655 Hannover Project on Soil and Subsoil Resources of North and South-West Regions (PRESS NO & SW) in Cameroon.
Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	<p>Provide geospatially and harmonized soil data for the North and Southwest Regions that can assist in decision-making, coordinated and sustainable development planning in these two regions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment and enrichment of geo-spatial databases of soil properties (pH-water, pH-KCl, organic carbon, CEC, sand, silt and clay, exchangeable bases, saturation in bases, and Phosphorus) for the North and South-West regions in Cameroon; - Develop a methodology for digital mapping of soil properties in these two regions; - Test the methodology with some basic soil properties (pH-water, organic carbon, sand, silt, and clay); - Map the spatial distribution of these soil properties in the North and South-West regions at 250m resolution; - Proposal of a sampling strategy in both regions for the improvement of the prediction results; - Drafting and submission of the report.
Jan. 2017 to Apr. 2017 :	Digital Soil Mapping (DSM)
Name and address of employer:	International Soil Reference Information Centre (ISRIC), Droevendaalsesteeg 3, 6708 PB Wageningen, The Netherlands.
Position :	Guest researcher

Main activities and responsibilities :	Establishment of the Cameroon soil properties database (Camsodat 0.1), and digital mapping of soil properties. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Harmonization and standardization of legacy soil profiles data (1300 profiles) from Cameroon; ✓ Organizing and structuring the database; ✓ Data analysis for characterization of spatial variability of soil properties in Cameroon; ✓ Spatial modeling of the distribution of soil properties in Cameroon (Soil organic carbon and soil pH).
Jan. 2016 to Dec. 2016 :	Project: Green innovation Centre for the Agriculture and Food Sector (ProCISA)
Name and address of employer:	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA - Cameroun) ; PB. 2008 Messa, Yaoundé, Cameroon.
Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	Evaluation and characterization of soil fertility in the main cocoa production basins in South-West (Konye and Muyuka) and Centre (Ayos and Bokito) regions in Cameroon; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Assessment of the soil fertility of cocoa farms in the major's production areas; ✓ Establishment and follow-up of the experimental design of cocoa fertilization in farmer's plots (mineral fertilization) and on station (mineral fertilization and organic fertilization); ✓ Data collection and analyses ; ✓ Assistance in reporting.
Jan. 2015 to Dec. 2015 :	Project: Alternative to Slash and Burn (ASB)
Name and address of employer :	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA - Cameroun); BP: 2008 Messa, Yaoundé, Cameroon
Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	Characterization of cocoa-based agroforestry systems in the Centre and South-West regions of Cameroon. Estimate the carbon stocks and assess the Spatio-temporal dynamics of carbon stocks in the shifting agricultural landscape for REDD+ process implementation in cocoa agroforestry systems. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Characterization of cocoa-based agroforestry systems in different areas and collection of baseline data; ✓ Collection and analysis of data for estimating carbon stocks in cocoa-based agro-forests, fallows and secondary forests; ✓ Modeling the temporal dynamics of evolution of carbon stocks in the different pools; ✓ Prediction of the spatial distribution of soil organic carbon 30 cm depth in Ayos.
Nov. 2014 :	COBAM project, Cameroon (Climate Change and Forest in the Congo Basin)
Name and address of employer :	Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR) <i>Cameroon</i> , BP: 2008 Yaoundé Messa, <i>Cameroun</i>

Position :	Consultant
Main activities and responsibilities :	Estimation of soil organic carbon stocks in land uses, and statistical comparison in terms of types of land use in Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), and in Rwanda.
	EDUCATION :
2015 – 2020 :	Ph.D. candidate: University of Dschang / Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences (FAAS) / Department of Soil Sciences. “Digital mapping of soil properties in Cameroon” The project seeks to use Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) methods on a certain number of prerequisites such as the availability and the quality of legacy soil data, and the adaptability of the technologies in the context of Cameroon. The objective is to investigate the applicability of DSM for inventorying soil resources information in Cameroon, as input for sustainable agricultural development.
2010 - 2013 :	M.Sc. in Soil Science, with a specialization in “Environmental chemistry and soil fertility”, University of Dschang / Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences (FASA) / Department of Soil Science.
2008 - 2009 :	B.Sc. in Physics, with specialization in “Electronics, Electrotechnics and Automatism (EEA)”, at the University of Dschang, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics.
2006 - 2008 :	General University Studies Diploma in Physics, at the University of Dschang, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics.
2005 :	Baccalaureate in Physics and Mathematics, Bangangte High School.
	CONFERENCES AND SEMINARS :
Jul. 2017, Moscow – Russia :	International Conference "GlobalSoilMap2017", held at the RUDN University & V.V. Dokuchaev Soil Science Institute. Oral presentation on: "Digital soil mapping using national soil data for the North region of Cameroon".
Feb. 2017, Wageningen – Netherlands :	Capacity Building Seminar on Digital Soil Mapping Using Geostatistical and Machine learning Approaches (Random Forests), held at the Wageningen University.
Nov. 2016, Yaounde – Cameroon :	Training seminar on « Assessing project’s gaps to meet the VCS and CCB standards requirement for REDD+ », within the framework of the PNDP REDD+ project of the Pitoa municipality. Held in Yaounde, at IITA campus in Nkolbisson.
Jun. 2015, Yaounde – Cameroon :	15th meeting of Congo Basin Forest Partnership (CBFP) on "Congo Basin Ecosystems: Natural Capital, Producer of Economic Value and Green Growth Driver for the Well-Being of its People", held in Yaounde, Congress Center.
Aug. 2014, Yaoundé – Cameroon :	International Symposium ANAFE (African Network for Agriculture, Agroforestry and Natural Resources Education), on the topic "Agribusiness and agricultural risks management in Africa: Role of tertiary agricultural education", held in Yaounde, Hilton Hotel.

Dec. 2013, Yaounde – Cameroon :	Scientific animation workshop organized by CIRAD (Centre International de Recherche Agricole pour le Developpement), as part of the Partnership Competence Centers (PCP), held in Yaounde, Toun’Gou hotel.
Sep. 2013, Yaounde – Cameroon :	Seminar on the valorization of the results of research carried out as part of the ASB project (Alternative to Slash and Burn), held in Yaounde, at the IITA campus of Nkolbisson.
	PUBLICATIONS :
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Francis F. T. Silatsa, Martin Yemefack, Fritz O. Tabi, Gerard B. M. Heuvelink, Johan G. B. Leenaars. 2020. Assessing countrywide soil organic carbon stock using hybrid machine learning modeling and legacy soil data in Cameroon. <i>Geoderma</i> 367 114260. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2020.114260 2) Cedrick Nguemezi, Paul Tematio, Martin Yemefack, Désiré Tsozué, Francis B. T. Silatsa. 2020. Soil quality and soil fertility status in major soil groups at the Tombel area, South-West Cameroon. 6(2):e03432. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03432 3) Arrouays D., Leenaars L. G. B., Richer-de-Forges A. C., Adhikari K., Ballabio C. ... Francis B. T. Silatsa et al. 2017. Soil legacy data rescue via GlobalSoilMap and other international and national initiatives. <i>GeoResJ</i> 14 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grj.2017.06.001 4) Francis F. T. Silatsa, Heuvelink G. B. M., Yemefack M., Hengl T., Leenaars J. G. B., Wilczok C., Tabi F. O. 2017. Digital soil mapping using national soil data for the North region of Cameroon. Conference proceeding, GlobalSoilMap2017, Moscow – 2017. https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/e/9781351239707/chapters/10.1201/9781351239707-8 5) Francis B. T. Silatsa, Martin Yemefack. 2017. Digital Soil Mapping Strategies for Regional Land-use Planning in the North and South-West Regions of Cameroon. Technical report. BGR. PRESS NO & SW project. https://www.bgr.bund.de/DE/Themen/Boden/Projekte/Informationsgrundlagen-laufend/TZ-Kamerun/20190502_CMR_BGR-Report_en.html?nn=1549142 6) Francis B. T. Silatsa, Martin Yemefack, Nathalie Ewane-Nonga, Adoph Kemga, Rachid Hanna. 2017 “Modeling Carbon stock dynamics under fallow and cocoa agroforest systems in the shifting agricultural landscape of Central Cameroon” <i>Agroforestry Systems</i>. 91 (5) 993–1006. https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10457-016-9973-4 7) Francis B. T. Silatsa, M. Yemefack, H. Dameni. 2015. « Variabilité des stocks de Carbone en zone forestière du Cameroun ; approche evaluative dans le paysage agricole itinerant de la Commune d’Ayos ». Edition Universitaire Europeene. ISBN: 978–3–8417–4911–6. 8) Francis T. B. Silatsa, M. Yemefack, H. Dameni, N. Ewane-Nonga. 2014. “Variabilité spatiale du carbone organique du sol dans la Commune d’Ayos” Poster, ANAFE 2014.
	LANGUAGES SKILLS :
English :	Good
French :	Excellent

	OTHER SKILLS :
Basic informatics skills :	Office package and libre office package, Internet, Windows, Linux, etc.).
Data collection :	Knowledge of the ODK (Open Data Kit) platform for the preparation and use of questionnaires and forms for rapid data collection.
GIS :	Geographic Information systems software; QGIS, ILWIS
Statistics and spatial modeling :	Statistics and spatial modeling software, SPSS, R and Python
Driving Licence :	B
	<p>I, the undersigned, certify that the above information accurately reflects my situation, qualifications, and professional experience as of July 09, 2020.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Francis Silatsa</p> </div>